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I-WALAMAR

A joint research project funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) within the funding initiative „CLIENT II – International Partnerships for Sustainable Innovations“

I-WALAMAR

Sustainable Technologies and Services for Water and Land Resources Management in Morocco

Joint final report of the collaborative project

Funding grant number: 01LZ1807A-G

Funding period: 01.07.2019 – 31.12.2022, 30.06.2022 (valid for 01LZ1807F), 30.05.2023 (valid for 01LZ1807G)

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CLIENT II
International Partnerships for
Sustainable Innovations

Joint research project
„CLIENT II – International Partnerships
for Sustainable Innovations“

I-WALAMAR
Sustainable Technologies and Services
for Water and Land Resources Management
in Morocco

01LZ1807A-G

IMPRINT

Network coordination

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CLIENT II
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SUPERVISED BY

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Citation:

Krauss M., Abouabdillah A., Allaoui S., Badidi M., Bekri A., Bennani M., Biel M., El Hafiane F., Essahlaoui A., Grimmeisen F., Hafidi Y., Hafidi M., Hoogen H., Hruschka S., Jomaa A., Kemmerling B., Kirchhof W., Leandro M.-A., Maaroufi A., Mathyl E., Meiners G., Meissner K., Messaoudi L., Möller J., Müller J., Navarro R., Pettrak J., Ramirez J., Romuli S., Schmitz D., Spohrer K., Tabib M., Tijani N., Ouzahra L., Wirkus L., Ittobane N. (2024): Sustainable Technologies and Services for Water and Land Resources Management in Morocco. Final Report of the Joint Research Project I-WALAMAR, BMBF-Grant Number 01LZ1807A-G. FiW e.V. Aachen, Germany

Acknowledgement:

We thank our associated partners OLEAFOOD and GEA Westafalia Separator Group GmbH for their contribution and cooperation.

Funding:

The joint research project I-WALAMAR, on which this final report is based on, was funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) within the funding initiative „CLIENT II – International Partnerships for Sustainable Innovations“ (Client II) under the grant number 01LZ1807A-G. The responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors.

<https://www.bmbf-iwalamar.com/>

<https://www.fiw.rwth-aachen.de/en/references/i-walamar>

Aachen, May 2024

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AA	Antioxidant activity
ABHS	Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sebou (Agency of the Sebou Hydraulic Basin)
AUL	Absorbency under load
ASP	Aspartic acid
β CD	β -cyclodextrin
BICC	Bonn International Center for Conversion (now: Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies)
BMBF	German Federal Ministry of Education and Research
BOD5	Biological Oxygen Demand in five days
CF	Coliforms Faecal
COD	Chemical Oxygen Demand
CVG	Coefficient of variation of the germination rate
CVR	Coefficient of variation of the root length
DM	Dry matter
DMF	Dimethylformamide
EC	Electrical conductivity
EU	European Union
ENA	National School of Agriculture (École nationale d'agriculture de Meknès)
ENSAM	École nationale supérieure d'arts et métiers Meknès
ESA	European Space Agency

ETc	Crop evapotranspiration
ET0	Evapotranspiration of a reference grass surface
ETP	Effluent Treatment Plant
FHAC	University of Applied Sciences Aachen, Institute of Applied Polymer Chemistry
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FiW	Research Institute for Water Management and Climate Future
FMR	Fès-Meknès Region
FM	Fresh matter
GA	Gallic acid
GLA	Glutamic acid
GEA	GEA Westfalia Separator Group GmbH
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GIS	Geographic Information System
GMP	Green Morocco Plan (Maroc plan vert)
GPC	Gel Permeation Chromatography
HMD	Hexamethylene diamine
HPLC	High-performance liquid chromatography / High-Pressure Liquid Chromatography
HTy	Hydroxytyrosol
IAV	Institut Agronomique et Vétérinaire HASSAN II (Agricultural and veterinarian institute)
IAP	Institut für Angewandte Prozesstechnik der FH Aachen
INDH	National Initiative for Human Development

INNOAGRI	inno agri GmbH, Alpen
IR	Infra red spectroscopy
IWRM	Integrated Water Resources Management
Kc	Crop Coefficient
LULC	Land use land cover
MAH	Maleic Anhydride
MFA	Material flow analysis
Mm ³	Million cubic meter
MLV	Munoo-Liisa-Vitality indexes
MO	Methyl orange
MR	Marrakesch Region
MW	Megawatt
OLR	organic loading rate
OLEAFOOD	Name of Moroccan Project Partner
OMW	Olive Mill Waste
OMWW	Olive Mill Wastewater
ONEE (Fès)	Office National de l'Electricité et de l'Eau Potable (Fès) (National Office of Electricity and Drinking Water)
OPC	Olive press cake
OPW	Olive pomace waste
ORP	Oxidation reduction potential
PAH	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
PASP	Poly (aspartic acid)

p.e.	Population equivalent = daily wastewater load, 1 p.e. expressed as 60 g BOD ₅ per day
PP	Poly-phenol
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
PSI	Pound-force per square inch, 100 psi = 6.89 bar
PT	Phosphate total
RADEM	(Fr.) Rgion Autonomie de Distribution eau et electricit Mekks
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway
SEBA	SEBA Hydrometrie GmbH & Co. KG
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy
SHBA	Hydraulic Basin Agency of Sass
SNK	Student-Newman-Keuls
SIS	Soil improving substrate
SMY	specific methane yield
SSMK	Sidi Slimane Moul Al Kifane Region
STEP	Waste Water Treatment Plant
TDS	Total dissolved substances
TPC	Total phenolic content
TRMM	Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission
TS	Total solids
TSS	Total suspended substances
TY	Tyrosol
UAA	Utilised Agricultural Area

UHOH	University Hohenheim
UMI	Université Moulay Ismail
UN-SDG	UN Sustainable Goals
UR	Urea
UV	Ultra-violet
VFA	Volatile fatty acids
VS	Volatile solids
WEAP	Water Evaluation Analysis Planning System
WHC	Water holding capacity
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work package
WR	Water Resource
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant

Note: In this report, we use English SI number format (with decimal point instead of comma).

Executive Summary

Water and food security are becoming increasingly important issues in the Maghreb. The region is currently facing one of the worst seasonal droughts in decades. Against the backdrop of growing water scarcity and the importance of the agricultural sector, the aim of the Moroccan-German research project I-WALAMAR is to identify and test ways of using resources more efficiently and at the same time increasing water and food security. Research area is the Fès and Meknès Region (FMR), where around 30 percent of olive cultivation is located. In the FMR as well, water resources are being depleted and land degradation is increasing.

The FMR is one of the most important regions in Morocco for the production of olives and olive oil. Olive oil is produced in traditional and modern mills and the olive trees are planted in traditional as well as intensive and super-intensive plantations. These mills produce solid and liquid wastes, which can be used, after treatment, as resources for improving water and food security. The characteristics of olive mill wastewater (OMWW), margine, depend on the production system. The wastewater consists mainly of water and organic material and it is rich in fertilizing material and also contains phenols.

The direct reuse of margine as a fertilizer in agriculture is possible and applied in some of the smaller mills, but application must be limited and research is needed to investigate the effect on soil and agricultural products. Phenolic compounds in margine could be extracted from margine and reused. They can also be adsorbed or filtered to improve the reuse possibilities of the olive mill wastewater in agriculture. Olive mill wastewater is subjected to be discharged in evaporation ponds, where the water evaporates over the summer months.

The solid wastes (sludges) from the olive mills are also stored in evaporation basins, while the cernells are used to generate heat which is internally used.

Agriculture is one of the main users of water and in the last 20 years the groundwater level has fallen by around 60 m indicating a non-sustainable use of the water resources. The discharge of untreated olive mill wastewater is polluting the water resources especially in the winter months, when the olive mills are in operation.

Around 54,000 hectares of olive orchards can be found in the FMR. Around 5,000 hectares are managed traditionally. 29,000 hectares are managed super intensive with a spacing of 3 - 5 m between trees and 20,000 hectares are managed super intensive with a tree-spacing of 1 - 2 m. Super intensive olive farming systems are normally irrigated. A comparison between land use in 2010 and 2020 shows that there is a trend toward higher spatial concentration and larger plot sizes.

There have been several reforms to restructure the agricultural sector in Morocco. A key driver has been to become less dependent on cereal imports. Irrigation patterns and crop types have changed and increased overall. The main challenges are the increasing demand and

decreasing availability of water and the degradation of agricultural land. With innovations in water and land management, treated waste resources in the FMR can be used to increase agricultural productivity, protect the environment and adapt to climate change.

The water quality of the Sebou has deteriorated, especially downstream from Fès to the estuary, due to the adverse effects of the many sources of pollution. The Sebou's drinking water treatment plants often stop operating, especially during periods of extreme pollution between December and February (olive harvest). Fish mortality is also common. Poor water quality is also observed in the Oued Inaouen downstream of Meknés.

Municipal wastewater management in the FMR is largely carried out by the wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) of Meknés and Fés, which collect, treat and discharge almost 90% of the FMR's total wastewater volume into the Sebou river system. As an example, the impact on river water quality of the WWTP of Ain Taoujdate, a medium-sized WWTP, was assessed. The results of the analysis do not indicate severe pollution at the point of discharge, but do indicate that there are additional sources of wastewater upstream of the WWTP.

Investigations at the Ain Taoujdate wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) and the nearby river indicate that the effluent from the WWTP complies with category B standards established by the World Health Organization (WHO) for water reuse in agriculture. Category B permits irrigation of cereal and fodder crops. By reusing water from the WWTP Ain Taoujdate, approximately 4,800 hectares of land could be irrigated, providing 14.5 tons of nitrogen, 6.9 tons of phosphorus, and 9.3 tons of potassium. The results indicate a high potential for direct and indirect reuse of wastewater. It is important to thoroughly monitor the microbiological parameters to ensure they are met. Additionally, farmers must be educated on how to safely irrigate with treated wastewater. It is safe to reuse sewage sludge in agriculture after it has been stored for over a year.

The olive oil sector is expanding its capacity to meet the national strategic goal. Larger mills are being introduced, and three different production methods are used: 'pressing', '3-phase decanter', and '2-phase decanter'. Switching from the 3-phase decanter to the 2-phase decanter process reduces water requirements by approximately 50% and doubles the concentration of pollutants in the wastewater. The estimated total wastewater load from olive mills is approximately 2.5 times the total design capacity of municipal wastewater treatment plants. This can lead to an overload of these plants, resulting in a significant decline in the quality of the effluent water and severe pollution of the receiving water bodies. It is important to note that OMWW is only produced during November to February.

Innovation to increase water and food security in the Fès-Meknès region through the use of olive oil industry residues, municipal wastewater treatment plants and agricultural innovations has been explored and tested in the I-WALAMAR project.

To enhance understanding of the recovery and removal of various phenols from olive industry residues, we adapted an HPLC analyzer to meet the specific needs of phenol analysis in Meknès and trained the scientific staff in its use. We can now identify, determine, and extract different phenol fractions from various material streams. Our measurement methodology has been successfully applied in various scientific studies.

A water monitoring station has been successfully developed to continuously determine the amount of olive mill wastewater in the influent of wastewater treatment plants or in water bodies. Various tests were carried out at the Stolberg wastewater treatment plant near Aachen, Germany, and at the Aachen University of Applied Sciences laboratory to calibrate a sensor for the analysis of olive oil wastewater for the first time. The monitoring station will be installed in a wastewater treatment plant in Morocco and will measure in addition to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) the parameters water level, temperature, conductivity, salinity, TDS, pH, water density, turbidity and TSS.

A water quality monitoring program and an exemplary pollution cadaster for olive mills have been developed. The Water Management Model WEAP was set-up for the Saïss Plain aquifer and four river basins of the FMR. Besides the current account scenario, five additional scenarios were integrated. These are the “Climate change scenario”, “population growth scenario”, “Land use change scenario”, the “Olive sector development scenario” and the “Water Infrastructure Project scenario” integrating the dam M’Dez. This enables the water management authority ABHS in cooperation with UMI to use and adapt the monitoring program and mathematical model for evidence-based decision making.

Investigations regarding the optimization of the 2-phase decanter process, to get a phenol-enriched phase by increasing the pH to 9-11 are very encouraging. The resulting phenol-enriched phase is a promising source for natural substances containing antioxidative and antimicrobial properties for food additives or used as oxidation protection and antimicrobial additive in materials. Most important is the use of fresh pomace to obtain phenol-enriched substances.

Tubular membranes based on a clay from the Meknès region have been developed. The clay powder obtained after crushing and sieving was characterized by several experimental techniques to understand its behaviour according to the thermal treatment. This powder is used for the manufacture of tubular membranes of high mechanical, chemical and purifying performances. The membranes could be successfully used for the filtration of a dye (Methyl Orange). The usage of these membranes is promising for increasing the quality of municipal wastewaters by pretreatment of wastewaters from the leather or textile industry.

Beside membrane filtration, the adsorption of polyphenols on β -cyclodextrin (β CD)-modified materials was evaluated. The general procedure for this work was an analysis of β CD-complexes, synthesis and characterization of β CD-containing materials and uptake studies with polyphenols from olive wastewater. The general procedure was the crosslinking of β CD with

the compound epichlorohydrin (EP) in basic aqueous medium – in presence of Ghassoul clay or ground olive stone, respectively. This results in β CD-containing crosslinked polymer or corresponding composite with the above-mentioned natural materials. All materials lead to reduction of polyphenol concentration. Among the used model polyphenols, Hydroxytyrosol has the highest amount in the untreated wastewater followed by Oleuropein and Tyrosol. After treatment, the amount of the phenolic compounds decreases with usage of all samples. Polymer and polymer-modified Ghassoul as well as a Ghassoul-polymer mixture showed the best results in adsorption of the selected polyphenols.

We developed and implemented a solar powered agro-meteorological station system to increase the up-to-date distribution of weather parameters to the farmer communities in the study area.

Olive mill wastes and wastewater were assessed for its application as biogas feed material. Especially the dry waste material (pomace) showed high biogas yield with 178.6 l per kg added fresh mass (FM) according to the Hohenheim biogas yield protocol. Continuous biogas fermentation trials in digesters with 700 l and 560 l were performed. The experiment was run for 148 days in a row after months of pre-test. For the first 50 days the average specific methane yield (SMY) from olive pomace (without stone) was more than 395 L kgVS while feeding at OLR of 1.0 kgVS m⁻³ d⁻¹. The composition of methane in the biogas was 60 % - 65 %, which is common in substrates rich in fats/oils (VDI 4630). However, in the subsequent days of experiment the SMY declined steadily to the completion of the experiment. In the same way, the methane composition of the biogas was declined from peak value 72 % to 32 %. It seems that the increase in the concentration of sinapic acid might be one of the causes for the decline of the methane formation in the digester. Another reason for the decline of the biogas formation might be the deficiency of trace metals in the substrate itself. Thus, co-fermentation with other substrates, especially animal manure, seems to be promising. Co-fermentation of horse manure with liquid olive mill wastewater (margine) was successful. Biogas yields of 315 L/kg VS for horse manure and 120 L/kg VS for the co-digestion of margines highlight their viability as valuable feedstocks for anaerobic digestion. The methane content of 73 % for horse manure and 80 % for the co-digestion of margines indicates the high purity of the biogas, making it suitable for energy applications. These results emphasize the importance of exploring organic waste sources for biogas generation, contributing to the shift towards renewable energy and reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

As part of the work package “soil improving additives”, the aim was to develop hydrogel-based soil additives, which act as a water saving reservoir for soils in mainly arid regions as in the Fès-Meknès area. The water absorbing properties make hydrogels interesting for saving and using the resource water effectively, enable plant cultivation and improve plant health and growth. The main goal was the development and synthesis of hydrogels based on poly(aspartic acid) (PASP) as a new alternative to poly(acrylic acid)-based products for future commercial

products. PASP provide the possibility to obtain main reactants from renewable resources in contrast to mineral oil resources and reported better biodegradability in contrast to the reported poor degradability of poly(acrylic acid). The main result is the formation of hydrogel from the PASP/LYS copolymer without additional crosslinking. This eliminates an additional reaction and work-up step in the reaction. Based on this, the reaction needs further optimization (already from copolymerization of ASP and LYS) but is very promising regarding ecological and economic aspects. Biodegradability was analyzed and pot-experiments of PASP-based products showed good results in comparison to PAA-based hydrogels. The work done on this polymer type as a soil additive in the project I-WALAMAR can be considered successful. Nevertheless, further work must be done; main aspects are price, upscaling, reaction optimization (solvent-free, „green“) and fine-tuning for specific site-dependent properties. Tests at UHOH showed that the water-holding capacity of the developed hydrogels proved to be equal to those available in the market. Moreover, the results showed that the tested hydrogel types had no phytotoxic effect on cress germination and seedling growth. Furthermore, moistening the substrates with different concentrations of OMWW, especially those containing low phenolic content, seems to be safe for agricultural use.

Trials were conducted to investigate whether the use of OMWW in a drip irrigation system leads to clogging of the irrigation drippers and/or purification filters. The results showed that there was no significant change in flow rate (FR) between OMWW concentrations of 30% and 50%. Additionally, no visible blockages were observed at the irrigation drippers during all experimental runs. Regarding the leakage of phenols from OMWW, based on quantitative analysis of the percolate, the one-time use of volumes of OMWW up to 120 m³ ha⁻¹ on slightly loamy sand, given a groundwater level lower than 1 m, does not pose a short-term risk of groundwater contamination.

Field trials were performed over two years to investigate the impact of the contribution of margins as soil additives on onion and melon crops, by determining the optimal dose of margins to obtain an optimal yield in terms of quantity and quality. The total plot area used for this study was 880 m² for both years; it was prepared to accommodate a complete randomized block design. The dosages tested were “T1 : No OMWW added”, “T2 : OMWW dose = 140 L = 25 m³/ha”, “T3 : OMWW dose = 280 L = 50 m³/ha” and “T4 : OMWW dose = 420 L = 75 m³/ha”. We can conclude that the use of margins has affected the physiological parameters in the first year of trial, contrary to the yield, where no effect was found. On the other hand, in the second year of the trial, the physiological parameters were not affected. However, there was an increment in yield with the addition of higher margin doses. Regardless, this can only be confirmed after a third year, as it takes time for mineralization to determine the actual effect of margins on the soil characteristics.

Hydrogels have been applied as an amendment product to increase the water-holding capacity of the soil on field trials at ENA in Meknès. It can be noted that the use of hydrogels without

deficit irrigation resulted in an increase of 27 % in yield compared to the control treatment irrigated with 100 % of water requirements for the melon crop and an increase of 18 % for the onion crop. Furthermore, the deficit treatments with 50 % ETc combined with hydrogel application, showed an increase in yield by 13 % compared to the deficit control treatment with 50 % ETc and no hydrogel application for the melon crop and 12 % increase for the onion crop. From this result, it is confirmed that the amount of hydrogel added has a significant impact on the increase of melon production even in the presence of a water deficit of 50 % compared to the control treatments. Hydrogels allowed water saving without affecting the yield. Additional experiments with hydrogels, that were performed in a greenhouse, supported the conclusion, that a 50% deficit irrigation can be compensated with the application of hydrogels.

Equipment is available for the application of alternative substrates and for soil preparation applications such as stone removal or hardpan destruction. These machines can be combined for multifunctional use and adapted to the required size and performance. For small farms or farmers, it is advisable to collaborate in cooperatives, service companies, and share machines. This report provides a guide for selecting the appropriate land application technique for developed soil additives.

The I-WALAMAR results demonstrate the potential for reusing waste and wastewater streams, as well as innovative soil additives like hydrogels with enhanced biodegradability, to improve water and food security in the FMR. The study shows how these streams can be treated and safely applied to agriculture, enhancing the population's resilience to climate change. Appropriate land application technologies and biogas production from the waste stream can contribute to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.

Zusammenfassung

Die Themen der Wasser- und Ernährungssicherheit werden im Maghreb immer wichtiger. Die Region ist derzeit mit einer der schlimmsten saisonalen Dürren seit Jahrzehnten konfrontiert. Vor dem Hintergrund der zunehmenden Wasserknappheit und der Bedeutung des Agrarsektors besteht das Ziel des marokkanisch-deutschen Forschungsprojekts I-WALAMAR darin, Möglichkeiten für eine effizientere Ressourcennutzung zu ermitteln und zu erproben und gleichzeitig die Wasser- und Ernährungssicherheit zu erhöhen. Untersuchungsgebiet ist die Region Fès und Meknès (FMR), in der rund 30 Prozent des Olivenanbau Marokkos angesiedelt sind. Auch in der FMR sind die Wasserressourcen knapp und die Bodendegradation nimmt zu.

Die FMR ist eine der wichtigsten Regionen Marokkos für die Erzeugung von Oliven und Olivenöl. Olivenöl wird in traditionellen und modernen Mühlen hergestellt, und die Olivenbäume werden sowohl in traditionellen als auch in intensiven und superintensiven Plantagen angebaut.

Die Ölmühlen produzieren feste und flüssige Abwässer, die nach der Behandlung als Rohstoffe zur Verbesserung der Wasser- und Ernährungssicherheit genutzt werden können. Die Eigenschaften der Abwässer aus den Ölmühlen hängen vom jeweiligen Produktionssystem ab. Das Abwasser besteht hauptsächlich aus Wasser und organischem Material und ist reich an Düngemitteln und Phenolen.

Die direkte Wiederverwendung von Abwässern als Düngemittel in der Landwirtschaft ist möglich und wird in einigen kleineren Mühlen angewandt, wobei die Anwendung begrenzt werden muss und Forschungsarbeiten erforderlich sind, um die Auswirkungen auf den Boden und die landwirtschaftlichen Erzeugnisse zu untersuchen. Die in den Abwässern enthaltenen phenolischen Verbindungen könnten aus den Abwässern extrahiert und wiederverwendet werden. In der Region werden die Abwässer der Olivenmühlen in Becken eingeleitet, in denen das Wasser in den Sommermonaten verdunstet. Die Schlämme aus den Olivenmühlen werden ebenfalls in Verdunstungsbecken gelagert, während die Kerne zur Erzeugung von Wärme verwendet und verbrannt werden.

Die Landwirtschaft ist einer der wichtigsten Wasserverbraucher. In den letzten 20 Jahren ist der Grundwasserspiegel um etwa 60 m gesunken, was auf eine nicht nachhaltige Nutzung der Wasserressourcen hindeutet. Die Einleitung von ungeklärten Abwässern aus den Olivenmühlen verschmutzt die Wasserressourcen vor allem in den Wintermonaten, wenn die Olivenmühlen in Betrieb sind.

In der FMR gibt es rund 54,000 Hektar Olivenhaine. Rund 5,000 Hektar werden traditionell bewirtschaftet, 29,000 Hektar superintensiv mit einem Abstand von 3 - 5 m zwischen den Bäumen und 20,000 Hektar superintensiv mit einem Baumabstand von 1 - 2 m. Superintensive

Olivenanbausysteme werden in der Regel bewässert. Ein Vergleich zwischen der Flächennutzung 2010 und 2020 zeigt, dass es einen Trend zu einem geringeren Baumabstand und größeren Parzellen gibt.

In Marokko wurden mehrere Reformen zur Umgestaltung des Agrarsektors durchgeführt. Einer der Hauptfaktoren ist eine größere Unabhängigkeit von Getreideeinfuhren. Die Bewässerungssysteme und die Art der Nutzpflanzen haben sich geändert und die Erträge sind insgesamt gestiegen. Die größten Herausforderungen sind der steigende Wasserbedarf und die abnehmende Verfügbarkeit von Wasser sowie die degradierten landwirtschaftlichen Flächen. Mit Innovationen in der Wasser- und Bodenbewirtschaftung können die aufbereiteten Abfallstoffe im FMR zur Steigerung der landwirtschaftlichen Produktivität, zum Schutz der Umwelt und zur Anpassung an den Klimawandel genutzt werden.

Die Wasserqualität des Sebou hat sich verschlechtert, insbesondere flussabwärts von Fès bis zur Mündung, was auf zahlreiche Schadstoffquellen zurückzuführen ist. Die Trinkwasseraufbereitungsanlagen am Sebou unterbrechen häufig ihre Tätigkeit, insbesondere in den Zeiten extremer Wasserverschmutzung (Dezember-Februar während der Olivenernte). Auch Fischsterben wird häufig beobachtet. Schlechte Wasserqualität wird auch im Oued Inaouene flussabwärts von Meknès beobachtet.

Das kommunale Abwassermanagement in der FMR erfolgt maßgeblich in den Kläranlagen von Meknès und Fés, wo etwa 90 % der Gesamtabwassermenge der FMR erfasst, behandelt und in das Flusssystem des Sebou eingeleitet werden. Exemplarisch wurden die Auswirkungen der Kläranlage von Ain Taoujdate, einer Kläranlage mittlerer Größe, auf die Wasserqualität des Flusses untersucht. Die Analyseergebnisse deuten nicht auf eine wesentliche Verschmutzung an der Einleitungsstelle durch die Kläranlage hin, sondern zeigen, dass es bereits stromaufwärts der Kläranlage weitere signifikante Abwassereinträge gibt.

Die Untersuchungen an der Kläranlage Ain Taoujdate und des nahe gelegenen Flusses zeigen, dass das Abwasser der Kläranlage der Kategorie B der von der WHO festgelegten Normen zur Wiederverwendung von gereinigtem Abwasser in der Landwirtschaft entspricht. In dieser Kategorie wäre die Bewässerung von Getreide und Futterpflanzen möglich. Mit der Wiederverwendung von Wasser aus der Kläranlage Ain Taoujdate könnten rund 4,800 ha Land bewässert werden mit einer Nährstoffbereitstellung von 14,5 t Stickstoff, 6,9 t Phosphor und 9,3 t Kalium. Die Ergebnisse zeigen das hohe Potenzial für die direkte und indirekte Wiederverwendung von Abwasser. Es muss jedoch sorgfältig kontrolliert werden, ob die mikrobiologischen Grenzwerte eingehalten werden. Landwirte müssen darüber aufgeklärt werden, wie sie mit behandeltem Abwasser sicher bewässern können. Klärschlamm könnte nach einer ordnungsgemäßen Lagerung von mehr als einem Jahr sicher in der Landwirtschaft wiederverwendet werden.

Der marokkanische Olivenölsektor erweitert seine Produktionskapazitäten, um das nationale Ausbauziel zu erreichen. Es findet eine Umstellung auf größere Mühlen statt und es werden drei verschiedene Produktionsarten eingesetzt: 'Pressen', '3-Phasen-Dekanter' und '2-Phasen-Dekanter'. Die Umstellung vom 3-Phasen-Dekanter auf den 2-Phasen-Dekanter führt zu einer Verringerung des Wasserbedarfs um etwa 50 %. Die Schadstoffkonzentration des Abwassers verdoppelt sich jedoch. Die Gesamtabwasserbelastung durch Olivenmühlen wird auf das 2,5-fache der Gesamtkapazität kommunaler Kläranlagen geschätzt. Da OMWW jedoch nur zwischen November und Februar anfällt, kann dies zu einer Überlastung der kommunalen Kläranlagen führen. Dies wiederum führt zu einer erheblichen Verschlechterung der Wasserqualität des Abwassers und somit zu einer starken Verschmutzung der aufnehmenden Gewässer.

Die Verbesserung der Wasser- und Ernährungssicherheit in der Region Fès-Meknès mithilfe von Rückständen aus der Olivenölindustrie, kommunalen Kläranlagen und Innovationen in der Landwirtschaft wurde im Rahmen des Projekts I-WALAMAR untersucht und erprobt.

Um die Erkenntnisse über die Rückgewinnung und Entfernung verschiedener Phenole aus Rückständen der Olivenölindustrie zu verbessern, wurde ein HPLC-Analysegerät an die spezifischen Anforderungen der Phenolanalyse adaptiert, in Meknes implementiert und das wissenschaftliche Personal in der Anwendung geschult. Verschiedene Phenolfractionen können nun identifiziert, bestimmt und aus verschiedenen Materialströmen extrahiert werden. Die Messmethodik wurde in verschiedenen wissenschaftlichen Studien erfolgreich angewendet.

Es wurde erfolgreich eine Messstation zur kontinuierlichen Bestimmung des Anteils von Olivenölabwasser im Zulauf von Kläranlagen oder in Gewässern entwickelt. Hierfür wurden in der Kläranlage Stolberg bei Aachen und im Labor der Fachhochschule Aachen verschiedene Tests durchgeführt, um erstmals einen Sensor für die Analyse von Olivenölabwässern zu kalibrieren. In einer Kläranlage in Marokko wird eine Messstation installiert. Diese misst neben den polyzyklischen aromatischen Kohlenwasserstoffen (PAK) auch die Parameter Wasserstand, Temperatur, Leitfähigkeit, Salzgehalt, TDS, pH-Wert, Wasserdichte, Trübung und TSS.

Es wurde ein Programm zur Überwachung der Wasserqualität entwickelt und ein exemplarisches Verschmutzungskataster für Olivenmühlen erstellt. Zudem wurde das Wasserbewirtschaftungsmodell WEAP für den Aquifer der Saïss-Ebene und vier Flusseinzugsgebiete der FMR erstellt. Es wurden fünf weitere Szenarien integriert, neben dem Status-quo Szenario. Es handelt sich um die Szenarien 'Klimawandel', 'Bevölkerungswachstum', 'Landnutzungsänderung', 'Entwicklung des Olivensektors' und 'Wasserinfrastrukturprojekt' mit dem Staudamm M'Dez. Die Wasserwirtschaftsbehörde ABHS kann in Zusammenarbeit mit der UMI das Monitoringprogramm und das Wassermanagementmodell nutzen und anpassen, um evidenzbasierte Entscheidungen zu treffen.

Die Untersuchungen zur Optimierung des 2-Phasen-Dekanter-Prozesses, um eine mit Phenol angereicherte Phase durch Erhöhung des pH-Werts auf 9-11 zu erhalten, sind sehr vielversprechend. Die resultierende phenolangereicherte Phase ist eine vielversprechende Ressource, um natürliche Substanzen mit antioxidativen und antimikrobiellen Eigenschaften für Lebensmittelzusatzstoffe oder als Oxidationsschutz und antimikrobieller Zusatz in Materialien zu gewinnen. Am wichtigsten hierbei ist die Verwendung von frischem Oliventrester zur Gewinnung phenolangereicherter Phasen.

Es wurden Membranen auf Basis von Ton aus der Region Meknes entwickelt. Das Tonpulver, welches durch Zerkleinern und Sieben gewonnen wurde, wurde durch verschiedene experimentelle Verfahren charakterisiert, um sein Verhalten bei thermischer Verarbeitung zu bestimmen. Das Pulver wird zur Herstellung von röhrenförmigen Membranen mit hohen mechanischen, chemischen und filtrierenden Eigenschaften verwendet. Die Membranen wurden erfolgreich zur Filtration von Methylorange eingesetzt. Ihr Einsatz verspricht eine Verbesserung der Qualität von kommunalen Abwässern durch die Vorbehandlung von Abwässern aus der Leder- oder Textilindustrie.

Neben der Membranfiltration wurde auch die Adsorption von Polyphenolen an β -Cyclodextrin (β CD)-modifizierten Materialien untersucht. Das allgemeine Verfahren für diese Arbeit war die Analyse von β CD-Komplexen, die Synthese und Charakterisierung von β CD-haltigen Materialien und Untersuchungen zur Aufnahme von Polyphenolen aus Olivenabwässern. Das allgemeine Verfahren war die Vernetzung von β CD mit der Verbindung Epichlorhydrin (EP) in basischem wässrigem Medium - in Gegenwart von Ghassoul-Ton bzw. gemahlene Olivenkernen. Das Ergebnis ist ein β CD-haltiges vernetztes Polymer oder ein entsprechendes Komposit mit den oben genannten natürlichen Materialien. Alle Materialien führen zu einer Verringerung der Polyphenolkonzentration. Unter den verwendeten Polyphenolen hat Hydroxytyrosol den höchsten Anteil im unbehandelten Abwasser, gefolgt von Oleuropein und Tyrosol. Nach der Behandlung nimmt die Menge der phenolischen Verbindungen mit der Verwendung aller Proben ab. Polymere und polymermodifiziertes Ghassoul sowie ein Ghassoul-Polymer-Gemisch zeigten die besten Ergebnisse bei der Adsorption der ausgewählten Polyphenole.

Eine solarbetriebene agrometeorologische Station wurde entwickelt und implementiert, um die Landwirte im Untersuchungsgebiet besser mit aktuellen Wetterdaten versorgen zu können.

Abfälle und Abwässer aus Olivenmühlen wurden auf ihre Eignung als Biogas-Einsatzmaterial untersucht. Insbesondere die trockenen Abfälle (Trester) zeigten mit 178,6 l pro kg zugesetzter Frischmasse (FM) einen hohen Biogasertrag nach dem Hohenheimer Biogasertragsprotokoll. Es wurden kontinuierliche Biogasvergärungsversuche in Fermentern mit 700 l und 560 l durchgeführt. Der Versuch wurde nach einem monatelangen Vorversuch 148 Tage am Stück durchgeführt. In den ersten 50 Tagen betrug der durchschnittliche spezifische Methanertrag (SMY) aus Oliventrester (ohne Steine) mehr als 395 l kgVS bei einer Beschickung von 1,0 kgVS m-

3 d-1. Die Zusammensetzung des Methans im Biogas betrug 60 % - 65 %, was bei fett-/ölreichen Substraten üblich ist (VDI 4630). In den folgenden Versuchstagen nahm der SMY jedoch bis zum Ende des Versuchs stetig ab. Auf die gleiche Weise sank die Methanzusammensetzung des Biogases von einem Spitzenwert von 72 % auf 32 %. Es scheint, dass der Anstieg der Konzentration von Sinapinsäure eine der Ursachen für den Rückgang der Methanbildung im Fermenter sein könnte. Einer der Gründe für den Rückgang der Biogasbildung könnte auch der Mangel an Spurenmetallen im Substrat selbst sein. Daher scheint die Co-Fermentation mit anderen Substraten, insbesondere mit Tiermist, vielversprechend zu sein. Auch die Co-Fermentation von Pferdemit mit flüssigen Olivenmühlenabwässern (Margine) war erfolgreich. Biogaserträge von 315 l/kg VS für Pferdemit und 120 l/kg VS für die Co-Vergärung von Margine unterstreichen deren Eignung als wertvolle Ausgangsstoffe für die anaerobe Vergärung. Der Methangehalt von 73 % bei Pferdemit und 80 % bei der Co-Fermentation von Margen weist auf die hohe Reinheit des Biogases hin, wodurch es sich für energetische Anwendungen eignet. Diese Ergebnisse unterstreichen die Bedeutung der Erforschung organischer Abfallquellen für die Biogaserzeugung und tragen zur Umstellung auf erneuerbare Energien und zur Verringerung der Treibhausgasemissionen bei.

Im Rahmen des Arbeitspakets " Bodenverbesserung" war das Ziel, Bodenhilfsstoffe auf Hydrogelbasis zu entwickeln, die als Wasserspeicher für Böden in überwiegend trockenen Regionen wie in der Region Fès-Meknès dienen. Die wasserabsorbierenden Eigenschaften machen Hydrogele für die Einsparung und effektive Nutzung der Ressource Wasser interessant, ermöglichen den Pflanzenanbau und verbessern die Pflanzengesundheit und das Pflanzenwachstum. Das Hauptziel war die Entwicklung und Synthese von Hydrogelen auf der Basis von Poly(asparaginsäure) (PASP) als neue Alternative zu Produkten auf der Basis von Poly(acrylsäure) für zukünftige kommerzielle Produkte. PASP bieten die Möglichkeit, die Hauptbestandteile aus erneuerbaren Ressourcen zu gewinnen, im Gegensatz zu Mineralölressourcen, und weisen eine bessere biologische Abbaubarkeit auf, im Gegensatz zur schlechten Abbaubarkeit von Poly(acrylsäure). Das wichtigste Ergebnis ist die Herstellung eines Hydrogels aus dem PASP/LYS-Copolymer ohne zusätzliche Vernetzung, wodurch ein zusätzlicher Reaktions- und Aufarbeitungsschritt in der Reaktion entfällt. Die Reaktion muss daher noch weiter optimiert werden, ist aber unter ökologischen und ökonomischen Aspekten sehr vielversprechend. Die biologische Abbaubarkeit wurde analysiert, und Topfversuche mit PASP-basierten Produkten zeigten gute Ergebnisse im Vergleich zu PAA-basierten Hydrogelen. Die im Rahmen des Projekts I-WALAMAR durchgeführten Arbeiten zu diesem Polymertyp als Bodenhilfsstoff können als erfolgreich angesehen werden. Dennoch müssen weitere Arbeiten durchgeführt werden; Hauptaspekte sind Preis, Upscaling, Optimierung der Reaktion (lösungsmittelfrei) und Anpassung an spezifische standortabhängige Eigenschaften. Die Tests an der UHOH haben gezeigt, dass das Wasserhaltevermögen der entwickelten Hydrogele dem der auf dem Markt erhältlichen gleichwertig ist. Außerdem zeigten die Ergebnisse, dass

die getesteten Hydrogeltypen keine phytotoxische Wirkung auf die Keimung und das Wachstum von Kresse haben. Darüber hinaus scheint die Benetzung der Substrate mit verschiedenen Konzentrationen von OMWW, insbesondere mit solchen mit niedrigem Phenolgehalt, für die landwirtschaftliche Nutzung unbedenklich zu sein.

Es wurden Experimente durchgeführt, um zu ermitteln, ob die Anwendung von OMWW in einem Tropfbewässerungssystem eine Verstopfung der Bewässerungstropfer und/oder Filter zur Folge hat. Es wurde festgestellt, dass zwischen den OMWW-Konzentrationen von 30 % und 50 % keine signifikante Änderung der Durchflussrate (FR) beobachtet wurde. Bei allen Versuchsläufen wurden keine sichtbaren Verstopfungen an den Bewässerungstropfern beobachtet. Hinsichtlich des Versickern von Phenolen aus dem OMWW ergab die quantitative Analyse des Sickerwassers, dass die einmalige Verwendung von OMWW-Mengen bis zu 120 m³ ha⁻¹ auf leicht lehmigem Sand bei einem Grundwasserspiegel von weniger als 1 m kein kurzfristig eintretendes Risiko einer Grundwasserkontamination darstellt.

Über zwei Jahre hinweg wurden Feldversuche durchgeführt, um die Auswirkungen des Einsatzes von OMWW als Bodenadditiv bei Zwiebel- und Melonenkulturen zu untersuchen und die optimale Dosierung von OMWW zu ermitteln, um einen optimalen Ertrag in Bezug auf Quantität und Qualität zu erzielen. Die Gesamtfläche der Parzelle, die für diese Studie verwendet wurde, betrug 880 m² für beide Jahre. Die getesteten Dosierungen waren "T1: kein Zusatz von OMWW", "T2: OMWW-Dosis = 140 L = 25 m³/ha", "T3: OMWW-Dosis = 280 L = 50 m³/ha" und "T4: OMWW-Dosis = 420 L = 75 m³/ha". Daraus kann geschlossen werden, dass die Verwendung von OMWW die physiologischen Parameter im ersten Versuchsjahr beeinflusst hat, im Gegensatz zum Ertrag, bei dem keine Auswirkungen festgestellt wurden. Im zweiten Versuchsjahr hingegen wurden die physiologischen Parameter nicht beeinflusst. Allerdings stieg der Ertrag mit der Zugabe höherer Gaben von OMWW an. Dies kann jedoch erst nach einem dritten Jahr bestätigt werden, da die tatsächliche Auswirkung des OMWW auf die Bodeneigenschaften erst nach einer gewissen Zeit der Mineralisierung festgestellt werden kann.

Hydrogele wurden als Hilfsmittel zur Erhöhung der Wasserspeicherkapazität des Bodens in Feldversuchen bei der ENA in Meknès eingesetzt. Der Einsatz von Hydrogelen ohne Defizitbewässerung führte zu einer Ertragssteigerung von 27 % bei der Melonenkultur und 18 % bei der Zwiebelkultur, im Vergleich zur Kontrollbehandlung, die mit 100 % des Wasserbedarfs bewässert wurde. Darüber hinaus zeigten die Defizitbehandlungen mit 50 % ET_c in Kombination mit der Anwendung von Hydrogelen eine Ertragssteigerung von 13 % bei der Melonenkultur und 12 % bei der Zwiebelkultur, im Vergleich zur Defizitkontrollbehandlung mit 50 % ET_c und ohne Hydrogelanwendung. Dieses Ergebnis bestätigt, dass die Menge des zugefügten Hydrogels einen signifikanten Einfluss auf die Steigerung der Melonenproduktion selbst bei einem Wasserdefizit von 50 % im Vergleich zu den Kontrollbehandlungen hat. Mit Hydrogelen konnte Wasser eingespart werden, ohne den Ertrag zu beeinträchtigen. Zusätzliche Experimente mit

Hydrogelen wurden in einem Gewächshaus durchgeführt und bestätigten die Schlussfolgerung, dass ein Bewässerungsdefizit von 50 % durch die Anwendung von Hydrogelen ausgeglichen werden kann.

Für Technologien zur Ausbringung alternativer Substanzen und für vorbereitende Bodenwendungen, wie z.B. die Entfernung von Steinen oder die Zerstörung von Verhärtungen, sind Geräte verfügbar. Die Maschinen lassen sich zu multifunktionalen Anwendungen kombinieren und an die gewünschte Größe und Leistung anpassen. Für kleine Betriebe oder Landwirte ist es ratsam, sich in Genossenschaften, Dienstleistungsunternehmen zusammenzuschließen und Maschinen gemeinsam zu nutzen. In diesem Bericht findet sich ein Hinweis auf die Auswahl der geeigneten Ausbringungstechnik für die entwickelten Bodenhilfsstoffe.

Die Ergebnisse von I-WALAMAR zeigen ein großes Potenzial für die Wiederverwendung von Abfall- und Abwasserströmen sowie innovativen Bodenzusatzstoffen, wie Hydrogelen mit verbesserter biologischer Abbaubarkeit, zur Verbesserung der Wasser- und Ernährungssicherheit in der FMR. Das Projekt zeigt, wie diese Ströme behandelt und sicher in der Landwirtschaft eingesetzt werden können, um die Widerstandsfähigkeit der Bevölkerung gegenüber dem Klimawandel zu verbessern. Durch den Einsatz geeigneter Technologien zur Bodenausbringung und zur Erzeugung von Biogas aus Abfallströmen kann ein Beitrag zur Verringerung von Treibhausgasemissionen geleistet werden.

1 Introduction

M. Krauss

Water and food security are becoming increasingly important issues in the Maghreb. The region is currently facing one of the worst seasonal droughts in decades, with wheat and barley yields in Morocco expected to be 17 % and 18 % below the 5-year average, respectively. Between February and May 2023, rainfall in the Fès-Meknès region was 70-80 % below the long-term average (Manfron et al. 2023). In 2022, 247,000 jobs got lost in the agricultural sector in Morocco (Haut-Commissariat au Plan, Royaume du Maroc 2023). This can be attributed to the severe drought conditions.

Besides water scarcity the proportion of land that is degraded increased from 3.3 % in 2015 to 5.0 % in 2019 (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs 2023). This adds to the food security challenges. While the proportion of the population suffering from hunger was reduced from 6.3 % in 2001 to 3.8 % in 2018, it will increase to 5.6 % in 2020 (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs 2023). The agricultural sector is an important part of Morocco's economy attributing around 10 to 14 % of total GDP (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs 2023) and 19 % of the exports in 2022 (Kasraoui 2023).

Agriculture is currently experiencing intensification and commercialization in order to maintain or increase access to international sales markets, especially to the European market for its agricultural products. In addition to social and economic effects, this also has significant negative effects on soil resources, groundwater and surface water in the cultivation areas. Furthermore, climate change causes externally induced stresses on local water and land resources. The agricultural sector and settlements are not only water users and waste generators. Wastewater and waste streams, if treated and properly used, can be valuable resources that can be used in agriculture and for energy production.

Against the backdrop of growing water scarcity and the importance of the agricultural sector, the aim of the Moroccan-German research project I-WALAMAR is to identify and test ways of using resources more efficiently and at the same time increasing water and food security. Research area is the Fès and Meknès Region (FMR), where around 30 percent of olive cultivation is located (Fellah trade 2022) (Figure 1).

In the FMR, water resources are being depleted and land degradation is increasing. We successfully developed measures to improve sustainable land management in the region by treating waste and wastewater streams from settlements and olive mills, testing their applicability in agriculture, e.g. as irrigation water or fertiliser, developing innovative soil additives such as hydrogels, and developing planning tools for water and land management. The I-WALAMAR project is a Moroccan-German research project which incorporates research institutions, companies, administrations and other stakeholders.

In the following chapters pathways to an improved land management in the FMR by innovative sustainable land management practices are described. The I-WALAMAR project is funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research of Germany (BMBF) under the „CLIENT-II - International Partnerships for Sustainable Innovations" funding initiative, with co-funding by the Moroccan research partners.

Figure 1: Map of Morocco Fès as capital of the Fès-Meknès Region (FMR) chosen as the main I-WALAMAR project area (Asskali 2013)

2 Project Aims

M. Krauss, W. Kirchhof, N. Ittobane

The objective of the I-WALAMAR collaborative project is to develop innovative land and water management techniques to contribute to the implementation of integrated resource management and optimized farm management, while preserving ecosystem services, restoring severely degraded soils, and optimizing cultivation methods through innovative research approaches.

The project aims to implement exemplary elements of circular resource management and develop contributions to the integrated management of agricultural enterprises, such as farms and plantations. The results will strengthen practices in the Fès-Meknès region and bilateral research cooperation between the two countries.

Focusing on water and land resources (A) that are polluted, dumped, wasted or not properly used, the I-WALAMAR project's research is on innovations in the management of these resources combining new technologies in the fields of water and land management.

New soil-improving substrates (B) that increase the organic and/or fertilizer content of soils, functional (water-absorbing) hydrogels, humus-containing substrates (treated municipal sludge), will be generated. Local minerals (D), such as clays, bentonites, will be tested by applying new filtration and adsorption techniques. New materials can be generated that will help improve the quality of the new soil-improving substrates, which will be adapted to the local conditions. Through innovations in tillage (C), irrigation of the fields and new applications for regional climate monitoring (agricultural climate stations), reduced water consumption and higher resource-saving effects are targeted. Technological innovations in olive oil processing and waste management (E) aim at technical water and energy savings and a better use of resources. Novel high-sensitivity analytical methods (HPLC) and satellite imagery evaluations are introduced to monitor the quality and acceptance of new products (F).

The I-WALAMAR project addresses the following key research questions:

- What is the initial situation of water use, land use, environmental impact and socio-economic relevance especially of the olive oil production and municipal wastewater treatment plants in the Fès-Meknès Region? (Chapters 3.1 - 3.4)
- Where is the greatest potential for new resource recycling in the area of efficient use of water resources and reuse of liquid and solid waste from olive oil production and municipal wastewater treatment plants? (Chapters 4.1 - 4.3)
- What analytical and monitoring technologies are appropriate to support decision-making about the quality and safety of water resources and new alternative resources? (Chapters 5.1, 5.2, 5.5)

- Which technical processes are suitable to safely utilize the liquid and solid residues from olive oil production and municipal wastewater treatment plants in the Fès-Meknès region in the context of recycling? (Chapter 5.3, 5.4, 5.6)
- How can the processed and safe substances be used to increase soil fertility and support water needs (irrigation) in the Fès-Meknès region? (Chapters 5.7 - 5.9)
- How can the rural population in the Fès-Meknès region in particular benefit from the circular economy in this context? (Chapters 3.5, 3.6, 6.1)
- Which research results are particularly suitable for large-scale implementation in the Fès-Meknès region and beyond, and what are the implications for future water and landmanagement? (Chapters 5.10, 6.2)

Structure of the project

In the I-WALAMAR partner consortium four research institutions (Forschungsinstitut für Wasserwirtschaft und Klimazukunft an der RWTH Aachen e.V. (FiW), Institut für angewandte Polymerchemie (IAP) at Fachhochschule Aachen (FHAC), Universität Hohenheim (UHOH), Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (BICC)) and two commercial companies (SEBA Hydrometrie GmbH & Co.KG (SEBA), Inno Agri GmbH (INNOAGRI)) from Germany cooperate with three research institutions (Université Moulay Ismail (UMI), Institut Agronomique et Vétérinaire HASSAN II (IAV), École nationale d'agriculture de Meknès (ENA), one commercial company (OLEAFOOD) and partners from the water industry (Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sebou (ABHS), Régie Autonome De Distribution Eau Et Electricité Meknès (RADEM)) from Morocco under the coordination of FiW and UMI. The German-Moroccan Competence Network (DMK) supports the organisation of events and the dissemination of results.

Project study area

The administrative region of Fès-Meknès (FMR) is the study area of the project. Depending on the requirements of the research work of the different I-WALAMAR subprojects, smaller pilot areas are defined on a larger or smaller scale, such as the "Saïss" plain (white rectangle, Figure 2), the Sebou river basin or the experimental fields at ENA.

Figure 2: Fès-Meknès Region (FMR), I-WALAMAR project region

Methods

The research activities of the I-WALAMAR project are divided into six work packages (WP) (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Basic IWALAMAR Project Structure

Based on an inventory of the technical and socio-economic factors (WP 1), a comprehensive strategy for sustainable land and water management with special consideration of the material flows of alternative resources and a concept for an integrated water resources management were elaborated.

The demonstration projects are divided into three water technology / management work packages (WP 2) and four agricultural work packages (WP 3).

The water demonstration projects include:

- Monitoring and analysis programs with new sensor systems on two municipal wastewater treatment plants in the FMR (Ain Taoujadate),
- A comparative study with German wastewater treatment plants, to optimize the sewage sludge processing,
- An evaluation of alternative substrates that can be used as fertilizers or soil amendments,
- Study of material flows and resource use in a large-scale olive oil processing plant (OLEAFOOD, near Mèknès) in order to obtain an updated overview of the annual quantities of alternative resources that can be recycled, Separation trials with two-phase decanter to optimize the material flow of olive oil waste treatment by separating polyphenols from olive oil sludge (pulp),
- Application of HPLC analytical technologies (including preparatory analysis) for the analysis of phenolic compounds in various streams (such as wash water, first flush, second flush, olive slurry (margin, pulp) of the whole olive oil process and evaluation of the results to optimize the mass flow (better utilization of residues).

The agricultural demonstration projects concern:

- Study of the energetic utilization of municipal sewage sludge and sludge from the olive industry in a technical biogas plant.
- Trials on the growth of watercress roots using water feed with different concentrations of olive waste
- The production of site-adapted soil improvement substrates made from alternative raw materials and synthetic hydrogels to improve the ability of soils to hold water and fertilizer.
- The application of alternative fertilizers in comparative plant irrigation trials by using different crops.
- The improvement of degraded soils through the adaptation of alternative soil improving substrates such as liquid margine and/or olive oil pulp.

The following synthesis of the research results (WP 4) includes an analysis of the innovation potentials, the development of an application concept and the assessment of the acceptance by local users and the transferability. Based on the results of the I-WALAMAR research works, the team provides technical recommendations for technologies that have been proven to have a high potential for an implementation in the context of land, water and resource management.

The I-WALAMAR project is guided in the WP 5 (consolidation of the results) and coordinated in the WP 6.

3 Inventory Analysis in the Féz-Meknés Region

3.1 Inventory Analysis in the Olive Production and Olive Oil Processing in FMR

3.1.1 General Introduction

W. Kirchhof, S. Hruschka, N. Tijani

The **Fès-Meknès Region (FMR)** is one of the most important regions in Morocco for the production of olives and olive oil. Production volumes have increased over the past few years increased in recent years, while at the same time the effects of climate change on the region have become more apparent. Groundwater levels are dropping and the quality of the soil has also decreased in recent years. For some years now, the serious environmental impact of the discharge of untreated wastewater from urban water management and the olive processing industry has also been in focus. The technologies introduced, such as the evaporation and thermal recycling of solid olive residues, focus on avoiding the introduction of pollutants into the environment.

The FMR, created in 2015, consists of Meknès, Taouante, Taza, Moulay Yaacoub, Fès, El Hajeb, Sefrou, Ifrane and Boulemane. The region comprises of 194 municipalities, of which 33 are classified as urban (Royaume du Maroc, Ministère de l'Intérieur, Direction Générale des Collectivités Locales 2015). The region is strategically located at the crossroads of the important North-South and East-West Axis in the region, which has a positive impact on the development of the region. The two ancient royal cities of Meknès and Fès, which are also the center of industrial development, are at the heart of the region.

The Moroccan Green Plan (Maroc Plan Vert, GMP) is the main driving force behind the development of Moroccan agriculture, in particular the expansion of the Moroccan olive oil sector and its competitiveness with neighboring European countries such as Spain, Italy and Greece. The Moroccan agriculture is in transformation and is experiencing intensification and commercialization, which, in addition to social and economic impacts, has significant impacts on soil and water resources in key growing areas such as the Fès-Meknès Region (FMR). Climate change is triggering additional stress on water and land resources.

3.1.2 Olive tree plantations

W. Kirchhof, S. Hruschka, N. Tijani

In 1986, the King of Morocco encouraged the cultivation of olive trees by distributing seeds free of charge. This led to a great expansion. In 2010, a national plan was announced to plant a total of one million hectares of olive trees. The olive tree plantation in Morocco was subsequently intensified. The specific space requirements have been minimized by changing the distance between the planted olive trees from 5-6 meters to 1,5 to 2-3 meters (Figure 4)

Old-style olive tree plantation spacing 5-6m

Recent olive tree plantation spacing 1,5-3m

Figure 4: Old and new spacing type of olive tree plantation (Gardener's Path 2020; Tijani 2017b)

The size of the plantations is increasing, in the Saïss plain (part of FMR) the super-intensified type of olive plantations dominates over intensified and traditional plantations.

The annual cycle of olive production according to (Rehm 1989) is characterized by typical plant growth requirements and plantage maintenance works. In March, branches are cut (trimming) and the material could be used as a resource for alternative organic fertilizer materials. In May/June the application of nitrogen fertilizer is necessary to produce large fruits. In August and September, sufficient water must be provided for irrigation. During the harvest period, from November to February, leaves are cut from the harvested material, which is collected and transported to the olive mills.

During the harvesting period, there is a constant production of wastewater from the olive oil production. In technical mills, the wastewater is treated and stored in evaporation ponds. Some of the wastewater is discharged into open rivers. This opens up new opportunities as an alternative source of irrigation water or as a resource for the extraction of valuable substrates such as polyphenols.

3.1.3 Olive oil production

W. Kirchhof, S. Hruschka, N. Tijani

In Morocco, olive oil is produced using traditional small olive mills using a rotating grindstone, and by high-technical more-stage processes using crushers, malaxers, horizontal decanters, and vertical separators. An overview of traditional (Maâsras) and modern mills by region is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Moroccan olive mills and its capacity (Nabloussi et al. 2017)

Years	Daily olive oil capacity per mill	Number of mills	Main location (region)
Traditional (Maâsras)	< 10 t/day	16,000	Fès-Taounate: 18 % Taza: 11 % Marrakech: 11 % Chefchaoun: 9 % Agadir: 8 %
Modern mills	>10 t/day	300	Fès-Taounate: 42 % Marrakech: 23 % Meknès: 16 %.

Figure 5: Traditional olive press with a rotating grindstone (L'Observateur 2016)

In general, traditionally cold pressed olive oil is dark, opaque and contains more original substances. The grignons are piled up in open temporary storages near the press and mainly distributed as animal feed. During the storage period from November to February, leakage from the piles is softened and flushed into the groundwater or nearby open natural drains.

Figure 6: Schematic of a typical industrial olive oil processing applying a 2-phase-decanter (GEA Westfalia Separator Group GmbH (2013))

Industrial production is a large-scale process with much higher oil production and oil purification rate. The by-products and residues of the oil processing vary according to the selected process and type of processing units. The residues contain olive mush, crushed kernels, low saline wash water (electrical conductivity (EC) around 1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) and high

saline process wastewater (EC > 5000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). All residues contain small amounts of residual oils. The caloric value is high, the concentration of organic compounds is quite high. The olive oil factory OLEAFOOD uses the caloric value of the solid waste and presses the crushed kernels to small pellets, which are partly used for internal purposes or sold to the local market as fuel.

3.1.4 Quantities and qualities of olive oil production in Morocco

W. Kirchhof, S. Hruschka, N. Tijani

Table 2 shows the average annual production of olives from 2004 to 2020. The production has increased significantly in the last years due to national support under the Green Morocco Plan (GMP). The production of margine, including phenolic compounds, are closely correlated with olive production. The composition of organic matter of margines are listed in Table 3.

There are over 4,000 different phenolic compounds found in plants. In the olive oil sector, the term “polyphenols” is used by convention because not all of them are polyhydroxy derivatives. There are at least ten polyphenols that are reported to be common in olive oil. Margine, a by-product of the oil processing, has physical parameters shown in Table 4, is moderately soluble in water and can cause skin burn, eye damage, and irritations on contact.

Moroccan margines contains various phenolic compounds (Tijani 2017b), such as

- Simple phenolic compounds
- Phenolic acids
- Naphtoquinones
- Stilbenoides
- Flavonoides, and
- Complex polyphenolic aggregates

Table 2: Annual production of olives and margine in Morocco (Tijani 2017b)

Years	Total production of olives [t]	Trituration rate	Quantity of margine [t]	Quantity of Phenolic compounds [t]
2004-2008	782,000	75 %	320,000	16,000
2009-2013	1,344,540		685,000	34,250
In 2020 (strategic aim (GMP))	2,500,000			

Table 3: Composition of organic matter of margine in Morocco (Tijani 2017b)

Substance	Percentage in organic matter [%]
Phenolic compounds	2 - 6
Poly saccharides	13 - 53
Organic acids	3 - 10
Polyalcohols	3 - 10
Proteins	8 - 16
Lipids	1 - 14

Table 4: Physical parameters of margine in Morocco (Tijani 2017b)

Parameter	Value
Melting point (T.F).	41 °C
Boiling pint (T.E)	181 °C
Solubility in water S/H ₂ O	Moderate, 84 - 93 g/L bei 20 °C
Dipolar moment	1.69
pK _s value (pKa)	9.95
Risk category	H341 suspected of causing genetic defects H331 toxic by inhalation H311 toxic in contact with skin H314 causes severe skin burns and eye damage H301, H373, H411

3.1.5 Olive oil process wastewater characteristics

W. Kirchof, S. Hruschka, N. Tijani

The characteristics of olive margine depend on the production system (modern or traditional type), the process of separation (centrifugation or pressing), and the production type (rainfed or irrigated). The amount of additional water used to support the production and separation processes is a decisive factor affecting the salinity of the produced wastewater. Salinity can exceed normal limits by a factor of 100.

Olive margines are composed of 40 to 50 % of natural water from the olive fruit, 6 to 10 % of water in fruit by-products, traces of olive oil (about 0.7 %), and 50 to 40 % of additional water added for oil extraction (Table 5).

Table 5: Typical characteristics of olive margine (Nabloussi et al. 2017)

Parameter	After separation by decanters	After traditional cold pressing
Humidity (%)	93.4	90.20
Dry matter (%)	6.57	9.80
Organic matter (%)	5.41	8.13
N total (%)	0.08	0.68
P ₂ O ₅ (%)	0.03	0.11
K ₂ O (%)	0.35	0.66
Other minerals (Ca, Mg, Fe, Na, Zn, Mn) (%)	0.40	1.64
Nickel, Cobalt, lead	Traces (1.66 mg/L)	Traces (2.71 mg/L)
Polyphenols (%)	0.37	1.23
Electrical conductivity EC (mS/cm)	6.30	12.74
pH	4.78	5.14
COD (g/L)	73.70	170.80
BOD ₅ (g/L)	33	72

Beside antioxidant and skin irritating substances margines are rich in fertilizing materials and essential minerals (Table 6).

Table 6: Fertilizing materials and minerals of olive margine (Nabloussi et al. 2017)

Parameter	Amount per kg/ha, if an input rate of 50 m ³ /ha is applied	Concentration per unit (kg or m ³) Margine
Organic material	250	5 - 10 kg of Margine
N	25	g/m ³
P ₂ O ₅	32	g/m ³
K ₂ O	180	
CaO	7	g/m ³
MgO	7	g/m ³
Fe	14 – 103	g/m ³
Cl	270 – 600	g/m ³
Zn	3 – 10	g/m ³
Ni	3.4	g/m ³
Mn	1.6	g/m ³

3.1.6 Technologies to reduce Phenolic compounds or heavy metals from sewage and margine

In Morocco, clay mineral deposits such as Ghassoul are explored and partly tested whether the minerals can be used as adsorption or filtration media to reduce harmful compounds from wastewater of various municipal or industrial sources. It is intended that by adsorption polyphenols are extracted from highly polluted wastewaters of olive mills and in a subsequent separation process the extracted polyphenols are regained as valuable antioxidants.

Figure 7: Adsorption rate of Phenol and Chromium on bentonite (Tijani 2017a)

Adsorption tests reported by Tijani (2017a) showed high adsorption rates for phenol at Bentonite (Figure 7). Within this project, adsorption technologies have been further investigated.

3.1.7 Olive oil treatment technologies

W. Kirchof, S. Hruschka, N. Tijani

In the earliest production methods, the olives are crushed in mills (Figure 8) and put in bags (2) or frames (3) with the kernels. Lever presses (4) are used to extract the must. The must contains the olive oil and low-grade ingredients such as fruit water, flesh fibres, fruit skin particles and fine dirt. After a time-consuming sedimentation process, the oil was skimmed off (6) and poured into jugs (7) or tanks (8), where a further sedimentation process allowed the remaining undissolved components to settle (10).

Figure 8: Schematic of an olive oil production using a combination of mill crushers, lever presses, sedimentation basins and settlers (Westfalia Separator AG 1999)

In an improved process (Figure 9), hydraulic presses (5) are used for the pressing process. The settling process is carried out automatically in overflow containers (9) and is time consuming. The disadvantages are low output, large space requirements and poor oil quality due to the continuous influence of fruit water.

Figure 9: Schematic of an olive oil production using a combination of hydraulic presses, overflow sedimentation basins and settlers (Westfalia Separator AG 1999)

After washing (11), crushing in mills (1) and pressing in hydraulic presses (5), the subsequent step towards economical olive oil production is the separation of the valuable olive oil from the unwanted components using centrifugal separators (12) (Figure 10). Due to centrifugal force, the settling process takes place automatically, regardless of the quantity to be processed. The settling time becomes considerably shorter. The rapid separation of oil and fruit water results in higher yields and improved aroma and nutritional values.

Figure 10: Schematic of an olive oil production using a combination of washing, crushing in mills, hydraulic presses and centrifugal separators (Westfalia Separator AG 1999)

Centrifuges have a significant influence on economical process technology and a high-quality product. Today's modern process technology works with decanters and separators (Figure 11). The fruit pulp is broken down in a temperature-controlled mixer (13). Three-phase decanters (14) separate the fruit pulp diluted with water into valuable oil, fruit water and solids. The fruit water draining off the decanter, is de-oiled a second time in a separator (16). The downstream second separator (16) performs polishing functions. This process operates continuously with optimum yield, quality and high efficiency.

Figure 11: Schematic of an olive oil production using a combination of washing, temperature-controlled mixer, three-phase decanters and separation units (Westfalia Separator AG 1999)

The olive oil separation process in Morocco's most advanced olive oil plant, operated by OLEAFOOD, is based on four modular technological steps (Figure 12).

In the de-leafing and washing stage, the olives delivered from the plantations are washed, the leaves, branches, stones and soil are separated, and contaminated washing water is produced. At the crushing and malaxing stage, the kernels of the washed olives are crushed, a homogeneous olive paste is produced in the malaxers, which is cooled to 25 or 35 °C and stored. Some water is added. The paste is extracted by means of two-phase decanters to separate it into an oily fraction (extraction 1) and a sticky solid fraction which still contains some oil and is therefore separated again in a subsequent second separation stage by another set of two-phase decanters (extraction 2). Process water is added. The solid waste sludge is removed by screw pumps and stored in evaporation ponds. During separation, the oily fractions are secondly separated by plate decanters, which clean the oil and reduce the water content. In Morocco, the liquid residues from the washing and oil purification processes are collected in a large basins where the liquid is stored and thickened by evaporation during the non-harvest period.

Figure 12: Schematic olive oil production using modern system

Figure 13: Basin for OMWW evaporation

3.1.8 Overview of the treatment methods for residual materials

W. Kirchhof, S. Hruschka, N. Tijani

There are various treatment methods for processing residual material streams. Thermal processes, such as natural evaporation in basins, are frequently used. In central plants, biological treatment methods, like municipal biological wastewater treatment are also used. (El Bouazzaoui 2019; Koppen 1997; Giner Santonja et al. 2019)

Applying this biological treatment requires a minimum volume of wastewater and a continuous annual flow. Otherwise, logistical efforts for the collection, transportation and storage will be high. Often, the near-natural treatment is done in constructed wetlands or evaporation basins (Tekerekopoulou et al. 2017). Table 7 provides an overview of the treatment options for the different material streams and respective advantages and disadvantages.

Table 7: Advantages, disadvantages of treatment methods for residuals derived from olive oil processing (adapted after Doula et al. 2017)

Methods	Remarks	Advantages	Disadvantages
Margine			
Biological treatment	Enables the degradation of organic and inorganic suspended material. BOD and COD are reduced - Anaerobic: From highly concentrated streams of organic material into biogas - Aerobic: Is produced from less concentrated material flows applied. For further reduction of nutrients and organic material.	Anaerobic treatment has advantages over aerobic treatment. E.g., a higher removal rate, less space consumption and a lower sludge production.	A preceding treatment (e.g., sedimentation, filtration) is necessary, since oil- and phenol-containing substances can disturb the biology. Due to high investment chains rather for large farms or in central treatment plants.
Composting	One of the main recycling methods for processing of wastewater into a fertiliser. The margine is gradually added to the process.	Value creation, recycling through nutrient recycling.	The wastewater must be removed before treatment
Membrane filtration	Application possible. The resulting concentrate can be either incinerated or landfilled.	High efficiency in the reduction of COD. If necessary, complementary to conventional biological treatment.	Not suitable for use in small oil mills because of high investment and operating costs, high energy and monitoring requirements.
Chemical-physical treatment	Removal of dissolved organic - non-biodegradable - substances by means of adsorption, precipitation or flocculation. Characterized by using specific substances such as activated carbon or precipitants .	Low investment and operating costs. Better suited for small oil mills.	Large quantities of sludge and corresponding disposal problems.

Natural evaporation in evaporation ponds	The most common treatment method.	Low investment and operation costs. Due to the climate in the Mediterranean region favoured.	Large area required. Further problems such as odour formation, seepage and attraction of insects. In addition, sludge is produced, which in turn also has to be disposed. It is often composted when it is treated.
Forced evaporation	Multi-stage evaporation, whereby heat can be recycled. Pre-purification, e.g., by biological treatment necessary.	Heat recovery possible.	High energy demand. Complex process that requires appropriately trained personnel. High operating costs and emissions. Only suitable for large plants.
Pomace (Grignon humid and grignon sec)			
Drying	Heat from the process is used for drying.	The dried pomace can be used to generate energy burned, used in agriculture or landfilled. Air emissions must be treated accordingly.	High energy and personnel costs. The use of the wetter 2-phase-trester (Grignon Humid) poses a challenge to the existing plants.
Thermal treatment	Thermal drying with subsequent incineration.	Energy recovery possible.	Very expensive technology, especially with exhaust gas treatment. Most of the energy obtained is consumed in the process.
Biological treatment	Both anaerobic (fermentation) and aerobic (composting) treatment is necessary. If composting, to reduce the water content and to establish an aeration, it is necessary to add structural material.	Comparatively low emissions, space and energy requirements. Possibility of energy generation through biogas or reuse of the nutrients in agriculture.	Biogas is more expensive than composting and the investment costs are higher. In addition, the phenols limit the effectiveness of biogas production.

3.1.9 Socio-economic actors in the olive oil industry

B. Kemmerling, R. Navarro, L. Wirkus

There are different actors in the olive sector, with distinct financial capacities and motivations for investment and thus adoption of modern technologies. Field research and interviews conducted by BICC found there are three types of olive oil mills: small mills (*petites huileries*) run by (often farming) families, medium-sized mills established by investors, and large industrial mills affiliated to agribusinesses. These types are neither fixed nor mutually exclusive; there are cases where the lines between them are blurred, e.g., if a family enterprise invests in the development of its oil mill, or if an investor consists of several family members. However, creating typologies is useful not only to describe and better understand the current situation of the olive oil industry in the region, but also to use them as a basis for analysing the different potentials for innovation and conflict within or between these different groups.

Small mills or “*petites huileries*” are usually run by families who are bound to their land, having built up their mills several decades ago and inherited them from their fathers and/or are planning to inherit them to their children. The small mills we have included in our research have a trituration capacity between 8 and 14 tonnes per day, which is only reached during the peak of the season in November and December. Their main objective is to process their own olives and those of the farmers and individuals in the region during the harvest season. Some of them also sell olive oil to other clients from Morocco or even Europe, which are usually personal contacts. Selling oil to travellers passing by the olive mill is hardly possible for those mills in the villages, but an option for those situated along the road between Fès and Meknès. For these family enterprises, olive oil of good quality means oil produced from local olive varieties and in olive presses (discontinuous procedure). While they have invested in technologies and grown over the past decades, most of them are not planning to invest into a continuous system (three or two-phase decanter) or to enter new markets, either because the costs are too high given the current state of their business and size of oil mill, or because of their own and their clients’ olive oil preferences. Some of them complained that the profits of the oil mill are low or have decreased over the past years, also because of an increasing competition from bigger oil mills that emerged over the past decade.

Like the small family-run oil mills, most of the medium-sized mills are run by investors, who have close family bonds in the olive sector. They use the oil mill as part of their business portfolio alongside other economic activities; and they focus on buying olives and selling olive oil to businessmen and companies, even though most of them also work on their own and on clients’ olive during the harvest season. The biggest difference between the diverse investors interviewed is their choice of technologies, either the electrical press or the decanter. The major reason for investing in an electrical press is the demand for its oil. Some of the investors also believe that the oil from the electrical press is better than that from the decanter. Some oil mills

choose the middle way: We found oil mills that use both, the electrical press and the decanter, so that the client can choose, or they use both technologies in one. In turn, others who have invested into the 3- or mostly 2-phase decanter clearly see the future of olive oil production in these new technologies to keep pace with the world market.

The medium-sized mills have a higher trituration capacity than the small mills, although the mills that use the continuous system (the decanter) process more tonnes of olives per day (between 20 and 60 tonnes of olives per day) than the mills using electrical presses (10-15 tonnes per day for the medium-sized oil mills included in our research). These medium-sized mills sell their oil on local and national markets also beyond the harvest season. Some of the investors have links to businessmen in France or Spain to whom they sell small quantities of olive oil, too. Apart from this, none of the medium-sized investors, that we have interviewed, export olive oil. Several research participants stated that they are planning or would like to enlarge this business, although they mentioned the challenge to balance high investments with seasonal variations in yields and a fluid network of olive farmers, distributors, competing oil mill operators and clients who range from private individual persons or businessmen and companies.

Some big oil mills have emerged in the region over the past decade, which are sometimes referred to as industrial oil mills. They are usually part of bigger agribusinesses and combine the entire production cycle, from olive cultivation via the processing into oil to the bottling and marketing of the olive oil. As such, they have access to capital and loans and can invest in modern technologies. They run multiple production lines with the two-phase decanter, thus having a high processing capacity per day, which can reach several hundreds of tonnes of olives processed per day. This way they can process the olives from their own large plantations, on which they grow high-yield and irrigated olives on several hundreds of hectares. They have several permanent employees and need several dozens of additional staff during the harvest season. Industrial olive oil mills do not only process the olives from their own plantations, but also olives from surrounding larger farms or intermediaries who have bought olives from the various farms in the region and resell them. In addition, these industrial mills also buy olive pomace from the oil mills in the region that are used for the production of olive pomace oil. The processed olive oil is sold on national and international markets.

They are not a direct competition for the small and medium-size oil mills: First, they do not work with clients who want to process their olives for their own domestic use or small businesses; second, most Moroccan clients prefer the oil from the oil press of the “petites huileries” and medium-sized mills; and third, they do not sell their oil on local or regional markets but access national and international markets.

3.2 Inventory Analysis of the Water Resources and Analysis of the land use pattern, assisted by remote sensing in the FMR, Morocco

3.2.1 Water Resources in the Féz-Meknés Region

W. Kirchhof

All the major rivers in northern Morocco have their sources in the Middle Atlas. The two main catchment areas are the Sébou in the Saïss plain and the Moulouya in the Moulouya plateau.

The climate in the region is Mediterranean to continental and arid to semi-arid. Precipitation varies greatly between the different regions. For example, the Innaouen, Ouergha and Bab Louta river basins are affected by intermittent heavy flooding.

While the climate in the western part of the Saïss plain is Mediterranean with an average precipitation of 400-600 mm/a, the mountainous regions of the Middle Atlas and Rif are characterized by a wetter climate with more than 600 or more than 800 mm/a. The driest areas of the region are in the southeast with annual precipitation less than 300 mm (Royaume du Maroc, Ministère de l'Intérieur, Direction Générale des Collectivités Locales 2015). A challenge for Moroccan agriculture is the high variability of rainfall.

As Morocco, like its North African neighbors, is severely affected by climate change, the frequency and intensity of future droughts are expected to increase as temperatures rise and rainfall decreases (Schilling et al. 2012; El-Ashry et al. 2010).

Agriculture has the largest demand for water in the Greater North Africa region, accounting for 84 % of demand, ahead of municipal supply and industrial demand (Statista 2016).

Groundwater resources account for 20 % of the country's total hydraulic potential, with four billion usable cubic metres per year. The Sebou aquifer accounts for 1.3 billion. The depth of the aquifer varies from 200 m in the south to 1,700 m in the centre of the plateau. Groundwater is used to supply drinking water to the regional centres of Fès and Meknès, as well as for irrigation. Each year, 0.7 billion m³ is abstracted for industrial and municipal use and 2.0 billion m³ for rural irrigation. In the last 20 years, the groundwater level has fallen by 60 m. For artesian aquifers, this corresponds to a pressure drop of 2.8 m per year (Royaume du Maroc, Ministère de l'Intérieur, Direction Générale des Collectivités Locales 2015; Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sebou 2020; BMWI 2017). In the area of the Rif Mountains, there are several local aquifers, separated from each other by impermeable rock layers, which are used for irrigation and other purposes. There is no information available on the quantities or possible changes in groundwater levels.

Since the 1980s, Morocco has been increasingly affected by droughts. Dams are an important means of compensating for the fluctuating amounts of rainfall. The four large dams in the region are mainly used for irrigation and drinking water supply; two of them additionally for

power generation (Table 8). Other smaller dams complement the system. Their main function, apart from water supply, is flood protection.

Table 8: Main Water Dams in the FMR (after Royaume du Maroc, Ministère de l'Intérieur, Direction Générale des Collectivités Locales 2015; Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sebou 2021)

Water Dam	Storage volume [mio. m ³]	Main purpose	Province
Driss ler	1,156.80	Energy Generation and Irrigation	Taounate
Sidi Chahed	170	Potable Water and Irrigation	Moulay Yaacoub
Allal-Al-Fassi	63.7	Potable Water, Energy Generation and Irrigation	Sefrou
Enijl	12	Potable Water and Irrigation	Boulemane

3.2.2 Environmental (Water, Climate) Monitoring Systems in the FMR, Morocco

W. Kirchhof

The catchment areas are organized in authorities. In Morocco, there are nine water boards, each named after the catchment area, and water commissions in the respective provinces. In the following, the data of the ABHS (Water Board Sébou, french: Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sébou) are used because it covers the main part of the study region. Groundwater management is also within the remit of Moroccan water boards (Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sebou 2014, 2020, 2021).

The ABHS maintains a cadastre for point source discharges by industry and municipalities. Diffuse discharges from agriculture, for example, are not recorded (Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sebou 2021). Nevertheless, it is known that the increasing use of fertilizers and pesticides negatively affects surface water quality. Also, industrial wastewater is often not treated sufficiently. One reason is poor regulation and monitoring. An example is the olive oil industry, which pollutes surface waters in the winter months by discharging highly polluted wastewater (BMW 2017).

3.2.3 Land Systems in the FMR

R. Navarro

Remote sensing-based analyses using 10-m resolution Sentinel-1 and -2 data from the European Space Agency (ESA) constellations allowed a thorough inventory analysis of the main land systems in the Saïss plain.

These analyses allowed detecting the following land use land cover (LULC) classes in the study area for the year 2020:

Table 9: Land use land cover classes and their extent in the study area

Land use class	Area (ha)
Olive orchards	54,167
Deciduous orchards	25,136
Greenhouses	3,936
Winter crops	27,350
Spring crops	69,767
Summer crops / double cropping	6,243
Shrubland	49,712
Other vegetation (riparian mainly)	2,482
Bare land	18,955
Surface water bodies	330
Impervious ground	12,623

The olive class could be further sub-categorized into traditional, intensive and super intensive plantations, based on the tree-to-tree distances as follows:

Table 10: Olive tree planting patterns and cultivation surface in the study area

Olive orchards (planting patterns)	Description	Area (ha)
Traditional	10 x 10 m distance between trees and rows	5,254
Super intensive / Super high density	3 - 6 m between trees, 6 m between rows	28,896
Super intensive / Super high density	1 - 2 m between trees, 4 between rows	20,017

The most represented crop type found in the study area are spring crops followed by winter crops, which based on crop statistics are expected to be mainly rainfed cereals (Conseil Régional Fès - Meknès 2020). Spring crops are distributed all over the study area, as well as winter crops, while the latter were stronger represented in the western part of the Saïss Plain. Summer crops and double cropping are less represented and mainly located in the central area, but also in the northeast where some cooperatives and fruit exporters are located (Cooperative Ghania, Cooperative Berta, Domaine Douiet, e.g.). There were no summer crops found in the western region (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Distribution of annual crops (2020), subcategorized into winter, spring and summer/double cropping, (Navarro (2021))

Orchards are evenly distributed across the whole study area. The northern mountain ranges are mainly covered by intensive and traditional evergreen orchards. Super intensive evergreen plantations extend from east to west through the whole study area, with clusters in the central part and in the western mountain ranges. The average area of the central plantations is around 400 ha for each plantation. The central part and especially the southwest present predominantly deciduous orchards. Some deciduous intensive plantations are also located nearby intensive/super intensive evergreen plantations in the centre of the plain, which due to relief properties might be a good location for mechanized harvesting on super intensive plantations. Greenhouses in Morocco can cover cash crops such as tomatoes, or deciduous perennial crops such as wine or *Rosaceae* like apple or almond trees. Most greenhouses are in the western half of the study area close to the city of Meknès, but also in the north-eastern area close to Fès where other irrigated summer crops are found (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Different orchard types under different management forms, (Navarro (2021))

Due to climatic conditions, irrigation is required for summer green agriculture, including summer crops and deciduous tree crops. While olive trees can also prosper in dry climates without irrigation during the dry season, super intensive olive farming systems are usually irrigated. Based on their phenological characteristics and climate data these land use classes are most probably irrigated in the Saïss plain, covering an area of approximately 55,000 ha.

Figure 16: Potentially irrigated agriculture and surface water bodies, source: Navarro (2021)

Summer and double cropping systems are especially present in areas with less intensive olive orchards (see section before, Figure 16). The main areas of irrigated annual crops are in the northeast close to Fès, where there is also an important cluster of deciduous orchards and greenhouses, and in the central plain, close to super intensive olive plantations. As illustrated

in the map (Figure 17), the main land use with irrigation water requirements is not olive, but rather a mix of intensive horticulture and deciduous orchards.

Surface water bodies are concentrated in the western part of the study area, often overlapping with intensive forms of agriculture, such as super intensive olive and deciduous tree plantations. The presence of irrigated annual crops (see section before) is also correlated to the presence of water bodies, but to a lower degree.

Figure 17: Surface water bodies (centroids) in the Saïss plain, source: Navarro (2021)

Note: Surface water bodies as centroids are detected by applying a threshold of 0.3 on McFeeters 1996, NDWI (based on McFeeters 2013). A 10-cluster k-Means clustering algorithm was applied on the centroids to generate a heatmap based on cluster size. Based on Copernicus Sentinel-2 data (2020) from January 2020, modified by applying the `qualityMosaic()` function in Google Earth Engine.

Natural vegetation in the Saïss plain comprised riparian vegetation, bare and shrubland areas (Figure 18). Bare land referred to all areas where almost no vegetation grows due to poor soils or bare rock, and was located mainly in the north-eastern borders of the study area, while some isolated spots were found in the central parts of the Saïss plain. The land use class shrubland characterized sparse endemic vegetation, including grasslands and perennial shrubs, and was found in areas of steep terrain in the central-eastern part of the plateau. Riparian vegetation, also named as “other vegetation”, was found nearby main rivers, in the northern part of both cities Fès and Meknès.

Figure 18: Natural vegetation (2020), including bare and shrubland and other vegetation, which is mainly riparian, source: Navarro (2021)

Areas with sharp delimitations in the plain area are classified as shrubland consisting of young, super intensive orchards with a low percentage of tree crown area. Thus, this land use class is probably overestimated. Correctly classified shrubland was found on hilly steep areas which would not allow any form of cultivation due to erosion risks.

3.2.4 Olive orchard intensification between 2010 and 2020

R. Navarro, L. Wirkus

Figure 19: Land use change of olive plantations of high tree density between 2010 and 2020 (Navarro et al. 2023).

Using PlanetScope and RapidEye high resolution satellite imagery for both years 2010 and 2020 allowed detecting main areas of super intensive and intensive olive plantations in each year (see Navarro et al. 2023). Comparing the results revealed that there is a trend towards spatial concentration and larger plot sizes (green colored plots), while some larger plantations have remained (yellow) and others have been given up and converted to other land uses (red) such as urbanization or annual crops (Table 11). Accuracy was assessed in different plot size ranges, revealing that there were higher commission errors for smaller plots. Thus, the higher number of smaller plots in 2010 is also associated to higher error rates, which needs to be considered when looking at the total areas calculated for each year and the estimated land use change.

Table 11: Olive tree planting patterns and cultivation surface in the study area

Type of plantation	Area (ha)
Super intensive plantations in 2010	6,267
Super intensive plantations in 2020	6,785
Area with no change	1,470
Area with new plantations	5,315
Converted areas to other land uses	4,797

3.3 Inventory Analysis in the Agricultural Sector in the FMR, Morocco

3.3.1 Population Structure and Agricultural Structures

According to figures from 2014, the total population in Morocco consists of 33.6 million people (Royaume du Maroc, Ministère de l'Intérieur, Direction Générale des Collectivités Locales 2015; Haut-Commissariat au Plan. Royaume du Maroc 2021). 60.4 % of the population live in urban areas. The population and the people living in urban areas have almost doubled since 1971. The FMR has a similar structure. Its population 2014 consisted of 4.2 million people, of which 60.5 % live in cities. In 2012, the region's population was 3.7 million. However, the population growth mainly occurs in the urban centers in Fès and Meknès. Population in Meknès grew by 1.5 % per annum, while rural population shrank by 0.5 %.

While the population density in the FMR is 105.7 inhabitants/km², the national average is only half as high. Regional structures within the region vary greatly: there are 30 municipalities with a population density of less than 30 inhabitants/km², while Fès has a density of 55,600 inhabitants/km². The region's two major culturally and industrially important cities are Fès, with around one million inhabitants, and Meknès, with around 600,000. In addition, there are three medium-sized cities, each with between 55,000 and 85,000 inhabitants, and ten small towns with less than 10,000 inhabitants. The rest of the region is rural. (Royaume du Maroc, Ministère de l'Intérieur, Direction Générale des Collectivités Locales 2015; Haut-Commissariat au Plan. Royaume du Maroc 2021)

The region is generally well developed due to its cities. There is an international airport - and other national airports. Several highways and railroads crisscross the region. The cities are also well served by electricity, water and sewerage. The main challenge is to provide services to the steadily growing informal periphery. In order to reduce the use of firewood for energy supply, especially in rural areas, solar power projects have been strongly promoted and expanded in recent years (Schilling et al. 2012; Haut-Commissariat au Plan. Royaume du Maroc

2021; Ministre de l'Agriculture du Maroc 2008). About half of the children who attend elementary school also attend secondary school. In both cases, just under half of the children are female. There are also various institutions of higher education in the region: four universities, as well as other educational institutions (Royaume du Maroc, Ministère de l'Intérieur, Direction Générale des Collectivités Locales 2015).

In addition to the industries of traditional crafts, energy supply, chemicals and pharmaceuticals, agriculture is the most important sector in the FMR. Along with the chemical and pharmaceutical industries, it is also the main employer (Haut-Commissariat au Plan. Royaume du Maroc 2021). Although conditions are good and production in some industries accounts for more than half of national output, the region's poverty rate is higher than average. This affects rural areas and the agribusiness sector in particular.

The FMR is one of the most important agricultural regions in Morocco, accounting for 1.4 million ha or 15 % of Morocco-wide arable land (Essahlaoui 2016). In the 2011/12 season, 21 % of national cereal yield was produced here. This is equivalent to over one million tons. The cultivation consists mostly of soft wheat (52 %), durum wheat (28 %) and barley (20 %). Corn is grown only to a small extent. In addition to cereals, oil crops such as sunflower, rapeseed and soybean are grown, as well as legumes and fruit trees. Of the fruit trees, olives and citrus are the most common. 9 % of the agricultural land in the FMR is irrigated (Royaume du Maroc, Ministère de l'Intérieur, Direction Générale des Collectivités Locales 2015; Haut-Commissariat au Plan. Royaume du Maroc 2021). Approximately 9.5 billion m³ of surface water and 2 billion m³ in the Sebou River basin are used for this purpose. About one third of the withdrawals are not authorized (BMW 2017).

In addition to the production of various crops, livestock farming has a long tradition and is diversified. Thus, all animal species that are bred in the Kingdom of Morocco are also kept in the region. In total, there are about four million livestock in the region. The vast majority of these (over 70 %) are goats. Cattle and sheep make up about ten percent each. Horses and camels are also kept (Royaume du Maroc, Ministère de l'Intérieur, Direction Générale des Collectivités Locales 2015; Haut-Commissariat au Plan. Royaume du Maroc 2021)).

3.3.2 Challenges and Changes in Agriculture

In recent years, the Moroccan government has launched various reforms to restructure the agricultural sector. The goal is to strengthen food security in Morocco. This is to be achieved, for example, by reducing the country's dependence on grain imports by producing a larger share of the required products locally (Sadik 2014).

One challenge in implementing these reforms is the highly fragmented ownership structure in Morocco. For example, there are many small plots of land owned by families, various traditional and new associations and collectives, as well as large farms. The actors with whom

negotiations must be conducted are correspondingly numerous, and measures such as compensation, reallocation or expropriation are correspondingly complicated (Schilling et al. 2012; Royaume du Maroc, Ministère de l'Intérieur, Direction Générale des Collectivités Locales 2015).

Nevertheless, agriculture in Morocco has changed in recent years. Irrigation has increased and the types of crops have changed. Traditionally, agriculture has been adapted to fluctuating rainfall. Cereals such as barley, which are less sensitive than wheat, were grown; livestock were grazed on otherwise inhospitable land; and fodder was stockpiled for worse years. Government promotion of fodder reserves, as well as regional cultivation of wheat, has in places dissolved these traditional systems, including mutual aid. On the other hand, alternative crops, such as olive trees and citrus fruits, are also promoted, as they can reduce soil erosion in combination with field crops (Schilling et al. 2012).

Morocco and the entire North African region are located in an area that is expected to face further stresses due to climate change. For example, temperatures are expected to increase by 2-3 °C and precipitation is expected to decrease. This is projected to decrease agricultural production by up to 40 % by 2080. Increased evaporation and, in some cases, incorrect forms of irrigation will also increase the risk of soil salinization. In some areas, up to 80 % of the soil is already affected.. From 2010 to 2030, a 50 % decline in agricultural productivity appears possible (Schilling et al. 2012).

Overall, yields increased from 1980 to 2010. However, in addition to maximum yields, the range of variation has also increased significantly. Larger farms and richer families are generally more resilient, as they can switch to alternatives such as buying fodder in drought years. In terms of other development goals, such as reducing social inequality, it is therefore recommended to promote the stability of agricultural production rather than maximizing yields (Schilling et al. 2012).

It can be stated that the increasing demand for water, the resulting decrease of available water resources and degraded agricultural land are main challenges for the region (Schilling et al. 2012; Royaume du Maroc, Ministère de l'Intérieur, Direction Générale des Collectivités Locales 2015).

3.4 Inventory Analysis of the Social and Economic Environment in the FMR

B. Kemmerling, R. Navarro, L. Wirkus

The Fès-Meknès Region (FMR) has an area of 40,075 km² and a population of 4.2 million inhabitants, representing around 10 % of Morocco's total population, with a demographic density (105 inh./km²) above the national average (47.6 inh./km²) (Conseil Régional Fès - Meknès 2020). For 2030, demographic projections estimate an increase to 4,640,286 inhabitants in the region (Conseil Régional Fès-Meknès).

As on a national level, also in the FMR around 40 % of the population lives in rural areas and the agricultural sector is an important contributor to the national GDP (15.2 %) (Conseil Régional Fès-Meknès), representing 19.9 % of the regional GDP (Conseil Régional Fès - Meknès 2020). The sector further accounts for 21 % of national cereal, 35 % of olive production. 32.7 % of the region's surface is used for agricultural purposes (Conseil Régional Fès - Meknès 2020), which is partly due to the high rainfall in the region and the presence of important groundwater resources. However, a growing water demand caused by demographic trends and shifts from rainfed to irrigated agriculture is currently threatening regional water resources. Additional pressure comes from increasing residues, which cause further harm to the environment (Conseil Régional Fès-Meknès).

The most populated prefectures in the FMR are those of Fès and Meknès, accounting for 47 % of its total inhabitants (Conseil Régional Fès-Meknès). The cities of Fès and Meknès are also geographical boundaries to the Saïss plain, one of the most fertile areas in the region (Dauteuil et al. 2016; Quarouch et al. 2014). At the same time, the Saïss area has lately been subject to several studies due to the increasing depletion of the underlying aquifers, threatening the livelihoods of an important share of the local population (Ameur et al. 2017; Molle et al. 2019).

There have been various national programmes trying to address social inequality and encouraging economic development in the agricultural sector in the last decades, which have shaped the social and economic environment in the FMR. This chapter identifies the main actors in the agricultural sector in the Saïss area, which are differently affected by socio-economic and environmental threats, but also have developed various forms of adaptation mechanisms.

3.4.1 Background

Agricultural intensification in the region has increased the pressure on natural resources, particularly on groundwater resources. Before the 1980s, the prevalent farming system in the Saïss Plain was rainfed agriculture, mostly of cereals and forage crops, and livestock production on extensive grazing areas. After a series of dry years in the 1980s, the Moroccan government relaxed access restrictions to groundwater, and farmers moved progressively to irrigation. Consequently, the number of wells and tube wells increased from 900 in the 1980s to more than 12,000 in 2012, accompanied by innovations in pumping technologies and drip irrigation systems (Quarouch et al. 2014). Irrigated land based on groundwater extraction increased to more than 45,000 ha, which is approximately 90 % of the total irrigated land in the Saïss Plain (Ameur et al. 2017) In addition, the use of fertilisers and pesticides, as well as increased residues from agriculture and food processing, contributes to the contamination of groundwater (Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sebou 2018). The impacts of global climate change are likely to put additional pressure on natural resources, particularly the decreasing annual precipitation regimes estimated in the course of the twenty-first century and a rising

average temperature by two or three degrees by 2050 (Schilling et al. 2012; Verner et al. 2018; Filahi et al. 2017). They increase the drought risk, water scarcity and deterioration of soils, and they are likely to reduce agricultural productivity in the region in the long run (Schilling et al. 2012).

Moreover, the privatisation of land has facilitated agricultural intensification in the Saïss Plain over the past three decades. In the 1970s, the Moroccan government established ninety-three agrarian cooperatives on state-owned land in the Saïss Plain, around 12 % of the number of cooperatives countrywide (Bossenbroek and Zwarteveen 2015). In 2006, the Moroccan government decided to privatise the land of the cooperatives as stipulated in the *melkisation* law (see section 3.6). Many farmers acquired a plot (usually between nine and 13 ha), but subsequently rented it to lessees or sold it to agricultural investors or real estate companies (Ameur et al. 2017; Bossenbroek and Zwarteveen 2015; Valette et al. 2013).

The Green Morocco Plan (*Plan Maroc Vert*), irrigation politics and recent land reforms, have transformed the agro-production system in Morocco and led to the emergence of new agricultural actors in different regions of the country.

3.4.2 Emergence of new actors

The emergence of new actors has changed the agro-production system in the region and resulted in a significant diversification in farming. Agriculture plays a different role in various types of farming, particularly in terms of livelihood security. Similarly, the various agricultural actors contribute differently to environmental challenges and are affected by the impacts of climate change in diverse ways, not least because their capacities to adapt vary. Several researchers have developed farm typologies in the Saïss Plain, based on qualitative or a combination of quantitative and qualitative data. Ameur et al. (2017) and Petit et al. (2018) identify four different agricultural actors in their study of two former cooperatives on public land in El Hajeb province, namely agribusinesses, medium-sized investors, lessees and family farms.

The first farm type Ameur et al. (2017) and Petit et al. (2018) have identified on public land in El Hajeb province consists of large agribusinesses, which have emerged on former state farms and evolved through public-private partnerships promoted by the GMP. They lease land from the state on a long-term basis and take over machinery and equipment from the state. They cultivate cash crops on several hundreds of hectares. These companies access groundwater through high-performance tube wells and are therefore able to secure their water needs even in dry years. They depend entirely on hired labour, permanent as well as temporary workers during the peak seasons. As many agribusinesses in Morocco (Sippel 2014), these companies process, pack and store their products on the farm and sell them on national and international markets (Ameur et al. 2017; Petit et al. 2018).

The second type of farmers are medium-sized investors who began to buy land from former members of cooperatives in the study area of El Hajeb in the late 2000s. Land size depends on the investments of each actor and can vary between a few and several dozens of hectares. They invest in irrigation infrastructure, particularly deep tube wells, to access the aquifer and to secure their water needs. On these irrigated lands, they cultivate cash crops such as fruit trees for national and international markets, but they can also diversify their cultivation with cereal production on rain-fed lands. Most investors are absent from the farm, live in urban centres and have transferred managing responsibilities to a farm manager who hires casual workers, particularly during the planting and harvest season. Farm income varies according to water resources and choice of crops. If a large part of the land is used for rain-fed agriculture, income depends on annual precipitation regimes. If a major part of the land is irrigated and cultivated with orchards, farms provide a lucrative source of income, but only after several years, after successful investments and once orchards are fully bearing fruit. For most investors, agriculture is only one source of income, since they are also involved in trade, industry, or public works. Agriculture, thus, is part of their diversification strategy (Ameur et al. 2017; Petit et al. 2018).

Another new actor on the land of former cooperatives in the study area of El Hajeb is the lessee. Like investors, lessees emerged in the late 2000s after the *melkisation* law (see section 3.6) that allowed individual ownership of cooperative land. In contrast to investors, lessees rent out land from former cooperative members on a short-term basis and invest less. They usually have a background in agriculture and work on the farm, but depend on additional labour, particularly during the planting and harvest season. They practice intensive horticulture, mostly onions and potatoes in the area of El Hajeb, to maximise their profits. Lessees often invest in deep tube wells to access groundwater. According to Petit et al. (2018), they are the largest water user per hectare in the region. Moreover, their input rates of fertiliser are high to increase agricultural yields, although this rapidly deteriorates the soil and pollutes water. After three to six years, when soil quality and/or water scarcity reduces agricultural productivity, they leave the land and move to other areas (Petit et al. 2018; Ameur et al. 2017). They deal with changing market prices by storing their products in cooler mountainous areas nearby and by selling their products themselves (Petit et al. 2018; Ameur et al. 2017). In this reverse-tenancy relation, investment capacities and high mobility makes lessees more powerful than the owners from which they lease the land (Petit et al. 2018).

The last type of farm Ameur et al. (2017) and Petit et al. (2018) have identified is the family farm. In their study region in El Hajeb, the family farms are members of former cooperatives that have bought their parcels after the *melkisation* law and continue to cultivate the land or parts of it with diverse crops, such as beans, onions, carrots and cereals. Usually, they combine the cultivation of crops with livestock, above all cattle. Some of these lands are irrigated with shallow wells, but most of the land is not, or not any longer and depends on

rainfall. Due to lesser capacities for investment and higher dependency on shallow groundwater or rainwater, these family farms are more exposed to volatile precipitation regimes and declining water tables. Family members do most of their farm work by themselves and only hire labour during planting and harvest, if necessary. They usually depend on intermediaries to market their products (Petit et al. 2018), which puts them in a vulnerable position, because intermediaries control selling prices (Baccar et al. 2018; Petit et al. 2018). Their income varies according to rainfall, prices for agricultural products and input costs, but is generally lower than the income of the other three types. It is therefore very common that family members look for additional sources of income, often working as wage labour on the fields of agribusinesses, investors, or lessees (Ameur et al. 2017; Petit et al. 2018).

This overview shows that agriculture plays a different social and economic role for these diverse agricultural actors, ranging from diversifying the investment portfolio, maximising the profit and increasing agricultural revenue, to making a living from agriculture, either entirely or partially. These actors also differ in their access to capital, land and water, as well as in their exposure to volatile precipitation regimes and declining groundwater levels. Whereas some actors can secure their water access due to infrastructural investments or high mobility, most family farms are dangerously exposed to decreasing water resources, especially in rainfed agriculture (Dugué et al. 2014). The following table (Table 12) provides an overview of the different characteristics of the actors identified in the Saïss plain.

Naturally, the farming types presented here neither represent the complexity of farming systems in the project region nor are these types fixed or mutually exclusive categories. Different organisational and monetary capacities, experiences with subsistence and entrepreneurial farming, access to land and water and cultural reasons lead to multiple, hybrid forms of farming and to a co-existence of diverse actors, present or absent, who are involved in farming in the Saïss Plain (Petit et al. 2018; Bouzidi et al. 2015).

Table 12: Schematic Overview of Farm Types on Public Land in the Saïss Plain

	Agribusinesses	Investors	Lessees	Family farms
Access to Water	Groundwater extraction from confined aquifer by high-performance tube wells.	Mostly groundwater; areas under rain-fed cultivation planned to be converted into irrigated areas.	Groundwater from confined aquifer and rain-fed agriculture.	Mostly rain-fed agriculture; groundwater extraction above all from shallow aquifer; often abandoning of shallow wells due to lack of water.
Agricultural Production	Fruit trees, wine, olives.	Fruit trees, cereals on rain-fed areas.	Intensive horticulture (e.g. onions and potatoes).	Ranging from diversified to specialised production, often a combination of irrigated and rain-fed agriculture with livestock production (<i>bour</i>).
Land Tenure	Long-term leasing from state in the form of public-private partnerships.	Bought land from other farmers, e.g., former cooperative members.	Short-term renting of land from family farmers.	Individual or collective land tenure.
Farm Management	Farm manager, hired labour.	Investors mostly absent, farm manager, hired labour.	Hired labour, particularly during peak seasons.	Family labour, some use hired labour during peak seasons (planting & harvesting).
Income Diversity	Diversification along the value chain: Agricultural products are processed, packed and stored on-farm and sold on national and international markets.	Economic diversification: Agriculture often only one source of income, others in trade, industry, public works.	Diversification in time and space: Agricultural production moved to other areas when productivity decreases.	Product diversification: agricultural products and livestock. Additionally, search for alternative income sources, often on farms of agribusinesses, investors and lessees.

3.4.3 Social Dynamics: The New Role of Youth in Agriculture

Since 2015, the role of rural youth in agricultural development has gained an interest in research. Research in Morocco demonstrates that rural young people have become drivers for agricultural change; they engage in small-scale agricultural enterprises fostering technical and institutional innovation and start agricultural projects seeking support from different development funds. Rural youth seek, above all, a ‘modern’ production based on irrigated agriculture and improved access to national and international markets for their products (often niche products such as plums or endive) to increase their revenues and live more comfortable lives than their parents (Amichi et al. 2015). This is particularly the case for young graduates that return to their villages and often do not identify themselves as farmers, since they were originally seeking a job and life outside of agriculture in the cities (Quarouch et al. 2015). Other

young people strongly identify as farmers but are constantly searching for new technical and managerial competences to expand their possibilities and perspectives in agriculture. Kadiri et al. (2015) examine how an increasing number of young, educated people seek leadership positions in rural communities that were previously reserved for village notables. They can mobilise financial resources, are active in different networks and coalitions, hold important institutional functions and travel within and beyond their communities. Their success, therefore, is less related to inheriting positions, but more to seizing opportunities. The authors conceptualise youth in line with Bourdieu as a social construction; youth is not an age category, but rather a social relation, cultural construction and associated as a time of passage from a situation of dependence on their parents towards being in charge by themselves (Amichi et al. 2015).

Young people often depend on the state to realise agricultural projects (Abdellaoui et al. 2015). For this reason, young people maintain different relationships with state institutions (Faysse et al. 2015). Especially those in leading positions are in regular contact with state institutions, for example, as members of the board of directors of cooperatives and associations (Faysse et al. 2015; Aroussi Bachiri et al. 2015). Another relation emerges from public funding possibilities: Over the past ten years, young people have been able to apply for agricultural projects mainly via the GMP, particularly pillar II (see chapter 3.5), and the National Initiative for Human Development (INDH). While the GMP does not put special emphasis on young people within its projects and usually relates funding to the access to land, the INDH considers young people (in the programme defined as people under 35 years old) in its project conceptualisation. In fact, project applications must indicate the proportion of women and young people participating in the project (Ftouhi et al. 2015). However, young people also have reported difficulties in accessing these funds due to limited information about funding options or lengthy administrative procedures (Ftouhi et al. 2015).

While still playing a marginal role in these processes, the Moroccan government has increasingly recognised the youth and their role as drivers of change in Moroccan agriculture. This becomes clear in the new agricultural strategy Generation Green, which explicitly identifies young people as one of the target groups for policy interventions over the next ten years.

3.5 Analysis of the Political Environment: Adaptation Strategies in Morocco

B. Kemmerling, R. Navarro, L. Wirkus

3.5.1 The GMP: Agriculture as a Driver for Development

The national agricultural strategy from 2008 to 2020, the Green Morocco Plan (GMP, Plan Maroc Vert), considered agriculture as the driving force for economic and social development

in the country and aimed to intensify agricultural production, enhance agricultural productivity, and increase agricultural exports. The GMP consisted of two pillars and several transversal actions in sectors, such as land and water. The first pillar focused on the development of the highly mechanised and export-oriented agriculture predominant on irrigated land and in favourable *bour* land (where a mix of agricultural production and grazing prevails) (Agence pour le Développement Agricole 2020). These projects promoted mainly the cultivation of high-yield cash crops for national and international markets, such as citrus fruits, olive trees, horticulture, sugar, dairy products, meat and seeds (Akesbi 2011, 2012). The second pillar focused on poverty reduction and income generation for small and medium-sized agricultural holdings in marginalised areas, such as mountainous areas, oases, plains, or plateaus in semi-arid-regions. The provincial Departments of Agriculture were responsible for implementing projects in pillar II and providing funds for existing or newly established farmers' organisations that applied for projects. In addition, transversal measures that accompanied projects consisted of a review of land tenure structures and water resources management, increased access to markets and improved export strategies (Faysse 2015).

Transversal measures also included institutional reforms in the Department of Agriculture as well as a reform of the agricultural advisory policy with the aim to give agricultural advisors a legal status and enable them to work for both the public and private sector. In addition, the Agricultural Development Fund, which is responsible for providing subsidies to individual farmers for diverse equipment and infrastructural development, was substantially increased (Faysse 2015).

The GMP phased out in 2020. In February 2020, King Mohamed VI announced the new agricultural strategy until 2030, Generation Green. The first objective is the socio-economic development of farmers and agricultural labour. As part of this objective, the plan promotes the establishment of a new generation of young entrepreneurs. The second objective is the further development of agricultural productivity. The plan aims to increase agricultural exports from 50 billion to 60 billion Moroccan dirham and to double the agricultural GDP by 2030 (AgriMaroc 2020; Hatim 2020).

Between 2010 and 2014, eight projects were implemented in the Meknès Province (Direction Provinciale de l'Agriculture de Meknès 2014) and twenty-nine projects were implemented in the Fès-Boulemane Province (Sebgui 2014). Until 2015, Fès-Boulemane was one of the sixteen administrative regions in Morocco. In 2015, a reform reorganised administrative boundaries and integrated Fès-Boulemane into the newly established Fès-Meknès Region. These projects provided technical and institutional support, for example improvements in irrigation infrastructure, the establishment of new agricultural cooperatives among farmers and investments in marketing measures. They have contributed to the expansion of agricultural production among smallholders, the improvement of product quality and increasing incomes of farmers.

Despite this success, studies have identified various challenges: A first problem discussed in the literature is the lack of resources, either human or financial, of the provincial agricultural departments to implement and evaluate the projects appropriately (Sebgui 2014; Faysse et al. 2014). A second problem is the value chain approach which emphasises the intensification and valorisation of individual cultivars. Sebgui (2014) argues that this approach might be useful for the first pillar, which addresses specialised agricultural production but is less applicable for small and medium-sized farms, whose production is usually diversified. A third challenge refers to how projects are implemented. Agricultural enterprises take over the land of farmers to set up plantations for two years. Before 2012, farmers were neither included in the selection of enterprises, a task in the hands of the provincial agricultural departments, nor in the evaluation of their work. In a study on eight projects in the provinces of the Fès-Meknès Region, Faysse et al. (2014) observe difficulties in communication between entrepreneurs and farmers. While farmers complained about a lack of competency and quality of the entrepreneur's work, entrepreneurs reported difficulties in collaborating with farmers. In other cases, however, cooperation worked, for example, when farmers took over the work of the enterprises on their lands, paid or unpaid.

However, the biggest problem in achieving sustainable results in the projects has been the establishment and functioning of farmers' cooperatives. To benefit from funds allocated to pillar II, farmers must organise themselves in cooperatives, a process accompanied by the provincial agricultural departments. But studies on projects in the Saïss Plain revealed that cooperatives' capacities differed significantly, and some cooperatives remained dysfunctional at the end of the project (Direction Provinciale de l'Agriculture de Meknès 2014; Faysse et al. 2014; Vitry et al. 2015). Vitry et al. (2015) conclude in line with Akesbi (2012) that the GMP (re-)produces a homogeneous view on family farms, often ignoring the social and economic differences existing within the group of small and medium-sized (family) farms. Rather than integrating small and medium-sized farmers into a 'modernised' agricultural production system, there is a risk that those who have little access to land, water and markets will be further marginalised.

3.5.2 Water for Agriculture: Irrigation Politics

Water resources management is a major concern of the Moroccan government. Due to agricultural expansion and intensification, the demand for irrigation water is continuously rising. Although most of the land is still rain-fed, irrigated agriculture is an important factor in the agro-production system, particularly during dry years, when yields on rainfed areas remain low (Aquastat 2019). Investments in Morocco's irrigation infrastructure is a key component of the country's agricultural policy. More than 135 large dams exist with a total storage capacity of 17,500 million cubic metres. In addition, hundreds of small barrages are dispersed over the country which satisfy local needs for drinking water, irrigation, and livestock watering. Their

total storage capacity is estimated to reach 100 million cubic metres (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. 2015).

In the Saïss Plain, political interventions in water management have reorganised the distribution of and access to irrigation water by diverse institutional and technical measures. Three years before the launch of the GMP, the Moroccan government founded the Sebou River Basin Agency (*Agence du Bassin hydraulique de Sebou, ABHS*) with the objective of monitoring, protecting and conserving surface and groundwater resources in the basin (Fofack 2015). As one of its first actions, the agency set up regulations for private groundwater exploitation. It prevented the drilling of new boreholes except for smallholders owning less than five hectares and confiscated illegal drilling machines. But despite new laws and institutions, the number of wells increased in the region. On the one hand, the drilling of new wells received official authorizations in the context of projects related to the GMP, whereas, on the other, unauthorised drilling of wells continued (Fofack 2015).

In another attempt to regulate groundwater exploitation, the Moroccan government has aimed to establish aquifer contracts (*contrats de nappe*), which shall regulate and improve sustainable groundwater management of all actors involved at the aquifer level. However, several challenges have slowed down the process. For example, in the Souss-Massa-Drâa River Basin, different interests of various stakeholders involved (ministries, agribusinesses, investors and smallholders), poor coordination and legal representation, as well as lack of enforcement capacity has impeded negotiations and contract implementation (Closas and Villholth 2016).

In addition to these institutional measures to control and reduce groundwater extraction, the Moroccan government promoted diverse technical instruments, such as the expansion of drip irrigation as defined in the National Program on Water Saving in Irrigation. However, Kuper et al. (2017) conclude for their study in El Hajeb that the introduction of drip irrigation “results in the reallocation of water to those that have access to groundwater and installed drip irrigation to the detriment of those who do not” (Kuper et al. 2017, p. 14).

As an alternative to strategies for efficient groundwater use, the Moroccan government plans to augment surface water supply in the region (Fofack 2015). The main project is the construction of the M'dez dam, which King Mohamed VI launched in 2015. The new dam is situated at Lake Sebou close to the city of Fès and will have a storage capacity of 700 million cubic metres. The dam is intended to contribute to the supply of electric power and domestic water but, above all, to provide 120 million cubic metres of water to the Saïss Plain, an amount exceeding the estimated groundwater deficit (Faysse et al. 2012). Construction works are supposed to end in 2024 (Chabaa 2022).

3.5.3 Agricultural Land: Changing Tenure Structures and Land Reforms

In addition to agriculture and water politics, land tenure structure is one of the most decisive factors for agricultural production. The land tenure structure in Morocco is pluralistic and recognises five predominant types of land status (Mahdi 2014, 2014; Bouderbala 1999):

- *Melk* status: Privately owned and registered lands (75.8 %);
- Collective status: Lands in the collective ownership of an ethnic group, for which they have usufruct rights, and which use is exercised under the supervision of the state (17.7 %);
- *Guich* status: Cultivated land granted as usufruct land to tribal communities by Monarchs of different Moroccan dynasties for the provision of armed men (2.75 %);
- *Habous* status: Land administered by the Ministry of Habous and Islamic Affairs to serve a religious, charitable, humanitarian, or social purpose. It cannot be sold, given away or inherited (0.67 %);
- State domain land: Land with state-owned status, mostly consisting of former public or private colonial land (3.09 %).

When Morocco became independent in 1956, the proportion of colonial land was estimated at slightly over one million hectares, of which 289,000 ha were public colonial land and 728,000 in private colonial ownership (Mahdi 2014). Between 1956 and 1960, the first Moroccan government launched a 'small agrarian reform' (*petit reforme agraire*), through which it confiscated 26,300 ha of formerly public colonial land and distributed it to smallholders. However, this reform was not able to tackle unequal land distribution, since the government did not deal with the private holdings of Europeans, who quickly began to sell their lands to wealthy Moroccans.

A first five-year plan in 1960 designed a more complex agrarian reform, which stipulated a maximum size of landholdings and aimed to expropriate public and private colonial land, fallow land, as well as land from large landowners who had benefitted from public irrigation infrastructure without paying indemnities (Swearingen 1987). It received, however, widespread opposition from the landowning elite. After revisions, 400,000 ha were acquired by wealthier Moroccans, 326,000 ha were distributed to smallholders (of which merely 70,000 ha were in irrigated zones), and between 270,000 and 300,000 ha remained in hands of the state. (Mahdi 2014).

In the 1970s, the Moroccan government launched another agrarian reform and organised farmers on redistributed and state-owned lands in cooperatives. In the 1980s the Moroccan government embarked on a path of gradual liberalisation of the agricultural sector, through which it decreased state subsidies for cooperatives. These measures, together with other challenges such as increasing conflicts among members of cooperatives, led to a decline of

the net income of cooperatives to the extent that members were not able to make necessary investments or even cover their expenses (Bossenbroek 2016; Vitry et al. 2015).

In 2005, the Moroccan government issued the so-called *de la mainlevée* or *melkisation* law, which made individual ownership of state-owned cooperative land possible (Bossenbroek 2016; Vitry et al. 2015). Former members were able to buy the plots they had cultivated, but many farmers subsequently sold parts of or the entire land they had acquired, since they either lacked the capital to take over the land and to continue agricultural production or because they fetched a good price, as in the Saïss Plain, where land prices are high. This led to new agricultural actors (see section 3.4), such as investors or lessees (Petit et al. 2018). In addition, the Moroccan government began to grant concessions for state-owned land to Moroccan and international investors through public-private partnerships. These investments must conform to the objectives of the GMP (Mahdi 2014).

3.5.4 Challenges and Risks of Agricultural Transformation

Studies quoted in this report indicate that agricultural intensification induced by agricultural, water and land politics entail socio-economic and ecological challenges and risks. Houdret et al. (2017) argue that the current transformation processes challenge the existing negotiations of this contract between the state, rural elites, and other agricultural actors. The degradation of water and land resources and negative impacts of global climate change lead to new forms of competition between different farming types over the access to resources but also demonstrate that any actor aiming for long-term benefits from agriculture needs to consider sustainable ecological solutions. Not least, other actors arise that redefine the rural social contract between the state, elites and the rural population, such as young people, but also other parts of the rural population, who claim more political participation and social justice, at least at the local level (Houdret et al. 2017).

The new agricultural and water strategy, Generation Green 2020–2030, places these social and environmental challenges at the heart of its plans. It aims to expand the agricultural middle class by increasing the salary of agricultural labour, expanding social security services and by adding at least 350,000 new farming households to the current 1.5 million households. Key component of these developments is the redistribution of one million hectares of land. However, announcements on the new agricultural strategy did not address the heterogeneity of the potential beneficiaries (those entitled with land use rights, investors, and youth), who have very different interests and means to participate in the process. All these uncertainties, Mahdi (2020) argues, make the operability and feasibility of the new agricultural strategy challenging.

Hence, the current transformation in the agro-production in the FMR bears several opportunities, but also challenges and risks. The task will be to ensure sustainability in

agricultural transformation processes by integrating not only economic factors, such as increased agricultural productivity, but also environmental protection and adaptation measures to climate change, while simultaneously aiming to mitigate social inequalities.

3.6 Challenges in the Environmental Management, Political and Social Sector in the FMR

The **Fès-Meknès Region (FMR)** is one of the most important regions in Morocco for the production of olives and olive oil. Olive oil is produced in traditional and modern mills and the olive trees are planted in traditional as well as intensive and super-intensive plantations.

These mills produce solid and liquid wastes, which can be used, after treatment, as resources for improving water and food security. The characteristics of olive mill wastewater (OMWW), margine, depend on the production system. The wastewater consists mainly of water and organic material and it is rich in fertilizing material and also contains phenols.

The direct reuse of margine as a fertilizer in agriculture is possible and applied in some of the smaller mills, but application must be limited and research is needed to investigate the effect on soil and agricultural products. Phenolic compounds in margine could be extracted from margine and reused. They can also be adsorbed or filtered to improve the reuse possibilities of the olive mill wastewater in agriculture. Olive mill wastewater is subjected to be discharged in evaporation ponds, where the water evaporates over the summer months.

The solid wastes (sludges) from the olive mills are also stored in evaporation basins, while the cernells are used to generate heat which is internally used.

Agriculture is one of the main users of water and in the last 20 years the groundwater level has fallen by around 60m indicating a non-sustainable use of the water resources. The discharge of untreated olive mill wastewater is polluting the water resources especially in the winter months, when the olive mills are in operation.

Around 54,000 hectare of olive orchards can be found in the FMR. Around 5,000 hectare are managed traditionally, 29,000 hectare super intensive with a spacing of 3 -5 m between trees and 20,000 hectare super intensive with a tree-spacing of 1-2 m. Super intensive olive farming systems are normally irrigated. A comparison between land use in 2010 and 2020 shows that there is a trend toward special concentration and larger plot sizes.

There were several reforms to restructure the agricultural sector in Morocco. One main driver is becoming more independent from grain imports. Irrigation patterns and the types of crops changed and the overall increased. The main challenges are the increasing demand and decreasing availability of water and the degraded agricultural land. With innovations in water and land management, treated waste resources in the FMR can be used to increase agricultural productivity, protect the environment and adapt to climate change.

4 Impact Assessment of Wastewater Management and Olive Oil Processing

4.1 Assessment of impact and potential of valorization of the Municipal Wastewater in the Féz-Meknés Region

W. Kirchhof, E. Mathyl, F. Elhafiane, M. Hafidi, M. Badidi, A. Essahlaoui

4.1.1 Impacts of the Municipal Wastewater Management in the FMR

In addition to the quantitative challenges, water quality is also a problem in the study area. The Sebou River Basin Agency (ABHS) has carried out several monitoring campaigns for water quality in rivers and for groundwater in the whole Sebou basin, including the Fès-Meknés study area. However, these monitoring campaigns are not conducted in a continuous way. The last campaign was conducted in 2013. The results of surface water quality analyses are compared with the simplified surface water quality table (Order No. 1275-01 of 17.10.2002). The parameters of this table refer to indicators of organic, nitrogen, phosphorus and bacterial pollution.

Table 13: Selected Surface Water Quality Parameters for the Sebou River Drain Area area , adapted from Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sebou (2014)

Water Quality Parameter	Dissolved O ₂ (mg O ₂ /L)	BOD ₅ (mg O ₂ /L)	COD (mg O ₂ /L)	NH ₄ ⁺ (mg NH ₄ ⁺ /L)	PT (mg P/L)	CF (UFC/100mL)
Excellent	>7	<3	<20	<0.1	<0.1	<20
Good	7 - 5	3 - 5	20 - 25	0.1 - 0.5	0.1 - 0.3	20 - 2,000
Medium	5 - 3	5 - 10	25 - 40	0.5 - 2	0.3 - 0.5	2,000-20,000
Poor	3 - 1	10 - 25	40 - 80	2 - 8	0.5 - 3	>20,000
Very poor	<1	>25	>80	>8	>3	

The results obtained from the campaign in 2013 showed that:

- 89 % of the primary stations had satisfactory dissolved oxygen levels and 11 % of the primary stations had very low levels.
- 77.8 % of the primary stations had low BOD₅ levels, these stations had an excellent to good quality while 22.2 % of the stations had significant levels.
- 77.8 % of the primary stations had low COD levels and 22.8 % had high levels.
- 66.7 % of the primary plants had low NH₄⁺ levels and were of excellent to average quality while 33.3 % of the primary plants had high levels and were of poor to very poor quality.
- 55.5 % of the primary stations had low levels of total phosphorus (PT) and were therefore of excellent to average quality and 44.5 % of the stations had high levels and were therefore of poor quality.
- The microbiological quality of the primary stations was good to average except for the two stations downstream Sidi Slimane and El Kouchet which had a poor quality.

The water quality of Oued Sebou has deteriorated, especially downstream from Fès to the mouth, due to adverse effects caused by the many sources of pollution. In fact, the drinking water treatment facilities that serve Kariat Ba Mohamed and Mkansa from the Oued Sebou their activities are frequently interrupted, especially during the periods of extreme pollution December-February (Olive harvest). Similarly, fish mortality is frequently observed in the Wadi Sebou (Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sebou 2016)

Poor quality is also observed in Oued Inaouene downstream of the discharge of Oued Rdom, downstream of the discharge of Meknès, Oued Sebou downstream of the discharge of Fès and Oued Tifet downstream of the discharge from Tifelt (Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sebou 2020). Figure 20 represents the quality status of the surface waters of the basin in 2004.

Figure 20: Water Quality Map of surface waters in the bassin of the Sebou (Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sebou 2004)

The data of 2013 for the Station Souk El Had, which receives the municipal waters of the city of Méknes, showed an overall poor quality, with high levels of ammonium and phosphorous (Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sebou 2014). The team from the UMI University has been conducting water quality monitoring at two different points at this location in 2022. One of the parameters monitored (electrical conductivity) showed very high values (between 1400 and 1659 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) in three campaigns. Other parameters such as pH, turbidity and nitrate were within normal values.

4.1.1.1 Wastewater treatment

In the Fès-Meknès Region (FMR), the municipal wastewater is collected and treated in 24 wastewater treatments plants. They are operated by the Moroccan institution for electricity and water "Office National de l'Electricité et de l'Eau Potable (ONEE)" (El Bouazzaoui 2019).

The WWTPs were classified according to the size of installed treatment capacity into three classes (1 population equivalent (p.e.) relates to 60 g BOD₅/day):

- Small 0 – 10,000 p.e.
- Medium 10,001 – 100,000 p.e.
- Large 100,001 and more p.e.

Figure 21: Distribution of the numbers and the installed treatment capacity of the treatment plants in the Fès-Meknès Region grouped into three capacity classes

In the Fès-Meknès Region the wastewater treatment plants (Fès, Meknès) that are categorized as big size plants with a treatment capacity of over 200,000 population equivalents (p.e.) correspond to just 12 % of all registered treatment plants, but their capacity comprises about 90 % of the total amount of wastewater in the FMR. 18 plants are classified as medium-sized and are planned to treat 16 % of the total load. 19% of the plants treat 1 % of the wastewater. About 90 % of the total wastewater is treated in Meknès and Fès. (FiW, 2020) (see Figure 21).

4.1.1.2 Study on the wastewater treatment plant at the Ain Taoujdate at the Oued Mikkès River in the FMR, Morocco

(F. Elhafiane, M. Badidi, M. Krauss)

The discharges of wastewater treatment plants can degrade the quality of receiving environments such as rivers. In the scope of the I-WALAMAR project we studied the impact of

the effluent of the station Ain Taoujdate on the physicochemical and microbiological quality of the river Oued Mikkès during the period from December 2021 to July 2022 (Figure 22).

The water samples taken from the Oued Mikkès upstream and downstream of the WWTP have been subjected to physicochemical, bacteriological, and parasitological analysis to measure all indicators of pollution.

The results show that the impact of the discharge of the WWTP is not very pronounced. We even notice an improvement of the water quality from upstream to downstream for the parameters indicating organic pollution (COD and BOD₅), a decrease of the concentrations of fecal coliforms, fecal streptococci and *E. coli*, as well as the disappearance of *Ascaris* eggs.

According to the surface water quality, Oued Mikkès is classified as poor quality for the following parameters ortho-phosphates, total phosphorus, BOD₅, COD, NTK, fecal coliforms and fecal streptococci.

The results show that the water of this river meet the standards for water intended for irrigation for the physico-chemical parameters but not for microbiological parameters.

The results also indicate that the water of the river upstream of the WWTP are polluted which is due to the presence of a discharge of an industrial unit and a population settlement along the river which is not connected to the sewerage system.

In addition, the study of the physicochemical quality of Oued Mikkès highlights the self-purification ability of the watercourse. Indeed, the parameters of organic pollution (BOD₅, COD) show a decreasing gradient from upstream to downstream.

Moreover, these waters respect the standards of water intended for irrigation for the physicochemical and non-parasitological parameters. Nutrient inputs from the Oued are estimated at 23.7 g of N, 5 g of P₂O₅ and 1.63 g of K₂O per m³ of water. These inputs can satisfy the NPK needs of olive tree, NP of alfalfa and P of onion.

Figure 22: Aerial view of the wastewater treatment plant of Ain Taouijdate (Badidi, 2022)

4.1.2 Potentials for agronomic utilization of municipal wastewater

This work focuses on the characterization of wastewater treatment by-products for resource recovery. Its main objective is to study the physical, chemical and microbiological quality of the treated wastewater and sludge of the Ain Taoujdate WWTP, as well as to quantify their input of fertilizer materials in order to recover them in case of reuse in agriculture.

The WWTP of Ain Taoujdate consists of facultative ponds. It receives wastewater from the city of Ain Taoujdate with an average flow of 2,400 m³/d. The characterization of raw wastewater and treated wastewater shows that the WWTP is efficient and according to the results of physico-chemical and microbiological analyses, the treated wastewater of the WWTP of Ain Taoujdate complies with the Moroccan discharge limit values. And according to the standards established by the WHO they are classified in category B, which allows their reuse in irrigation of cereal and fodder crops. Furthermore, farmers near the river take the water of Oued Mikess which consists of surface water mixed with treated water from WWTP discharges to irrigate their crops such as alfalfa and olive trees.

The study of the potential of treated wastewater from the WWTP for irrigation (Figure 23), shows that the discharge equals 876,000 m³ water per year with quantities of 14.52 tonnes N per year, 6.91 tonnes P per year, 9.32 tonnes K per year, 16.07 tonnes Ca per year, 7.41 tonnes Mg per year and 0.16 tonnes B per year.

In addition, the area irrigable by treated wastewater of the WWTP can reach a total of 4772.4 ha, the reuse also generates a significant economic gain of 2410.4 DH/ha and reduces the carbon footprint by 135 t of CO_{2eq}.

Figure 23: The discharge of treated wastewater from WWTP of Ain Taoujdate

The physico-chemical characterization of the sludge produced by the WWTP shows its richness in organic matter and its abundance in nutrients, providing annually, in tons, respectively: 0.32 of N, 0.57 of P₂O₅, 0.84 of K₂O, 34.03 of CaO, 6.58 of MgO, 0.3 of Na₂O, 17.86 of SO₄, 0.05 of Manganese, 2.93 of Iron, 0.05 of Copper and 0.3 of Zinc.

Heavy metals are present without exceeding European standards and from a microbiological point of view, the results show that the sludge does not pose a risk to public health after a storage period of one year or more.

In comparison, the physical-chemical analysis of a treated sludge derived from the municipal wastewater treatment plant Simmerath, Germany is shown in Table 14. The small town of Simmerath is representative for a rural settlement. The wastewater derived from this area is characterized only by agricultural origins and some villages. The sludge was used for development of soil additives within the I-WALAMAR project.

Table 14: Physical-chemical analysis values of the sludge from the wastewater treatment plant Simmerath, Germany (Fuchs-Heinen 2021)

Parameter	Unit	Value
Water content	% original sludge	77.4
Dry matter (DM) after 105 °C	% original sludge	22.6
Analysis of dry matter (DM) after 105 °C		
Ash content after 815 °C	% DM	29.4
Incineration loss after 550 °C	% DM	69.9
Hydrogen (H) free of water (wf)	% DM	5.1
Carbon total wf	% DM	34.3
Nitrogen wf	% DM	5.5
Sulfur (S) total wf	% DM	0.61
Chlor total wf	% DM	0.1
Antimon (An)	mg/ kg DM	1.3
Lead (Pb)	% DM	32.9
Cadmium (Cd)	% DM	1.2
Chromium total (Cr)	% DM	25.5
Copper (Cu)	% DM	145
Nickel (Ni)	% DM	26.6
Phosphor total (P)	% DM	2.89
Oxyds (calculated)		
Calcium as CaO	% DM	1.57
Potassium as K ₂ O	% DM	0.22
Magnesium as MgO	% DM	0.5
Phosphorus as P ₂ O ₅	% DM	6.6

4.2 Assessment of Impacts and Potentials for agronomic valuation of the Olive Oil Processing in the Féz-Meknés Region

(W. Kirchhof, J. Möller, F. Elhafiane, M. Hafidi, L. Ouzahra, M. Krauss)

4.2.1 Impacts of the olive processing in the Féz-Meknés Region

The olive industry in Morocco has undergone notable transformations in recent years, thanks to the implementation of the agricultural sector's development plan. With the introduction of the Green Morocco Plan and the subsequent surge in demand for olives and their by-products, the olive sector has witnessed remarkable expansion in both cultivation areas and production output. Consequently, this growth has been accompanied by a parallel increase in the generation of effluents. These effluents, resulting from the olive crushing process, possess high acidity levels and are laden with organic matter, consequently causing considerable disruptions and nuisances in the surrounding environment.

The olive processing industry operates within the constraints of a seasonal nature. The meticulous task of harvesting olives must be carried out within a limited time frame of optimal ripeness, specifically in Morocco ranging from early November to late February, followed by

immediate processing. Given that the quality of the resulting oil experiences a notable decline over time, it is customary to engage in decentralized processing primarily within the olive-growing regions themselves.

Within all the delineated processes outlined below, the fundamental procedure remains unvarying. In this vein, the olives undergo an initial stage of meticulous washing and meticulous separation from leaves and twigs. Subsequently, the pitted olives are subjected to crushing, leading to the creation of a pulpy consistency. To extract the oil, various techniques such as malaxation, centrifugation, or pressing are employed to effectively separate it from any residual substances. Notably, the quantity and quality of the obtained oil, alongside the composition and quantities of residual materials, as well as the requisite volumes of process and washing water, exhibit variations across these diverse methods, which are detailed below.

Compared to the size of traditional plants, the industrial plants are significantly larger. However, there are far fewer traditional plants than industrial ones. The industrial plants differ mainly in the use of two different types of decanters, which also have a strong influence on the generation of residual substances (Niaounakis and Halvadakis 2006).

Pressing process: The traditional pressing process, which is still widely used around the world today, is characterized by its simple mechanical procedure. The olives are crushed from large stone chunks and the crushed pieces are then pressed in a large trough. Due to the often rapid processing at the "right" time, the olive oil from these processes is usually of good quality. Due to the small quantities and the little industrial processing, these oils are usually not marketed internationally, but locally marketed and consumed locally (Hruschka 2021; Doula et al. 2017).

3-phase process: The 3-phase process is the more traditional process between the two industrial processes. The difference is named after the decanter used, which divides the material into three phases. The three phases are olive oil, fruit water and olive pomace. The residues produced are margine (fruit water) and grignon sec, depending on different factors, such as the exact production process (e.g., the temperature and retention time in the mash) or the degree of ripeness of the olives at the time of harvest, as well as the storage time before and after the washing process, the residue streams have different compositions. They have a high organic load, low pH and difficult components such as phenols and fats that can lead to negative environmental impacts (Hruschka 2021; Doula et al. 2017).

2-phase process: In the 1990s, the 2-phase process was developed in response to problems with the residual streams and was first introduced in Spain. The process is identical to the 3-phase system except for the decanter. Due to the different way the decanter works, only two phases are produced. The fruit water is discharged together with the olive pulp. This process was developed because of the major problems with the resulting material flows. Because only

about half of the process and wash water is required, the resulting material flow is significantly smaller. It is reduced by about half. However, this also means that the concentration of problematic components in the residual material stream is about twice as high (Hruschka 2021; Doula et al. 2017).

Summary: In Spain 100 % of olive oil production is covered by industrial production. Of this, more than 90 % is produced by the newer 2-phase process. In Greece 80 % of olives are still treated in 3-phase decanters. In total, however, about 20 % of the production is processed in traditional presses, although they still represent about 80 % of the number of presses. In Morocco, the IWALAMAR industry partner OLEAFOOD has modified all 3-phase decanter into 2-phase decanter, after testing the 2-phase-process for 5 years. (Taccari and Ciani 2011; El Bouazzaoui 2019)

Estimation of the olive oil wastewater load in the FMR: For the FMR it is estimated that the olive oil processing wastewater, equivalent to about 10 million p.e. is produced and dumped into the open sewers during the months November, December, January and February. As this is 2.5 times the municipal wastewater generated continuously over the year (about 4 million p.e.) the non-treated olive mill wastewater is a severe overload of the municipal treatment plants and subsequently of the receiving waters.

4.2.2 Agronomic valuation

(F. Elhafiane, M. Hafidi, L. Ouzahra, M. Tabib)

The aim of this study revolves around the assessment of the agronomic value of margins for the agricultural lands within the city of Meknès. The deposition of margins in the Fès-Meknès region is estimated at 154,531 m³/year for all two-phase systems and 1,165,517 m³/year for all three-phase systems. It is worth noting that the margins found in the Fès-Meknès Region exhibit a complete absence of microbiological pollution indicators and a deficiency of metallic trace elements.

When adopting a three-phase system, the annual contribution of these vegetative waters is projected to yield approximately 79,424 tons of organic matter, 3,077 tons of nitrogen, 61 tons of phosphorus, and 283,675 tons of potassium. Conversely, under a two-phase system, the estimated contributions would be 10,531 tons of organic matter, 408 tons of nitrogen, 8 tons of phosphorus, and 37,611 tons of potassium. This underscores the significance of utilizing these margins as fertilizers through direct application on agricultural lands.

Furthermore, if these margins were subjected to biomethanization, their potential for energy recovery would be remarkably high. In Morocco as a whole, potential electricity production with biomethanization from margins is projected to range between 15.88 GWhs and 85.45 GWhs, while within the Fès-Meknès Region, the estimates range from 5.68 GWhs to 42.83 GWhs.

These figures highlight the substantial opportunities for harnessing the energy potential embedded within this waste stream.

4.3 Simplified material flow analysis and recycling options for alternative resources from the municipal wastewater treatment and the olive oil industry in the FMR, Morocco

(W. Kirchhof, J. Möller, M. Krauss)

4.3.1 Introduction

A simplified material flow analysis (MFA) was applied to describe the dimension of annual material flows in the FMR, focused on two main sectors:

- the municipal wastewater treatment plants (example WWTP Meknés) and
- the regional olive oil processing industry.

The calculation and visualisation of results were done by applying the opensource software package Stan2Web.

Material flow analysis, established itself as one of the basic tools for a balance of a defined space (spatially and temporally) and thereby have the conservation of mass as a basic principle.

Common MFA applications include system analysis, problem identification, and scenario development to provide input to support policy decisions. The results are presented in eSankey diagrams to make complex relationships easier to understand and to show the various interrelationships. Individual material flows in the system are shown in relation to their mass. The availability of data is critical to the design of a life cycle assessment and the validity of the results. This and the uncertainties of the data are the reasons why only a simplified MFA was carried out. Data gaps were filled by reference data from historical records, own experimental data and similar data from the olive oil sector of other regions, e.g. Spain.

4.3.2 Methods

4.3.2.1 Determination of input data

Determination of assumptions: The period chosen is one year. The sectors considered are fully covered for one year. For olive plantations and olive pressing, the periods of fertilization (June-July, August-September) and harvesting (November-February) were considered.

The open source program Stan2Web was used to create the model and the corresponding material flow balances. The data was entered into the program through a prepared Excel

spreadsheet. The corresponding input columns are assigned to the material flows of the same name in the program.

The models of the two sectors are kept separate because the material flows of the WWTP are much larger and there are no direct links between the sectors. For both models (WWTP and olive oil production) two scenarios (baseline (single line production and recycling)) with four categories (goods, water, nitrogen and phosphorus) have been developed.

Determination of input data for the wastewater treatment plant Meknès model and the olive oil processing model

For the material flows, the model input data are calculated from the measurement data of the Meknès wastewater treatment plant (Table 15) from 2018.

Table 15: Input data of the wastewater treatment model for the baseline scenario

Material	Goods	Water	Nitrogen	Phosphorus
	Annual Flow [Mg/a]	Concentration [Mg/Mg goods]	Concentration [g/Mg goods]	Concentration [Mg/Mg goods]
WWTP inlet	31,536,000	0.97	105.0	29.67
WETP outlet	28,382,400	0.97	27	5.73
Evaporation	3,153,600	1.0	0	0
Sewage	1,200	0.17	0.094	0.049

The following assumptions and calculations were performed:

- For the liquid streams, a density of 1 g/cm³ or 1 Mg/m³.
- In the wastewater treatment plant, an evaporation rate of 10 % is assumed.
- The reported sewage sludge quantities differ (El Bouazzaoui 2019). The recorded data for the withdrawal is 5,400 t in five years, i.e., 1,080 t per year. From other sources the annual withdrawal is assumed to be 1,200 t. Therefore, an uncertainty of 10 % is assumed.
- For the effluent of the wastewater treatment plant, a water content of 97 % was assumed with a fluctuation of 2 %.
- The data for the nitrogen and phosphorus fractions are different for night and day. Automatic recording is missing; an even distribution was assumed for the total water amount. Therefore, one third of the nighttime values and two thirds of the daytime values are included in the balance.
- The composition of the sewage sludge from Meknès is not available. For the dry matter 22.5 % of total sludge, for Nitrogen 5.5 % of dried matter and for Phosphorus 2.9 % of dried matter was assumed. These values derived from the analysis of a sewage sludge that has been treated by a similar method in Germany (sewage treatment plant in Simmerath, Kirchhof 2021)

Determination of input data for olive oil production

As data are limited, measurements from other regions and studies are integrated in the model approach. Table 16 shows the values considered for the model calculation.

Additional assumptions and preliminary calculations were made.

- The model represents all three process options of olive oil production (traditional pressing, 2-phase decanter and 3-phase decanter). As the number of applications of the processes in the region is not known at the time of study, it was decided to distribute the quantity of olives produced equally among the three processes. In this way, the differences between the processes are clearly visible in the result diagrams and are not distorted.
- As a basis, 628,000 t of olives per year were assumed (Departement de l'Agriculture 2021). These were distributed equally among the three processes.
- The proportions of water, nitrogen and phosphorus were taken from a study considering all three processes. (Souilem et al. 2017)

The material flow quantities [Mg/a] of the three processes were also calculated, using the specific waste quantities [Mg waste/Mg olive] as follows (data after Koppen 1997; Medouni-Haroune et al. 2018):

- For olive press process: 0.5 Mg margine / Mg olives; 0.5 Mg grignon / Mg olives
- For 2-phase decanter: 1.1 Mg margine / Mg olives; 0.5 Mg grignon / Mg olives
- For 3-phase decanter: 0.2 Mg margine / Mg olives; 0.8 Mg grignon / Mg olives

Table 16: Input data of olive oil processing for the baseline scenario

Material	Goods	Water	Nitrogen	Phosphorus
	Annual [Mg/a]	Flow	Concentration [Mg/Mg goods]	Concentration [g/Mg goods]
			Concentration [Mg/Mg goods]	Concentration [Mg/Mg goods]
Olive press process				
Olive fruits	209,333			
Liquid phase Margine	104,667	0.93	0.009	0.006
Grignon sec (Pomace)	104,667	0.27	0.007	0.0025
Olive oil	41,866	0	0	0
3-Phase decanter process				
Olive fruits	209,333			
Liquid phase Margine	230,266	0.93	0.009	0.006
Grignon sec (Pomace)	104,667	0.50	0.005	0.0025
Olive oil	41,867	0	0	0
2-Phases decanter process				
Olive fruits	209,333			
Liquid phase Margine	41,867	0.93	0.009	0.006
Grignon hum (Cake)	167,467	0.57	0.004	0.0012
Olive oil	43,960	0	0	0

4.3.2.2 Scenario development

The scenario analysis focuses on the maximum possible reuse of material flows in the considered industries. In all scenarios used here, a technically possible reuse of material flows was considered. Whether this is socially and economically feasible is not considered here. What has been included is the legal/normative evaluation of the safe recycling of conditioned material flows, e.g. sewage sludge.

In the model, it is assumed that the material flows from both sub-models (wastewater treatment and olive oil processing) can be fully utilized for reuse in agriculture. The focus of the agricultural component is on olives. There are several studies on the compatibility of residues from olive oil production in olive groves.

For the sub-model “olive oil processing” a complete material recovery was modelled. Since margine is approved for application in agriculture under certain regulations in many countries and is not prohibited in Morocco, a complete reuse is assumed. The application rate was limited to 50 m³/ha according to Italian guidelines.

The agricultural reuse of grignon is more controversial. Composting was modelled as the most suitable treatment method with a high reuse rate. A complete return to agriculture is assumed.

4.3.3 Results

4.3.3.1 Recycling potential of resources from the municipal wastewater

The calculated values of the submodel “Wastewater treatment” are shown in Table 17. All values were adjusted in this step to compensate for the inaccuracies and to ensure an emerging mass balance. The calculated recycling potential for agricultural reuse totals 28,514,255 t per year, of which 27,657,860 t is water. The recycling potentials of the nutrients nitrogen and phosphorus are 923 t per year and 192 t per year.

Table 17: Output data of the wastewater treatment model for the recycling scenario, combining water and fertilizer reuse

Material	Goods		Water		Nitrogen		Phosphorus	
	Annual Flow [Mg/a]		Annual Flow [Mg/a]		Annual Flow [Mg/a]		Annual Flow [Mg/a]	
WWTP inlet	31,536,009		30,679,614		923		192	
WWTP outlet (a)	28,513,045		27,657,654		912		186	
Evaporation	3,021,754		3,021,754		0		0	
Sewage (b)	1,209		205		11		6	
Recycling potential (a)+(b)	28,514,255		27,657,860		923		192	

Figure 24 shows the Sankey diagram of the recycling scenario at the level of goods (water, sewage sludge, nitrogen, phosphorus). All material flows are shown. The left side shows the inlet of the WWTP and the right and bottom side shows the outlets. The treated effluent, the estimated evaporation in the lagoons and the removed sludge are shown. In the baseline scenario, it is assumed that all three effluents are landfilled without reuse, evaporate, or are discharged to receiving waters. In the recycling scenario, shown here, it is assumed that the wastewater is re-used for irrigation and the sludge re-used as fertilizing or soil-improving substance.

Note: Numbers represent the annual flow in Mg(=tons).

Figure 24: eSankey-Diagramme: recycling scenario wastewater treatment plant Mekkès in the FMR (FiW, 2022)

4.3.4 Recycling potential of resources from the olive oil industry

An overview of the results of the olive oil production sub model is shown in Table 18. In all procedures, only the missing amount of process water, as well as the unknown composition of the inflowing olive stream, was calculated. This is because for the mass flows on goods level also in the input values no uncertainties were given. It is noticeable that the necessary inflow by process water in the 3-phase process is significantly larger than in the others. This corresponds to the literature data. The calculated composition of the olive streams is also very similar in all processes and can represent a kind of control value. The result for recyclable material streams is a total of 753,600 t per year. Of these, 551,481 t are water, 5,580 t are nitrogen and 9,695 t are phosphorus.

Table 18: Output data of the olive oil processing for the recycling scenario in Mg per Mg olives and in Mg per annum

Material	Goods Annual Flow [Mg/a]	Water Annual Flow [Mg/Mg]	Nitrogen Annual Flow [Mg/Mg]	Phosphorus Annual Flow [Mg/Mg]
Olive pressing				
Olive fruits	209,333	0.52	0.01	0,02
Process water	41,867	1.00	0.00	0,00
Liquid phase Margine	104,667	0.93	0.009	0,0060
Grignon sec (Pomace)	104,667	0.27	0,0071	0,0025
Olive oil	41,866	0.00	0,00	0,00
3-phase decanter process				
Olive fruits	209,333	0.48	0,01	0,019
Process water	167,467	1.00	0,00	0,00
Liquid phase Margine	230,266	0.93	0,009	0,0060
Grignon sec (Pomace)	104,667	0.52	0,0051	0,0025
Olive oil	41,867	0.00	0,00	0,00
2-phase decanter process				
Olive fruits	209,333	0.44	0,01	0,01
Process water	41,867	1.00	0,00	0,00
Liquid phase Margine	41,867	0.93	0,009	0,0060
Grignon hum (Cake)	167,467	0.57	0,0043	0,0012
Olive oil	43,960	0.00	0,00	0,00
Total recycling of margine and grignon [t/a]				
Margine	376,800	350,424	3,391	2,261
Grignon hum and sec	376,800	201,057	2,189	7,434
Sum of Margine and grignons	753,600	551,481	5,580	9,675

For the olive oil sector, Figure 25 shows the Sankey diagram of the recycling scenario on the level of goods (water, sewage sludge, nitrogen, phosphorus).

Olive Oil Production, Recycling Scenario, Layer: Goods

Note: Numbers represent the annual flow in Mg (=tons).

Figure 25: eSankey-Diagramme: all goods, recycling scenario olive oil production in the FMR (FiW, 2022)

Six material flows (harvested olives, process water, for the three different treatment processes (hydraulic press, 2-phase decanter, and 3-phase decanter) are shown on the lower left side in Figure 25. On the upper left side, the total material of recycled substances, expressed as fertilizer is shown. This total material flow comprises the liquid phase and the solid phase assuming that the solids are treated by a composting process. In the baseline scenario, it was assumed that all effluents are evaporated in constructed basins, partly discharged to receiving waters, or used as burning materials. In the recycling scenario, shown here, it is assumed that the liquid phase is used for irrigation and the solid phase as fertilizing or soil-improving substance.

4.3.5 Conclusions material flow analysis

Notwithstanding the limitations mentioned above, based on the results, recycling of material flows is recommended. The potential for more sustainable management of existing land is great.

By comparing the considered material flows with the legal requirements for reuse in agriculture, it was found that for all considered material flows there is a possibility to reuse them as materials in agriculture.

There are specific regulations in Morocco for the reuse of treated wastewater in agriculture. These are complied with for the most part. In accordance with European Union (EU) guidelines, a disinfection stage is nevertheless recommended.

The study shows that the greatest potential is in reuse of water as irrigation water. A total of over 27 million m³ is produced annually. Since no precise data on the composition is available, the suitability of the material flow cannot be definitively determined.

Although sewage sludge is classified as hazardous waste in Morocco, there is no specific regulation on the circumstances under which it may be reused. The complete reuse after a longer storage period was considered.

It is assumed that targeted application of margins as liquid fertiliser is effective according to a review of the literature. Composting was assumed for the gridnot, which also has no significant influence on the composition of the material flow. There are no specific regulations in Morocco for either of these material flows. Legal regulations of other countries, such as of Italy, recommend application of margins as liquid fertilizer of up to 50 m³/ha*a. Field test results with margine are shown in chapter 5.

As the data situation is uncertain, it is recommended that further analysis is commissioned before adjusting the material flows. In particular, only preliminary data are available for sewage sludge. Data on treated wastewater are also incomplete. As irrigation with treated wastewater can be logistically challenging and, if applied incorrectly, can contribute to soil salinisation, it is only recommended with an appropriate management approach.

Acceptance among the population regarding the reuse of sewage sludge is unclear. Therefore, participatory involvement and corresponding communication would be necessary here.

It is important to note that it is not recommended to use margine as irrigation water, but rather as a liquid fertiliser, limited to 50 m³/ha*a.

The material flows of olive oil production have the potential to cover the demand for mineral fertiliser in olive cultivation to a large extent. Two thirds of the demand for nitrogen fertiliser can be met. Phosphorus accounts for several times the demand.

4.4 Summarizing outcomes of Impact assessment of the Municipal Wastewater Management and the Olive Oil Processing in the Féz-Meknés Region

M. Krauss, W. Kirchhof, E. Mathyl

The water quality of the Sebou has deteriorated, especially downstream from Fès to the mouth, due to adverse effects caused by the many sources of pollution. Drinking water treatment facilities from the Sebou interrupt their activities frequently, especially during the periods of extreme pollution from December to February (Olive harvest). Similarly, fish mortality is frequently observed. Poor quality is also observed in Oued Inaouene downstream of the discharge of Oued Rdom downstream of the discharge of Meknès.

The municipal wastewater management in the FMR is decisively done in the WWTP of Meknès and in Fés, where nearly 90 % of the total wastewater amount of FMR is collected, treated, and discharged into the river system of the Sebou River. Exemplarily, impacts on the river water quality of the WWTP of Ain Taoujdate as a medium-size WWTP were assessed. Analysis results don't indicate severe pollution at the discharge point, but indicate that there are wastewater sources upstream of the WWTP which are polluting the river.

Investigations at the WWTP Ain Taoujdate and the nearby river indicate, that effluent from the WWTP complies with categorie B for standards established by the WHO. In category B irrigation of cereal and fodder drops would be possible. With reusing water from the WWTP Ain Taoujdate around 4800 ha of land could be irrigated including a fertilizing effect of 14.5 tons of Nitrogen, 6.9 tons of Phosphorous and 9.3 tons of Kalium. The results show the high potential for direct and indirect wastewater reuse. It must be thoroughly monitored if microbiological parameters are met and farmers need to be educated how to safely irrigate with treated wastewater. Sewage sludge could be safely reused in agriculture after a storage time of over one year.

The olive oil sector is still enlarging the capacity in order to reach the national strategic aim. There is a change to larger mills. Three different production types are used: "pressing", "3-phase decanter" and "2-phase decanter". Switching the process from 3-phase decanter to 2-phase decanter is leading to a reduction of the water requirements of around 50 %. The concentration of pollutants in the wastewater is twice as high. The total wastewater load from olive mills is estimated to be around 2.5 times of the total design capacity of municipal wastewater treatment plants. Considering that OMWW is only produced during November to February this can lead to an overload of municipal wastewater treatment plants, with a significant decline in the effluent water quality and a subsequent severe pollution of the receiving water bodies.

The material flow analysis for the FMR, focusing on the olive mill sector and the WWTP of Meknès shows a big potential for reusing liquid and solid wastewater streams. Regarding the potential from the municipal wastewater treatment plant in Meknès, around 28 million m³ could be reused as irrigation water, with additional around 900 tons of Nitrogen and 186 tons of Phosphorous for fertilizing effects within the irrigation water. The recycling potential from the olive mill sector can be estimated to be around 5.500 t of Nitrogen and 9.600 t of Phosphorous.

Additionally, 350.000 m³ of water could potentially be reused. Tests with innovative technologies on how to reuse the different waste streams are presented in the following chapter.

5 Innovations to improve food and water security

5.1 Adaptation of HPLC Analysis for the Identification and Qualification of Residuals in Water Resources derived as Wastewater and Waste from the Olive Oil Sector

(M. Bennani, N. Ittobane, A. Maaroufi, D. Schmitz, S. Allaoui)

HPLC is an important analytical method, suitable for the analysis of different polyphenols in olive oil production residuals. In the project I-WALAMAR, a semi-preparative HPLC was used. The analysis method is used to analyze different olive residuals and to analyze treated residuals (filtration, adsorption) regarding their polyphenol composition and amounts.

Based on this selection, measurements for the selection of an appropriate separation column for the HPLC were carried out. Additionally, samples provided by project partner Oleafood, were analyzed according to the selected reference polyphenols for first experiments regarding the olive mill wastewater (OMWW) composition.

Figure 26: Selected phenolic compounds for column selection and first analyses and their chemical structure (FHAC, 2022)

Figure 26 shows the separation of the selected standards on the finally selected columns (Eurospher II 100-5 C18A, 250 x 4 mm ID with precolumn).

Figure 27: Chromatographic separation of the selected standards on Eurospher II 100-5 C18A column. (Böttcher and Monks 2020)

Separation of the used polyphenolic substances is achieved by measuring with methanol-water (with 0.2 % phosphoric acid) mixture (gradient: 90-10 to 0-100) with a flow rate of 1.2 mL/min. Column temperature was maintained at 30 °C. These settings were used for the further experiments.

First analyses of the wastewater residuals from OLEAFOOD were also carried out using this column type. The chromatograms are shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28: Exemplary chromatograms of the analyzed washing-/wastewater samples from Oleafood (July 2020) („Margine-Olive Wastewater“ (left), „Margine-Basin“ (right), C18A-Säule)(Böttcher and Monks 2020)

Additionally to the selected substances, a wide range of other polyphenols and other components are present in the samples. All of the selected phenolic compounds were found throughout the samples (not all data shown), except quercetin. Main components are tyrosol

and hydroxytyrosol. Therefore, in further analyses of olive residuals, they will be in focus together with oleuropein. Oleuropein is the main (glycosylated) secoiridoid in the olive, from which tyrosol and hydroxytyrosol are derived as degradation products.

The results of this screening were published as an application manual by the company KNAUER with additional analyses of olive oil (Böttcher and Monks 2020).

Table 19: Analyses of the provided OMWW samples (Oleafood, Morocco, July 2020) and decanter phase (filtrate, GEA, Spain February 2021).

Sample	pH	DM [%]	TPC [g GAE/kg (DM)] ([g/L])	DM (MeOH extract) [mg/mL]	TPC [g GAE/kg (DM)] (MeOH extract)	Ty [g/L]	HTy [g/L]	Ole [g/L]
„Margine Olive Wastewater“	5.70	3.09	68.61 (2.12)	-	-	0.48	0.54	-
„Margine Basin“	4.47	9.20	39.24 (3.61)	-	-	0.41	0.18	0.05
„Spain-water“	4.97	3.63	124.52 (4.52)	-	-	-	-	-
„Spain-solid extract“	-	-	-	50.0	1.46	-	-	-

A semi-preparative HPLC-system was procured in the project I-WALAMAR and installed at UMI. Measurements of olive oil production residuals and treated (adsorption, filtration) residuals were analyzed via HPLC. Quali- and quantification of tyrosol (Ty), hydroxytyrosol (HTy) and oleuropein (Ole) was done.

Figure 29: Schematic illustration of the semi-preparative HPLC-analysis system KNAUER (Knaur Wissenschaftliche Geräte GmbH 2022)

The analyses and results of polyphenols in different olive oil production residual samples will be discussed in the corresponding chapters 5.3 and 5.4.

5.2 Analysis of the Environmental (Water, Climate) Monitoring Systems in the FMR

5.2.1 Design and construction of a pilot station for monitoring olive wastewater

(J. Ramirez, F. Grimmeisen)

One of the key issues identified regarding problems and challenges for water resources management (surface and groundwater) in the Saïss Plain region, was the need for more monitoring data, especially concerning the environment and water quality. The main institution responsible for water quality monitoring in the region is the Sebou River Basin Agency (ABHS). Among other tasks, ABHS collects data on climate (precipitation, temperature, etc.), river discharge, groundwater levels, as well as surface and groundwater quality in the whole Sebou River Basin. However, the monitoring campaigns for water quality are conducted very sporadically, and the most recent data available is from the year 2013 according to the Inventory of the Degree of Pollution of Water Resources in the Sebou Basin (Inventaire De Degre De Pollution des Ressources En Eau Dans Le Bassin De Sebou, Agence du Bassin Hydraulique du Sebou 2014).

For this reason, the work package Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) developed a strategy for supporting water quality monitoring in the Saïss Plain with two different goals and tasks.

The first goal was to develop, test and install a monitoring station (fixed installation with different sensors, datalogger and transmission system), **which can measure the impacts of the olive wastewater at the treatment facilities.**

For the design and construction of the pilot station the company Seba Hydrometrie provided two different types of sensors. The first one was a multiparameter probe model MPS-D8, which can measure the following parameters: water level, temperature, conductivity, salinity, TDS, pH Value, water density, turbidity and TSS. The second sensor was a Fluorometer probe model enviroFlu, for measurements of PAH (polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons), which allows to detect oil in water through UV fluorescence.

The two probes are connected to a SEBA datalogger (model UnilogCom; compare Figure 30) including an online transmission system in a cabinet, which needs to be connected to an electrical power outlet in order for the pilot station to run. The monitoring system contains an internal battery, which allows to record measurements and to send data for a couple of days, even if the power is interrupted.

Figure 30: SEBA equipment used for the pilot monitoring station of olive wastewater: a. multiparameter probe MPS-D8 for water quality (left), fluorometer probe enviroFlu (right) and b. cabinet with datalogger UniLog-Com, transmission system and internal battery for power outage, source: SEBA, 2023

5.2.1.1 Installation and test of a pilot monitoring station at the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) in Stolberg, Germany

(J. Ramirez, F. Grimmeisen)

Measurements were carried out as pre-study for the application of SEBA-fluorescence probe to detect polyphenols (PP) in the wastewater treatment plant of the city of Stolberg (near Aachen) in Germany before transportation and installation in Morocco. The partners of FiW and FH-Aachen organized the transport and set-up of all sensors, electrical cabinet, computer, laboratory and safety equipment for handling wastewater.

For calibration, a model-PP solution (tyrosol) and olive wastewater were measured in aqueous medium using the fluorometer and multiparameter sensors. Additionally, UV-measurements were carried out on olive wastewater added to water to monitor the total phenolic content.

Figure 31: Photo of Wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) in the city of Aachen-Stolberg, Germany., source: FiW, 2022

The tests (experiments) were conducted in the following way:

- A beaker was filled with water (distilled, tap water, wastewater)
- Both sensors were then fixed inside the beaker (fluorescence and multiparameter probe)
- A stirrer was used for continuous mixing
- Finally, the following steps were repeated: addition of sample, mixing, measuring, data collection

The four experiments conducted were:

- Gallic acid (GA) in tap water.
- Tyrosol (TY) in distilled water.
- Olive mill wastewater (OWW) in distilled water.
- Olive mill wastewater (OWW) in sewage wastewater.

Figure 32: Experimental set for tests applying gallic acid in tap water, olive wastewater in distilled water and olive wastewater in sewage wastewater in Stolberg, Germany., source: FiW, 2022

5.2.1.2 Analysis of data and results from tests (experiments) at WWTP in Stolberg, Germany.

(J. Ramirez, F. Grimmeisen, D. Schmitz)

Gallic acid (GA) in tap water.

Gallic acid (GA) is classified as a phenolic acid. The results showed the sensitivity regarding GA works for a probe adjusted for polyaromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) such as the fluorometer EnviroFlu. A saturation of the signal was observed.

Figure 33: Fluorometer measurements using Gallic acid (GA) in tap water. PAH value independence of pH, gallic acid concentration (FHAC 2022)

Tyrosol (TY) in distilled water

The tap water zero value in TY was high, between 100 and 200 PAH compared to about 10 in GA (Figure 34, left). Distilled water was used as a matrix, with another higher value result (about 60) compared to tap water in Stolberg (the detector limit for the fluorometer is 5,000 PAH).

Measurements with TY as model Polyphenol (PP) present in olive wastewater were done at FH Aachen, high sensitivity was shown and a linear behavior from about 0-2.5 mg/L (Figure 34, right).

Figure 34: Fluorometer measurements using Tyrosol (TY) in distilled water. PAH value independence of pH, gallic acid concentration (FHAC 2022)

Olive wastewater (OWW) in distilled water.

The data analysis showed an increase of PAH value upon addition of OWW until a maximum value. Further addition leads to saturation/decrease. Different mixtures of water-OWW showed higher values compared to pure OWW (the PAH of OWW alone was 236 ug/L).

A comparison with total phenolic content has in general a similar behavior, showing a linear relationship up to 20 mL added OWW.

Figure 35: Fluorometer measurements using OWW in distilled water. PAH value independence of OWW concentration (FHAC 2022)

Olive wastewater in domestic wastewater.

The results showed a similar behavior as with the use of TY, the zero values vary a lot. The addition of OWW leads to decrease/saturation of the PAH value.

One important element to consider, is the amount of OWW in municipal wastewater in Morocco, and the difference with respect to the tests (experiments) conducted in Germany. Unfortunately, this data has not been available. For this reason, we also tested very high concentrations.

Figure 36: Fluorometer measurements using OWW in municipal wastewater. PAH value independence of OWW concentration (FHAC 2022)

5.2.1.3 Installation of monitoring station at WWTP Ain Taoujdat

F. Grimmeisen

The results of the test (experiments) conducted showed that the use of a fluorometer sensor (PAH measurements) can be used to monitor the impacts of olive wastewater in Morocco. The next step is the installation of the pilot station at a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) located in the study area. Unfortunately, different important issues affected the transport from Germany to Morocco, for this reason, the company Seba has extended the time for the implementation of the project. The monitoring equipment is already in Morocco since beginning of May 2023 and was tested successfully (Figure 37) to be ready for implementation at the WWTP Ain Taoujdat wastewater treatment plant. Unfortunately, the permission for installation at WWTP Ain Taoujdat was not available during the duration of the project period. Therefore, the final implementation and testing is currently planned for the second half of the year 2023. SEBA will continue supporting the installation process despite the end of the project.

Figure 37: SEBA monitoring station during test preparation before installation at UMI Meknès in May 2023; b. Wiring diagram of SEBA monitoring station for wastewater quality monitoring and olive wastewater.

5.2.2 Development of a water quality monitoring

(J. Ramirez, A. Essahlaoui)

5.2.2.1 Definition of water quality parameters, surface and groundwater monitoring

After reviewing the current situation of water resources in the Saïss Plain, the I-WALAMAR team agreed on the importance of monitoring key parameters in both surface and groundwater. For surface water, the most important parameters agreed upon were: temperature, pH, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, turbidity and TDS. For groundwater, the parameters selected were nitrate, nitrite, phosphate, and ammonia, as well as pH, conductivity, and salinity measurements. Once the parameters were selected, a review of existing mobile sensors was conducted using several criteria including: portability, ease of operation, calibration and maintenance, data connectivity, and battery life. In the end, the Hanna Instruments HI 9829 multiparameter and the PCE-CP 22 compact photometer were selected.

The team of FiW tested the sensors in Germany and organized the transportation to Morocco. The next step, was to conduct several training activities on the assembling, operation and calibration of the devices. Similarly, a short training on the best way to save and download the data was conducted. Capacity building activities in Morocco for using water monitoring equipment in the field and in the laboratory were realized in April and in May 2022 in Meknès, Morocco.

Figure 38: Photos of assembling the multiparameter sensor on-site in Morocco and preparing a water sample for measurement with compact photometer in the water laboratory of the UMI in Meknès (UMI and FIW, 2022)

5.2.2.2 Development of surveys, collection of geodata, reports and time series data for the design of a cadastre and monitoring network (site selection) (UMI and FiW).

The FiW team developed several surveys to collect data during the field work in Morocco. The first surveys were designed to collect data on the location and characteristics of: a) pollution sources (olive mills), b) surface water sources, and c) groundwater sources. In addition, for the water quality monitoring activities, FiW and UMI also developed survey forms to collect structured data (in a standardized format) and include the most relevant attributes. In addition, a reference to the Sebou River Basin Agency monitoring sites was included to compare the data with historical values and to provide new data to the agency.

The UMI team analyzed different geographic datasets such as: land use, elevation, road network and location of ABHS monitoring points to do a site selection analysis for both surface water and groundwater monitoring. Afterwards, the final monitoring sites were selected. For surface water a total of nine points were selected (rivers and springs) distributed among four catchments. Similarly, for groundwater quality monitoring, a total of 10 sites were selected, distributed inside the Saïss Plain Aquifer (Figure 39 and Figure 40).

Figure 39: Map of pilot area with indicated locations of the surface water quality monitoring and the relevant rivers (UMI and FiW, 2022)

Figure 40: Map of pilot area with indicated locations of the groundwater quality monitoring (source: UMI and FiW, 2022)Implementation of several campaigns (field work)

The UMI team has been working in the field conducting several monitoring campaigns for surface water and groundwater since July of 2022. The data of the monitoring campaigns for surface water in July, August and September 2022 is presented below.

Table 20: Measurements of selected Water Quality Parameters from 10 surface water sites in the pilot area inside the FMR in July 2022(Université Moulay Ismail, 2022)

July, 2022									
Monitoring points	pH	ORP* (mv)	Elec. Cond. ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	Resistivity ($\text{M}\Omega/\text{cm}$)	TDS (ppm)	Salinity (psu)	Turbidity (FNU)	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Atm (psi)
Beht 1	8.11	109	13,440	0.001	722	7.73	18.4	26.62	14.604
R'Dom 1	8.32	81.9	1,656	0.0006	828	0.83	16.8	26.87	14.549
R'Dom 2	8.4	74	1,513	0.0007	756	0.76	10.2	27.5	14.417
Ain Zouaoua	7.62	107.7	2,096	0.0005	1,048	1.07	16.7	21.34	14.371
Ain Maarouf	7.58	122.5	742	0.0013	371	0.36	0	18.83	13.71
Ain Atrous	7.52	136.7	666	0.0015	333	0.33	0.3	20.27	14.033
Ain Aghbal	7.59	124.5	725	0.0014	363	0.36	0	17.96	13.634
Barrage Sidi Chahed	8.72	72.8	3,265	0.0003	1,632	1.69	16.9	28.94	14.463
Oued Fes	8.13	97.7	945	0.0011	472	0.46	17.5	28.39	14.235

Table 21: Measurements of selected Water Quality Parameters from 10 surface water sites in the pilot area inside the FMR in August 2022 (Université Moulay Ismail, 2022)

August, 2022									
Monitoring points	pH	ORP* (mv)	Elec. Cond. ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	Resistivity ($\text{M}\Omega/\text{cm}$)	TDS (ppm)	Salinity (psu)	Turbidity (FNU)	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Atm (psi)
Beht 1	8.65	98.4	756	0.0013	383	0.38	0.3	20.36	13.627
R'Dom 1	8.72	76.8	1,404	0.0007	702	0.70	15.2	27	14.774
R'Dom 2	7.94	69.5	1,667	0.0006	833	0.84	12.1	25.73	14.355
Ain Zouaoua	8.12	98.2	2,094	0.0005	1,047	1.07	2	22.5	14.301
Ain Maarouf	7.85	105.5	690	0.0019	521	0.45	0.8	19.21	14.71
Ain Atrous	7.23	120.5	662	0.0015	331	0.32	3.4	22	13.937
Ain Aghbal	8.19	110.3	740	0.0014	370	0.36	0	21.92	13.574
Barrage Sidi Chahed	7.72	68.5	3,276	0.0003	1,638	1.7	11	27.52	14.412
Oued Fes	8.63	94.3	1,159	0.0009	580	0.57	15.9	24.54	14.148

*ORP: oxidation reduction potential, 20 m water column equals 28.5 psi.

Table 22: Measurements of selected Water Quality Parameters from 10 surface water sites in the pilot area inside the FMR in September 2022 (Université Moulay Ismail, 2022)

September, 2022									
Monitoring points	pH	ORP* (mv)	Elec. Cond. ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	Resistivity ($\text{M}\Omega/\text{cm}$)	TDS (ppm)	Salinity (psu)	Turbidity (FNU)	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Atm (psi)
Beht 1	8.02	112.6	7,839	0.0001	3,920	4.35	18.3	22	14.586
R'Dom 1	8.12	84.2	1,462	0.0006	800	0.81	1.7	20.45	14.531
R'Dom 2	8.06	71.3	1,521	0.0006	835	0.85	0	20.28	14.402
Ain Zouaoua	7.98	101.5	2,115	0.0004	1,113	1.14	2.4	22.39	14.332
Ain Maarouf	6.68	113.1	754	0.0013	377	0.37	0	19.79	13.657
Ain Atrous	7.39	116.3	681	0.0015	340	0.33	1.9	23.54	13.981
Ain Aghbal	7.87	98.7	733	0.0014	366	0.36	0	17.97	13.621
Barrage Sidi Chahed	7.93	73.4	3,294	0.0003	1,647	1.71	19.4	27.98	14.463
Oued Fes	8.43	89.5	1,247	0.0008	624	0.62	12.8	24.42	14.196

Table 23: Measurements of selected Water Quality Parameters from 10 surface water sites in the pilot area inside the FMR in October 2022 (Université Moulay Ismail, 2022)

October, 2022									
Monitoring points	pH	ORP* (mv)	Elec. Cond. ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	Resistivity ($\text{M}\Omega/\text{cm}$)	TDS (ppm)	Salinity (psu)	Turbidity (FNU)	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Atm (psi)
Beht 1	8.21	93.4	6,820	0.0014	1,394	3.75	15.5	21.45	14.56
R'Dom 1	7.43	76.5	1,614	0.0006	807	0.82	1.4	19.97	14.51
R'Dom 2	7.96	85.4	1,569	0.0006	787	0.79	2.3	19.48	14.38
Ain Zouaoua	7.58	96.8	2,207	0.0005	1,104	1.13	4.5	21.3	14.31
Ain Maarouf	7.23	118.5	750	0.0013	374	0.37	0	19.76	13.64
Ain Atrous	7.59	102.3	669	0.0005	334	0.33	1.5	22.81	13.98
Ain Aghbal	7.84	110.8	732	0.0014	366	0.36	0	17.94	13.59
Barrage Sidi Chahed	7.75	86.4	3,277	0.0003	1,640	1.71	12.5	24.84	14.47
Oued Fes	7.63	107.1	1,147	0.0009	573	0.57	19	22.7	14.2

Groundwater Monitoring

The groundwater and surface waters of the Fès-Meknès Region, play a decisive role in the socio-economic development of the region. They are an essential factor in the development of agricultural activities. Currently, the irrigated area is more than 45,000 ha. These resources are increasingly being sought as a source of drinking water, in the towns of Fès and Meknès and neighboring centers. This has led to a breakdown of the system's balance by drying out the sources, continuously decreasing groundwater levels and reducing surface water supplies.

Figure 41: Development of the groundwater table in the Saïss plain, measured at Forage 260/22 (UMI and FiW, 2022)

The development of the groundwater table in the Saïss plain shown in Figure 41 indicates that the piezometric level has dropped by more than 60 m starting in 1980/1981.

Similarly, groundwater monitoring campaigns have been conducted for the months of July, August, September and October 2022. Water samples were collected in the field and later analyzed in the water laboratory using the photometer; or direct measurements were carried out in the field using the multiparameter sensor. The data has been downloaded from the devices and saved in .csv and .xls files. The results for selected parameters collected each month are presented below.

Table 24: Measurements of selected Water Quality Parameters from groundwater points in the pilot area inside the FMR in July 2022 (Université Moulay Ismail, 2022)

July, 2022								
Point	T (°C)	pH	Cond (µS/cm)	TDS ppm	Turbidity (FNU)	Nitrate (mg/L)	Nitrite (mg/L)	Ammonia (mg/L)
S1	20.3	7.97	929.3	461	1.6	16	0.02	OR
S2	37.0	7.92	1,376	688	0	10	0.06	OR
S3	19.8	8.13	658	329	5	42	0.02	0.79
S4	22.0	7.80	848	424	19.2	37	0	0.81
S5	26.5	8.22	894	447	14.4	18	0.02	OR
S6	20.6	7.70	732	366	3.8	11	0.07	0.76
S7	26.2	7.40	690	345	3	49	0.04	0.42
S8	26.2	7.74	784	392	6.6	34	0.05	0.6
S9	25.3	7.74	1,066	533	17.9	40	0.16	0.93
S10	27.2	7.65	819	410	1.4	13	0.08	0.44

Table 25: Measurements of selected Water Quality Parameters from groundwater points in the pilot area inside the FMR in August 2022 (Université Moulay Ismail, 2022)

August, 2022								
Point	T (°C)	pH	Cond (µS/cm)	TDS ppm	Turbidity (FNU)	Nitrate (mg/L)	Nitrite (mg/L)	Ammonia (mg/L)
S1	25.3	7.79	863	428	4.5	49	0,01	OR
S2	24.6	7.94	1,020	513	0.1	39	0.01	OR
S3	36.2	7.76	1,436	714	0.3	21	0	1.05
S4	23.7	7.77	653	328	3.4	40	0	OR
S5	23.7	8.52	654	325	3.6	38	0.05	OR
S6	23.4	7.91	682	341	4.0	67	0.02	0.65
S7	22.8	7.43	710	355	0.9	58	0.04	OR
S8	25.3	7.47	768	384	3.1	57	0.06	1.05
S9	25.6	7.54	1,257	629	7.5	46	0	0.94
S10	28.4	7.67	804	402	2.3	30	0.01	OR

Table 26: Measurements of selected Water Quality Parameters from groundwater points in the pilot area inside the FMR in September 2022 (Université Moulay Ismail, 2022)

September, 2022								
Point	T (°C)	pH	Cond (µS/cm)	TDS ppm	Turbidity (FNU)	Nitrate (mg/L)	Nitrite (mg/L)	Ammonia (mg/L)
S1	20.5	7.83	850	465	1.4	52	0.08	OR
S2	25.8	8.04	1,392	696	0.1	37	0.18	OR
S3	24.6	8.25	749	374	2.2	OR	0.24	0.74
S4	29.5	7.92	1,022	511	3.3	45	0.09	0.95
S5	20.6	8.10	694	347	1.9	25	0.02	0.71
S6	22.6	7.41	689	345	5.3	15	0.01	0.76
S7	27.3	7.56	1,297	649	0.6	76	0.34	1.03
S8	32.6	7.68	760	380	10.3	47	0.16	0.89
S9	26.5	7.81	667	333	2.1	84	OR	1.02
S10	26.4	7.53	812	406	1.2	17	0.17	0.63

Table 27: Measurements of selected Water Quality Parameters from groundwater points in the pilot area inside the FMR in October 2022 (Université Moulay Ismail, 2022)

October, 2022								
Point	T (°C)	pH	Cond (µS/cm)	TDS ppm	Turbidity (FNU)	Nitrate (mg/L)	Nitrite (mg/L)	Ammonia (mg/L)
S1	20.3	7.71	927	465	0.3	56	0	OR
S2	24.2	7.65	1,391	695	2.2	30	0.06	OR
S3	22.1	8.10	1,199	599	1.2	OR	0.09	0.65
S4	25.8	7.75	875	437	12.2	60	0.02	1.04
S5	21.5	8.23	671	336	10.4	13	0	0.09
S6	24.4	7.71	2,280	1,143	7.7	6	0	0.83
S7	20.1	6.93	650	325	18.8	58	0.01	1.56
S8	28.8	6.84	1,147	574	19.5	46	0	0.73
S9	28.2	6.73	892	446	4.0	61	OR	0.52
S10	24.5	7.69	815	408	1.5	28	0.02	OR

Below a graphic for the parameter nitrate is presented, comparing the results for the period July-October 2022 to ABHS data from 2015. As a reference, the Nitrate levels in groundwaters in Europe should not exceed 50 mg/L.

Figure 42: Column diagrams of Nitrate concentrations of 10 groundwater locations measured between July and October 2022 compared with historic data from 2015 measured by ABHS (Université Moulay Ismail, 2022)

5.2.3 Development of a Tool for Integrated Water Resource Planning for the IWALAMAR study area

(J. Ramirez, M. Essahlaoui)

The WEAP (Water Evaluation and Planning) tool was developed by the FiW and UMI teams in close cooperation. After the project, the UMI team will continue to be responsible for further developments and applications. The objective for the WEAP model was to develop a tool to support decision makers in implementing Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) strategies, taking into account current conditions as well as trends and future climate scenarios. Due to the low data availability in the project region, the focus was on: a) developing a hydrological model using remote sensing products for climate and land use, and b) assessing the water demand in the region (agricultural, domestic and industrial).

WEAP is an Integrated Water Resource Planning System which allows the modeler to create a simulation of a water system with its various sources (e.g., rivers, streams, groundwater, reservoirs), water withdrawals and users, restrictions on use for environmental protection, sources of contamination and treatment plants. The program can simulate: surface runoff and infiltration, evapotranspiration, irrigation demand, surface water/groundwater interaction, and water quality. WEAP can be used in many ways, for example (Stockholm Environment Institute 2020):

- **Water balance database:** WEAP provides a system for maintaining water demand and supply information.
- **Scenario generation tool:** WEAP simulates water demand, supply, runoff, stream flows, storage, pollution generation, treatment and discharge and instream water quality.
- **Policy analysis tool:** WEAP evaluates a full range of water development and management options, and takes account of multiple and competing uses of water systems.

The IWALAMAR team has described the development steps and summarized main results in the *GUIDELINE "Integrated Water Resource Planning for the IWALAMAR study area - based on the WEAP – Water Resources Analysis and Forecast - Tool"* that is added as an annex to this draft final report. The guideline should be used as a guide for understanding how the model was built and which datasets were used. To obtain the data used, please contact A. Essahlaoui.

Figure 43: Groundwater element representing the deep aquifer and transmission links to domestic sites

One important component of the WEAP Model was the simulation of the deep aquifer of the Saïss basin, which covers an area of about 3500 km². The depth of the exploitation structures varies from 200 m in the south to 1700 m in the center of the plain. The aquifer is exploited by deep boreholes intended for the drinking water supply of the cities of Meknès, Fès and centers located in the plain (Ain Taoujtate, Ras El Ma, Sebaa Ayoune and Haj Kaddour).

5.3 Application of Olive Oil Processing Waste Separation and characterization of the separated products – Application in agriculture and valorization

(W. Kirchhof, E. Mathyl, J. Möller, S. Hruschka, D. Schmitz, M. Krauss)

Background

The Alpeorujo PolyPhenol extraction (Figure 49) process developed by GEA Westfalia Separator Group GmbH is installed at various Spanish Olive Mills. It is designed to separate olive paste in wet pomace and oily liquid. By a rotating sieve separator the crushed olive stones (~20 %) are separated from paste (80 %) that is led into a malaxer for homogenisation. Afterwards, an injection pump is used to pump the homogeneous paste from the malaxer into the decanter by which the olive pomace (~20 % dry matter) is separated in wet pastous heavy phase and light phase.

The main research objective to improve this process is the reduction of polyphenols in the pastous solid phase and enrichment of the polyphenols in the liquid phase.

The wet pomace might be used as organic by-product or fertilizer. The liquid might be used as raw material for organic antioxidants or antimicrobial additives because of the high polyphenol concentration.

Figure 44: Schematics of a 2-phase Olive oil extraction and an “AlpePepe” Alpeorujo Polyphenol extraction by GEA (GEA Westfalia Separator Group GmbH 2016)

Material and Methods

The IWALAMAR team aims to adapt the AlpePepe extraction to the Moroccan olive oil mills to concentrate the polyphenols in the liquid phase and to optimize the separation of polyphenols from the wet olive paste by modifying the acidity of the olive paste. Beside the analysis of total phenolic content in various residues, the composition of different polyphenols will be determined; tyrosol, hydroxytyrosol and oleuropein were selected as model substances. Applying a mass balance, the technical and economic potentials for the generation of new raw resources for antioxidants will be estimated. The potential of their removal and regain by adsorption and filtration methods will be discussed in chapter 5.4.

Remark: Instead of tests in Morocco, the tests were conducted in Spain in 2020 due to constraints related to imports of machinery to Morocco during the COVID-19 period.

The separation tests were done in the olive mill applying a 2-phase decanter type GEA RCC 450 (see feed pump (Figure 45) and decanter (Figure 46) that was specially modified to separate light (“liquid”) and solid phases from an olive paste.

Figure 45: Pneumatic feed pump for treated wet olive paste (FiW and GEA 2021)

Figure 46: 2-Phase Decanter for pomace separation into a thicker pomace phase and an oily water phase (Photos by FiW and GEA, 2021)

Fractions of wet olive paste were sieved by fine 2 mm-mesh sieve to remove coarse crushed stone. Subsequently the paste was homogenized and mixed in a malaxer. In this process unit, calcium hydroxide solution with a concentration of 2.0 mg/L was added to increase the pH-value up to 9 to 11 to increase the separation rate of polyphenolic compounds from the solid phase. The extraction trials were done in daily batches. The derived liquid and solids fractions

were analysed and weighed daily. Applying a beaker centrifuge, the oily water phase samples were separated into an oily phase and a water phase. All samples were analysed. The process schematic is shown in Figure 47. Daily samples were taken and conserved, polyphenol contents were determined and HPLC was used to determine the composition.

Figure 47: New advanced wastewater treatment process for olive paste/ mush separation (By FiW and GEA 2022)

From all samples, the humidity, dry matter, total phenolic content (Folin-Coicalteau as m(PP)/L or g(DM), respectively, as hydroxytyrosol equivalents (HTyE)) and antioxidant activities were analysed.

The reductive properties of polyphenolic antioxidants can be determined via the Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) method. Formation of molybdenum/tungsten blue corresponds to the amount of polyphenols. Nevertheless, also other reductive compounds can interfere. Hydroxytyrosol stem solution was prepared by dissolving 62.46 mg in 50 mL deionized water. Concentrations between 0 – 1,000 mg/L in 250 mg/L steps were prepared for calibration. Therefore, 25 μ L sample (calibration sample or residual sample (might be diluted)) were added to 1,800 μ L deionized water. 120 μ L Folin-Ciocalteu reagent were added. After 5 min, 340 μ L sodium carbonate ($c = 75$ g/L) were added. After incubation for 90 min at room temperature, extinction at 750 nm was measured.

Antioxidant activity was measured using the stable radical 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH). Also in this method, the reductive effect of polyphenols is used for their determination and the antioxidant activity (AA) is given in per cent upon reduction of the initial extinction of DPPH due to presence of its reduced species.

Heavy phase (“solid”) samples were weighed and dried to determine humidity and dry matter. A methanolic extract was prepared for polyphenol analysis. Light phases (“liquid”) were filtered. From both fractions (filtrate and filter cake), the phenolic content was determined (methanolic extract from dried filter cake, directly from filtrate). Polyphenol composition was analyzed by HPLC from selected centrifuged light phases.

Results:

From the conducted experiments, eight samples (divided in heavy and light phase, sample IV only heavy phase) were collected for above mentioned analyses; Figure 48 shows exemplary some of the provided samples.

Figure 48: Photos of pre-treated samples: Grignon (kernelfree pomace) (top left), heavy decanter phase (pomace) (top right), liquid decanter phase (Margine 3 LP) (bottom left), liquid decanter phase (Margine XII 2 LP) (bottom right) (By FHAC-IAP 2022)

Table 28 and Table 29 show the results of humidity, dry matter and phenolic content analyses.

Table 28: Dry matter (DM) and humidity of analysed samples (Schmitz, 2022)

Sample	Process pH	Pomace*	Dwelling time	DM(filtrate) [g/kg]	DM (filter cake) [g/kg]	DM (total) [g/kg]	Humidity / water content [%]	Total solids [%]
Grignot SP	(5.4)	A	-	-	235.06	235.06	76.49	23.51
Margine LP			-	193.53	447.96	641.49	35.85	64.15
III SP	8.5		average	-	269.52	269.52	73.05	26.95
III LP			average	42.39	179.25	221.64	77.84	22.16
IV SP	6.6	B	-	-	278.67	278.67	72.13	27.87
VI SP			average	-	319.97	319.97	68.00	32.00
VI LP	10.5 - 11	C	average	56.91	141.44	198.35	80.16	19.84
X SP			short	-	232.43	232.43	76.76	23.24
X LP	short		264.51	515.12	779.62	22.04 ⁺	77.96	
XI SP	9.8		long	-	268.25	268.25	73.17	26.83
XI LP		long	94.62	286.16	380.78	61.92	38.08	
XII SP	9.2	D	short	-	258.10	258.10	74.19	25.81
XII LP			short	104.46	408.53	512.99	48.70	51.30
XX LP	-	-	-	90.94	550.64	641.58	35.84 ⁺	64.16

*A: several days old; B: one-day old; C: mixture of A and B; D: fresh, same day.

⁺containing residual oil

Table 29: Process pH at separation, used pomace and corresponding TPC (/L or /kg, respectively) of the analyzed samples from Spain, distribution between light and heavy phase (Schmitz, 2022)

Sample	Process pH	Pomace*	Dwelling time	TPC (light phase/solution) [g(HTyE)/L]	TPC (heavy phase/filter cake) [g(HTyE)/L]	TPC (light phase/solution) [g(HTyE)/kg]	TPC (heavy phase/filter cake) [g(HTyE)/kg]	TPC (total) [g(HTyE)/kg]	Amount in light phase [%]	Amount in heavy phase [%]
Grignot SP	(5.4)	A	-	-	0.48	-	9.62	14.87	35.32	64.68
Margine LP			-	0.61	0.10	3.17	2.08			
III SP	8.5		average	-	0.14	-	2.70	41.49	93.49	6.51
III LP			average	1.58	0.71	37.37	1.42			
IV SP	-	-	-	0.11	-	2.24	2.24	-	-	
VI SP	6.6	B	average	-	0.12	-	2.38	46.46	94.88	5.12
VI LP			average	2.23	0.25	39.10	4.98			
X SP	10.5 - 11	C	short	-	0.22	-	4.32	25.30	82.93	17.07
X LP			short	3.45	0.40	13.04	7.94			
XI SP	9.8		long	-	0.10	-	1.96	53.87	96.36	3.64
XI LP			long	3.77	0.60	39.83	12.08			
XII SP	9.2	D	short	-	0.16	-	3.20	51.95	93.84	6.16
XII LP			short	3.97	0.54	38.03	10.72			
XX LP	-		-	3.64	0.32	46.48	-	46.48	-	-

*A: several days old; B: one-day old; C: mixture of A and B; D: fresh, same day.

Depending on applied process parameters for separation, amounts of dry matter in the various samples and phases, respectively, could be regulated. Also – most importantly – the amounts of (“active”) polyphenols (PP) could be varied. As well, the higher amount of PP in the light phase was shown (~83-95 % compared to ~65 % without pH-adjustment). Herein, they are mainly part of the dissolved dry matter, less found in residual filter cake. These parameters are dependent on the process parameters like pH or the freshness of the pomace/pulp. Also dwelling time of pH adjustment influenced the parameters.

Figure 49: DM in the light and heavy phases dependent on pH, dwelling time and pomace (left) and TPC and the amount of PP in light phase dependent on these parameters (right). (Schmitz, 2022)

Figure 50: Antioxidant activity (AA [%]) of the filtrate of the light phase (left) and of the methanolic extracts of heavy phase and filter cakes (right); indicated is the time until equilibrium was reached and the corresponding TPC. (Schmitz, 2022)

The results show the complexity of the residuals' composition, because a higher polyphenol content does not correspond directly with higher antioxidant activity. This can have several reasons. One is that, e.g., light phase samples were separated between suspended solids and aqueous/dissolved phase. Different polyphenol compositions can lead to different enrichment in those phases. For example, the extract of the filter cake of the light phases of samples XI and XII show higher TPC and AA than other samples, while their filtrate has a little lower AA. Also, different types of polyphenols can have different antioxidative properties, thus, affecting the AA values apart from just the TPC. HPLC measurements will give insight in phenolic compositions regarding the selected model polyphenols tyrosol, hydroxytyrosol and oleuropein. The light phase samples III, VIII, X, XI and XII were used for HPLC analysis, Figure 51 shows the results.

Figure 51: HPLC analyses of light phase samples III, VIII, X, XI and XII.

The results show big differences in amounts of selected phenolic compounds. As well, differences to the measured total phenolic contents were discovered (see Table 29). This is explained by the actual presence of more different types of phenolic compounds on the one hand. On the other hand, TPC measurements with Folin-Ciocalteu are also sensitive to other interfering components. Nevertheless, the results show amounts of some important polyphenols present in the samples. Furthermore, they correlate with process factors: old pomace material, low pH and short dwelling time generally lead to lower amounts of the searched substances. Lack of stabilization (potassium metabisulfite or pasteurization) decreases phenolic contents due to oxidation over time. Most important is use of fresh pomace to obtain phenol-enriched samples, as sample XII shows. Resulting phenol-enriched phase is a promising source for natural substances containing antioxidative and antimicrobial properties for food additives or used as oxidation protection and antimicrobial additive in materials.

5.4 Application of filtration and adsorption for the improvement of the applicability of treated residuals as fertilizer

(L. Messaoudi, M. Tijani, M Bennani, S. Allaoui)

For removal of polyphenols from olive mill wastewater (OMWW), adsorption and filtration techniques were elaborated and tested. For adsorption experiments, materials were used and modified on lab-scale and removal of polyphenols was tested by experimental set-up in glass column or via stirring materials in polyphenol-containing OMWW. For filtration experiments,

ceramic membranes were elaborated and tested. For this purpose, a pilot filtration device was developed and installed at UMI.

Figure 52: Pilot filtration device installed at UMI for the project I-WALAMAR.

5.4.1 Pollutant removal trials applying an experimental filtration system with flat ceramic membranes

Two zeolithes (Sodalite and Faujasite) were deposited on ceramic support by hydrothermal method to tune the mesopores of clay support that are prepared from a widely available clay depot from the central region of Morocco (Midelt). Different granulometries were sieved and used for ceramic support preparation: $\Phi \leq 63 \mu\text{m}$; $63 \mu\text{m} \leq \Phi \leq 160 \mu\text{m}$ and $160 \mu\text{m} \leq \Phi \leq 250 \mu\text{m}$. Additionally, ceramic support was modified with the cyclic glucose oligomer β -cyclodextrin (β CD, see also chapter 5.4.3) for polyphenol adsorption.

Ceramic support synthesis

A sample of 3.88 g of the clay ($160 \mu\text{m} \leq \Phi \leq 250 \mu\text{m}$) powder is thoroughly mixed manually with 0.12 g of activated carbon (3 % w/w of the clay powder mass) for a period of 10 min. Afterwards, the mixture is inserted into a stainless die and uniaxially pressed under a pressure of 10 tons load (780.8 bar) to obtain raw pellets (flat discs) of 4.0 cm in diameter and 2.0 mm in thickness. The obtained discs are sintered at 1000 °C in a muffle furnace following a suitable heating program.

Membrane preparation

Sodalite membrane (SOM): Aluminate precursor (mixture of 0.075 mol NaOH, 7.15×10^{-4} mol NaAlO_2 and 0.277 mol H_2O) and silicate precursor (mixture of 0.027 mol Na_2SiO_3 and 0.389 mol H_2O) were stirred for 24 hours at room temperature. The aluminate precursor is added to the silicate precursor dropwise during stirring for 10 min. The ceramic support is placed in the mixture. Afterwards, the flask is placed in the oven at $T = 80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 hours. The precipitate

is filtered and washed several times with deionized water until a pH = 10. The obtained solid is dried overnight at 80 °C.

Faujasite membrane (FAM): A germination gel is prepared by mixing 0.0255 mole of NaOH, 5.328×10^{-3} mol of NaAlO₂ in 0.277 mol H₂O; 0.02 mol of Na₂SiO₃. The resulting mixture is sealed in a polypropylene container and is left to mature for 24 hours at room temperature and under vigorous stirring. The growth gel is prepared by dissolving 8.75×10^{-4} mol NaOH and 0.033 mol of NaAlO₂ in 1.82 mol H₂O; afterwards, 0.125 mol Na₂SiO₃ is added. The gel is kept to mature for 2 h. The germination gel is added under vigorous stirring to the growth gel. The ceramic support is placed in the mixture, which is placed in the oven at 80 °C for 24 hours in a sealed polypropylene container. The obtained solid is filtered and washed several times with deionized water until pH = 10. The solid is dried overnight in the oven at 80 °C.

Deposited βCD on ceramic support: To a mixture of 12.0 g βCD mixed with 4.8 ml of water, 14.4 mL of 12.5 molar NaOH were added. The ceramic support was put in this mixture, while under vigorous stirring 8.2 mL epichlorohydrin (Ep) were added slowly. The mixture was stirred until formation of a gel. The flat membrane was cleaned from residual material, washed thoroughly with methanol and water and dried at 50 °C. The residue of polymer was used for adsorption experiments (see chapter 5.4.3).

Filtration tests

Filtration tests were carried out in the above mentioned pilot device suitable for tubular and flat membranes. The dye methyl orange (MO), phenol, a bacterial containing medium and OMWW were tested regarding retention after filtration with the different membranes.

Conclusions

The filtration method on the clay membranes based on Zeolithes Faujasite and Sodalite as well as βCD-containing polymer modified membranes can be used as an alternative ecological method to remove dyes, other toxic chemicals and polyphenols from wastewater. As well filtration of microorganisms could be shown.

Figure 53: Results of membrane filtration tests of removal of methyl orange (MO) with prepared membranes (a-d)), removal of microorganisms from water with prepared membranes (e)) and removal of polyphenols from OMWW using hydrotalcite- and βCD-modified support, respectively(f)).

5.4.2 Fabrication of mineral tubular membranes from local clays of the Fés-Meknés Region (FMR), Morocco

Introduction

Mineral membranes have undergone spectacular development since the 1980s. Thanks to their high mechanical and chemical stability and their long-life span, they have replaced organic membranes. These membranes are now well established, replacing conventional separation techniques in economic sectors such as food processing, biotechnology, the chemical industry and wastewater treatment. These membranes are known for their reliability and profitability, due to their specific advantages guaranteeing a long range of application and allowing them to be used under extremely severe conditions.

The main objective of this purely experimental research work is to elaborate and characterize new ceramic membranes of tubular geometry by extrusion and their use in permeability tests and in the removal of dyes, by tangential filtration using a membrane pilot. The choice of clay as raw material for the manufacture of membranes is due to its availability in nature in large quantities and its mechanical and plastic behavior in the form of ceramic pastes.

This research work is of great importance because it is about starting from a less expensive raw material of local origin (clay), from which we manufacture tubular membranes that will then be used, after cooking and characterization, for the elimination of the dyes.

The first part of this work is devoted to the characterization of the raw material (clay) by various methods and techniques of analysis (X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), infrared spectroscopy (IR) and thermal properties (DTA/TGA).

The second part corresponds to the development of the membranes by extrusion of the plastic pastes prepared from the clay powders. Organic products are added to the starting powder to improve the porosity by their degradation during the thermal treatment without affecting the mechanical properties of the membranes. Analysis is done regarding mechanical and chemical resistance. Porosity and morphology using Scanning-Electron-Microscopy (SEM) are tested as well.

The third part is devoted to permeation tests and filtration of a dye (methyl orange (MO)).

Process step 1: Characterization of the raw material

The clay used in this work is taken from a site in the region of Meknès.

The preparation of the powder to be used in this work involves several steps: Crushing, grinding and sieving to obtain different granulometries, as shown in the following figure:

Figure 54: Preparation of the powder (By UMI Messaoudi, 2022)

Before using the powder for the elaboration of the membranes, it is necessary to characterize it by various experimental techniques as described above.

X-Ray fluorescence:

The X-ray fluorescence study shows that this clay is mainly composed of SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and CaO. The presence of 5 % of iron oxide in the powder explains the red color of the membranes after heat treatment.

Table 30: Results of the fluorescence measurements (UMI Tijani, 2022)

Oxyde	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	Fe ₂ O ₃	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O
%	46.2	15.6	10.5	3.06	5.12	1.79	1.13

The X-ray spectrum of this clay confirms the results of the X-ray fluorescence by the presence of quartz and kaolinite.

Figure 55: XRD diffractogram of raw clay (UMI Messaoudi, 2022)

Infra red spectroscopy:

Figure 56: FTIR spectrum of raw clay (UMI Messaoudi, 2022)

Thermal study DTA/TGA

The thermal study revealed a continuous mass loss by the presence of five endothermic peaks corresponding:

- to the evaporation of free and interfoliar water molecules from 85 °C,
- to the degradation of the organic matter at 250 °C,
- the departure of the water constituting the kaolinite at 573 °C
- the departure of CO₂ following the decarbonation of calcite: $\text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$

Figure 57: DTA/TGA of the starting powder (UMI Messaoudi, 2022)

Process step 2: Preparation of the membranes

The protocol followed in this case is the following: Once the powder is characterized, it is used to prepare pastes designed for the elaboration of membranes. To the starting powder, a percentage of organic product is added, which in our case is wood. The organic material allows to improve the porosity after its degradation during the thermal treatment. A dry mixing is carried out to have a homogeneous mixture and we add water to have a paste by mixing. The obtained paste is put into a plastic bag closed hermetically and then placed in the refrigerator for a certain time, called “time of ageing”. The paste is then extruded by a laboratory extruder to obtain tubular membranes (Figure 65, Figure 66).

Figure 58: Schematic of preparation of the paste from the powder (UMI Messaoudi, 2022)

Figure 59: Membranes before baking (a) and after baking (b) at 800, 900 and 1000 °C (15 % MO) (Photo by UMI Messaoudi, 2022)

Characterization of the membranes

Mechanical resistance, porosity and chemical resistance:

We note that the optimum porosity and mechanical strength is obtained for 12 % of organic product. The mechanical resistance is obtained by using an apparatus (ENSAM, Meknès) that indicates the bending resistance (method of three points), see Figure 60 below.

Figure 60: System for determining bending strength at ENSAM, Meknés (Photo by UMI Messaoudi, 2022)

Water porosity is determined by emerging membrane samples of known mass and volume into test tubes containing water. The amount of water absorbed per volume difference can then be determined and thus the total pore volume can be determined.

The chemical resistance is determined by immersing membrane samples in acidic and basic solutions at different concentrations and the evolution of the mass loss can be followed over a period of up to several days. If the mass loss does not exceed 4 %, we can say that our membrane is chemically resistant and can be used in industrial wastewater filtration operations.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

To ensure that our membranes do not contain defects (cracks), we must use scanning electron microscopy which allows us to see the micrograph, the general aspect and the diameter of the pores (Figure 61).

Figure 61: Two Micrographs of a membrane treated at 1000 °C with 15 % MO (UMI Messaoudi, 2022) Process step 3: Permeation tests and dye treatment

Permeation tests

Before using each membrane in a treatment operation, permeation tests must first be performed with tap water to ensure its purifying power.

For this purpose, the membranes are mounted in a crossflow filtration pilot, and the water is circulated in a closed circuit by means of an electric circulation pump. The water crosses the membrane tangentially and when the pressure starts to increase, the water exits through the porosity of the membrane and the filtrate is recovered in a graduated cylinder which allows us to calculate the flow as a function of time and pressure.

The water circulates in a closed circuit by using a pump whose pressure varies between 1 and 6 bar. This study is done by recovering the volume of water that crosses the membrane in a test tube by determining the time for each working pressure. The aim is to study the flow of the permeate as a function of time and pressure. Some curves of flow versus time and pressure for permeation tests are shown below.

Figure 62: Flux versus time and flux versus pressure. Water permeability: 5 %. Membrane baked at 1,000 °C (UMI Messaoudi, 2022)

Filtration tests of Methyl Orange (MO) dye:

Figure 63: Variation of the methyl orange flow rate as a function of time for membranes fired at different temperatures (P = 3 bar and 15 % MO) (UMI Messaoudi, 2022)

It can be seen that the flux starts to decrease until a stabilization corresponding to the stationary regime with the formation of a polarization layer. We are able to retain the MO dye completely through our membranes.

Conclusions

In this research work carried out within the framework of the WALAMAR project, we have developed tubular membranes based on a clay from the Meknès region. The clay powder obtained after crushing and sieving was characterized by several experimental techniques to understand its behavior according to the thermal treatment. This powder is used for the manufacture of tubular membranes of high mechanical, chemical and purifying performance.

A study of the permeability of these membranes was carried out by following the evolution of the permeation fluxes as a function of time and transmembrane pressure.

The application part of this work corresponds to the filtration of a dye (Methyl Orange), in which we obtained good results, because we were able to totally eliminate this dye with different membranes.

5.4.3 Adsorption of polyphenolic compounds on β -cyclodextrin (β CD) - modified materials (polymer and modified natural material)

(D. Schmitz, N. Ittobane, M. Bennani, M. Biel, S. Allaoui)

The problem and potential of polyphenols were already described in this report. Filtration methods mentioned before are also an option for water treatment for polyphenol removal. Beside membrane filtration, adsorption of polyphenols on modified materials was evaluated, which will be described in this chapter.

As binding group for the uptake of phenolic compounds, cyclodextrins were selected. Based on this, a crosslinked polymer and the correspondingly modified natural material Ghassoul clay from Morocco, were synthesized, characterized and evaluated regarding polyphenol adsorption. Cyclodextrins are cyclic oligomers of glucose. They form a cone-like structure with a hydrophilic exterior and hydrophobic interior, which provides a cavity for uptake of organic compounds like polyphenols. The cavity size varies depending on number of glucose units in the cyclic oligomer (native cyclodextrins between six to eight). For uptake of aromatics, like phenolic compounds, six units are reported to be most suitable, which is namely β -cyclodextrin (β CD).

The general procedure for this work was 1) analysis of β CD-complexes, 2) synthesis and characterization of β CD-containing materials and 3) uptake studies with polyphenols from olive wastewater.

Analysis of β CD complexes

For analysis, the selected polyphenols Ty, HTy and Ole were used for NMR-titration with α -, β - and γ -cyclodextrin. In a general procedure, cyclodextrin and polyphenol were mixed in different ratios maintaining the same total concentration in the sample solution. In proton NMR measurements, complex induced shifts (CIS) of the corresponding signal of protons taking part in complexation can be observed depending on the ratio. As well, a two-dimensional NMR study of HTy-complexes was carried out. The most important results of the NMR measurements are summarized in Figure 64.

Figure 64: Data of $^1\text{H-NMR}$ measurements: a) and b), NMR-spectra of single substances (CDs and PPs); results of NMR-titration: c) aromatic protons of selected PPs in presence βCD , d) CIS of CD-protons in

presence of HTy, e) Job's plot of Ty, HTy and Ole with β CD and f) ROESY-spectrum of 1:1 ratio β CD:HTy complex.

The results show a strong interaction between the aromatic protons of the selected polyphenols and interacting protons of β -cyclodextrin. The fitted Job-plot with a maximum at 0.5 (1:1 ratio) indicates 1:1 complexes between polyphenols and β -cyclodextrin. Further synthesis and modification of materials will be carried out using β CD to provide anchoring groups with the aim to improve the binding properties for polyphenolic compounds. The highest affinity is found in β CD-Ole complexes, which is indicated by bigger CIS.

Synthesis of β CD-containing materials

The general procedure was the crosslinking of β CD with the compound epichlorohydrin (EP) in basic aqueous medium – in presence of Ghassoul clay or ground olive stone, respectively. This results in β CD-containing crosslinked polymer or corresponding composite with the above-mentioned natural materials.

Figure 65: Schematic overview of synthesis of β CD-containing materials.

Uptake studies with polyphenols from olive wastewater

Uptake studies were carried out via mixing powdered materials with polyphenol containing medium (olive wastewater) for kinetic characterization and via column filtration. Removal of polyphenols was monitored using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent to determine the total phenolic content. Samples before and after column filtration were furthermore analyzed by HPLC measurements.

Kinetic measurements

The adsorption experiments were carried out in flasks. The procedure consists of adding 100 mg of each material to 20 mL volume of olive wastewater with 0.31 g (GAE)/L at 25 °C, 35 °C and 45 °C, respectively. Magnetic stirring is carried out for contact times of 30 min up to 420 min without pH adjustment. The mixture was centrifuged and the supernatant was passed through a 0.45 μ m filter and prepared for Folin-Ciocalteu measurements.

The determination of the quantity of adsorbed pollutants as a function of time was calculated using the following equation:

$$q_t = \frac{c_o - c_t}{m} \times V$$

q_t = absorbed amount of PPs at time t $\left[\frac{mg}{g}\right]$; c_o = initial PP concentration $\left[\frac{mg}{L}\right]$;

c_t = residual PP concentration in solution at time t $\left[\frac{mg}{L}\right]$; V = volume of solution [L]

The results are shown in Figure 66

Figure 66: Kinetic adsorption experiments of OMWW at 25 and 35 °C and adsorbed amounts of polyphenols in equilibrium.

The results show a decrease of adsorption at elevated temperature indicating exothermic adsorption process for all tested materials. Furthermore, the modification with βCD could increase the amount of adsorbed PPs. At 45 °C no significant difference between the materials can be observed.

Adsorption on column

For adsorption experiments, glass columns with 1.0 cm in diameter and 14 cm in height were used. The columns were filled with 7.0 g of corresponding material and afterwards fed with 20 mL of olive mill wastewater in different initial concentrations of polyphenols: 200, 400 and 550 mg/L (GAE) polyphenols. The experiments were carried out at room temperature. After complete filtration of the volume, the final concentration was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. Figure 67 summarizes the results.

Figure 67: Adsorption/removal on column of polyphenols from olive mill wastewater with different materials at different initial concentrations.

All materials lead to reduction of polyphenol concentration as determined via Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. Because Folin-Ciocalteu method only gives the general reduction of phenolic compounds and also is sensitive to other interfering substances, HPLC-measurements were carried out. This gives further information regarding the composition of the three selected polyphenols Ty, HTy and Ole.

Figure 68: HPLC analyses of OMWW before and after adsorption on different materials.

Among the used model polyphenols, HTy has the highest amount in the untreated wastewater followed by Ole and Ty. After treatment, the amount of the phenolic compounds decreases with usage of all samples. Only after adsorption on Ghassoul and β CD-modified olive stone, relevant amounts of polyphenols were found. Here, in comparison to Ole, the compounds Ty and HTy are more preferably removed from OMWW. This is in contrast to the results from complexation experiments, in which a higher affinity of Ole was found compared to HTy and Ty. Nevertheless, during the polymer and composite syntheses, β CD is modified by chemical reaction, which can change the complexation properties. Polymer and polymer-modified Ghassoul as well as a Ghassoul-polymer mixture showed the best results in adsorption of the selected polyphenols.

5.5 Agricultural Weather Monitoring Station for the Improvement of the Forecasting Options in the Agricultural Sector in the FMR

(F. Grimmeisen, A. Abouabdillah)

The I-WALAMAR group intends to upgrade the existing meteorological monitoring and communication system to increase the up-to-date distribution of weather parameters to the farmer communities in the study area. Therefore, SEBA developed an agro-meteorological station as shown on Figure 69 on the premises of ENA. Parameters which are recorded are

- Wind direction and wind speed
- Atmospheric pressure, air temperature, air humidity and solar radiation
- Precipitation
- Soil moisture and soil temperature at depths of 10 cm, 20 cm and 30 cm
- The data is being transferred via GPRS modem and available through the browser-based online module SEBA Hydrocenter (www.seba-hydrocenter.de; Figure 69)

Furthermore, SEBA provided a second reference station which records meteorological parameters such as wind direction, wind speed, atmospheric pressure, air temperature, air humidity, solar radiation, and precipitation with precision approved by WMO.

Figure 69: Photos of the SEBA Meteorological Station for Agricultural Climate Monitoring, source: Grimmeisen (2022); left and middle: SEBA Rain station including rain gauge, MultiMet-sensor, data logger, battery and solar power module, right: Soil humidity sensor for measurements at depths. 10 cm, 20 cm and 30 cm

Figure 70: Online Monitoring results of the SEBA Meteorological Station for Agricultural Climate Monitoring at ENA, source: Grimmeisen (2022)

Figure 71: Photos of the solar-powered SEBA Meteorological Station for reference at near ENA , source: Grimmeisen (2022); SEBA station including a tipping bucket rain gauge, wind speed and wind direction sensors, air humidity sensor, air pressure sensor, and solar radiation sensor.

5.6 Application of Anaerobic (Biogas) Treatment of Olive Oil Processing Waste and Wastewater for the Assessment of the Applicability of Olive Pomace Waste (OPW) as Biogas Feed Material

(K. Spohrer, Leandro, M., F. El Hafiane, M. Hafidi)

5.6.1. Batch test

5.6.1.1. Olive oil production pathways

Olive oil production generates a huge volume of by-products both in solid (press cake) and liquid (margin and wash water) forms. The olive mill solid waste obtained from the two-phase olive oil extraction system (*alperujo*) is the main by-product generated, accounting for up to 80 % of the initial olive mass (Fernández-Prior et al. 2020).

5.6.1.2. Characterization

The physicochemical characterization (Table 31 and Figure 72) of the olive oil by-products was determined following standard methods and protocols (DIN EN 14775; DIN EN 12880; DIN EN 12879).

Table 31: Characteristics of the pomace, margine and wash water

Parameter	Dry pomace	Margine	Wash water
TS (% FM)	97.7	---	---
VS (% TS)	91.3	---	---
Glucose (g/kg)	12.5	---	---
Lactic acid (g/kg)	---	0.75	---
COD (g/L)	---	30.9	9.8
N [%]	---	0.015	n.d.
C [%]	---	1.185	0.386

Figure 72: Analysis of dry pomace

The elemental analysis of the dry pomace, margine and wash water is shown in Table 32. Some values of the dry pomace, especially iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), and Zinc (Zn) indicate deficiencies if the substrate is considered for mono-fermentation (Chala et al. 2018).

Table 32: Elemental analysis of olive waste (values in mg/kg of fresh mass)

Sample	Na 23	Mg 26	Al 27	P 31	K 39	Ca 42	Mn 55	Fe 56	Ni 60	Cu 63	Zn 66	S 48
Dry pomace	752	1,323	344	2,908	25,388	6,669	15	826	4	14	21	1,663
Wash water	250	81	2	96	1,620	370	1	35	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	220
Margine	269	95	4	174	2,220	287	1	19	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	231

5.6.1.3. Methane yield

The methane and biogas yield were determined following the Hohenheim biogas yield test (HBT) protocol (Patent No. 10227685, 20.01.2005); a laboratory batch method, according to the Guideline VDI 4630. The fermentation temperature was 37 ± 0.5 °C for a period of 35 days. Subsequent to the volume measurement, the methane content was measured manually in

Vol %, using an infrared-spectrometric methane-sensor “Advanced Gasmitter” (Pronova Analysetechnik, Berlin, Germany). The measured methane and biogas volume had to be corrected to standard conditions (273 K, 1013 hPa) (Mittweg et al. 2012).

Figure 73: The specific methane yield from dry pomace, margine and water in fresh mass (a), VS and COD bases (b)

The highest specific methane yield was obtained from pomace (178.6 L per kg fresh mass added) followed by margine and wash water (6.4 and 2.4 respectively) (Figure 73). The yield from margine and wash water was very low compared to that of dry pomace. The SMY from the common substrates, maize silage and grass silage (first cut) was 91 and 93 L kg⁻¹ FM.

5.6.2. Continuously stirred tank reactor (CSTR) trials

Anaerobic batch tests cannot provide information on process stability and performance, mono-fermentability and limits of the organic loading rates (OLR) per unit volume. Thus, continuous fermentation procedures should be employed to address these limitations.

5.6.2.1. Digester

The digester was a vertical cylinder constructed from stainless steel. The total and active volume of the digester was 700 L and 560 L, respectively (Figure 74). Further information of the digester characteristics can be provided upon request.

Figure 74: Pilot scale digester, the biogas is collected in a gas bag connected to the digester (a) feeding digester with wet pomace (b).

Figure 75 shows the power consumption of the digester in 24-hour duration to maintain the temperature at about 37 °C while the ambient temperature is way lower than 15 °C.

Figure 75: The daily active power (by the stirrer motor and the heat mats) to maintain the digester at about 37 °C against the ambient temperature (08 Jan, 2021).

5.6.2.2. Inoculum and substrate

The inoculum was collected from active biogas digesters found in Unterer Lindenhof (Eningen, Germany), which is owned by the University of Hohenheim. The digesters were fed in different proportions with liquid manure, solid manure, maize silage, grass silage, wheat/grain, horse manure and sugar beet. A more detailed description of the transfer of the inoculum into the digester can be provided upon request. The olive pomace substrate was obtained from Spain and shipped to Hohenheim in a single container and stored in a freezer room (< -20 °C) until further use. The pomace was supplied with the crushed seed.

The sample was characterized (proximate and ultimate analysis) prior to feeding to the digester (Table 33). The OLR was planned to be 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 kg_{VS} m⁻³ d⁻¹ with the fresh pomace (without stone). Therefore, the seed stone was separated by adding water, settling and sieving. The liquid fraction of the pomace exhibits a dry matter and organic dry matter content of 7 % and 92 %, respectively.

Table 33: Characterization of the fresh pomace, the liquid and solid fraction of pomace and inoculum used.

Sample	DM (%FM)	oDM (%DM)	ADF (%DM)	ADL (%DM)	NDF (%DM)	RF (%DM)
Fresh pomace	30.6	95.6	60.1	36.4	69.7	53.2
Seed stone fraction	63.8	99.4	-	-	-	-
Liquid fraction	5.8	91.9	-	-	-	-
Inoculum	5.0	69.9	-	-	-	-

5.6.2.3. Start-up

After adaptation phase, the digester was started being fed with the pomace at OLR 1.5 kg_{VS} m⁻³ d⁻¹. The biogas was measured on daily basis using drum-type gas flow meter (TG 5/5, RITTER Apparatebau GmbH & Co. KG, Bochum, Germany). The composition of the biogas was determined with gas analyser (Sensors Europe AGM Plus 1010) which detects CH₄ and CO₂ inside a gaseous medium. The ambient temperature and pressure in the testing area were measured with a datalogger (Votcraft DL-220 THP, VOLTCRAFT – Conrad Electronic AG, Wollerau, Switzerland). The biogas temperature inside the gas flow meter was measured also with a data logger (Votcraft DL111K, – Conrad Electronic AG, Wollerau, Switzerland).

5.6.2.4. Gas yield

The experiment was run for 148 days in a row after months of pre-test. For the first 50 days the average specific methane yield (SMY) from olive pomace (without stone) was more than 395 L kg_{VS} while feeding at OLR of 1.0 kg_{VS} m⁻³ d⁻¹. The composition of methane in the biogas was 60 % - 65 %, which is common in substrates rich in fats/oils (VDI 4630). However, in the subsequent days of experiment the SMY declined steadily to the completion of the experiment.

In the same way, the methane composition of the biogas was declined from peak value 72 % to 32 % (Figure 76). A specific reason could not be mentioned for the decline of SMY and methane content. However, different measures were taken to rectify the problem. There were times where the daily loading was terminated, OLR decreased, trace elements added (specially Fe based).

Figure 76: The specific methane yield of olive pomace with different OLR (left), and the daily specific methane yield of pomae and the composition of methane in the biogas (V/V) (right).

5.6.2.5. Digester stability

The total and individual volatile fatty acids (acetic, propionic, butyric, and valeric acid), and concentration of the sample from a digester indicate the stability and early warning of the anaerobic process imbalance. Basically, these short-chained fatty acids are intermediate metabolites in the anaerobic digestion process that are produced during the acidogenesis step and are precursors of methane. Accumulation of these acids indicates the methanation is inhibited. The recommended concentration for the total volatile fatty acids (VFA) and individual VFAs is $<1000 \text{ HAc mg L}^{-1}$ for each parameter; however, the propionic acid of more than 250 may indicate unstable anaerobic processes (Chala et al. 2018; Drosig 2013).

There was no organic acid accumulation in the first 8 weeks. However, in the subsequent 3 weeks the organic acid contents steadily increased until the substrate loading rate temporarily stopped for about a week. When the substrate loading commenced with increased OLR, the concentration of the organic acids once again started to increase. Interruption of the substrate loading caused a decline in acid concentration; however, it couldn't continue with this pattern for the rest of the experiment period. Hence, the concentrations of the VFA, acetic and propionic acids remained high beyond the recommended limits for stable anaerobic fermentation processes (Figure 77).

Figure 77: Organic acid concentration in the digester with different organic loading rates (OLR) (left), and FOS/TAC ratio of digester with different OLRs (right).

The alkalinity ratio, a ratio of VFA to the total inorganic carbon (TIC), [which is also known as FOS/TAC ratio in German literature] provides information on the stability of the fermentation process and a ratio below 0.3 is recommended for a stable anaerobic fermentation (Voß et al.; Lossie and Pütz 2008). The digester was stable in the first nine weeks of fermentation. However, the alkalinity ratio increased with the increasing of OLR from 1.0 to 1.5 kg_{VS} m⁻³ d⁻¹, and eventually reached above 1.8 which is way more than the recommended figure (Figure 77).

5.6.2.6. Phenolic compounds

Phenolics can inhibit the degradation of readily biodegradable organic fractions and their own biodegradation (Hernandez and Edyvean 2008). The TPC in the digester (Figure 78) shows a decreasing trend during the fermentation period. The fresh pomace (without stone) exhibited higher TPC content than the samples taken on different days from the digester. Also, some of the phenolic compounds were decomposed in the fermentation processes. On the other hand, the analysis of the individual phenolic compounds shows that most of the phenolic compounds remains similar during the whole fermentation processes (Figure 78). It seems that the increase in the concentration of the sinapic acid might be one of the causes for the decline of the methane formation in the digester.

Figure 78: The total phenolic content (left) and individual phenolic compound contents (right) of digestates and fresh pomace (without stone).

5.6.2.7. Trace metals

Essentially, the concentrations of Fe and Mn just reached the minimum requirements for the respective trace elements in the third quarter of the experiment session (Figure 79). The decline in the concentration of trace metals can cause stability and performance issues in digesters. Therefore, one of the reasons for the decline of the biogas formation might be the deficiency of trace metals in the substrate itself. Thus, co-fermentation with other substrates, especially animal manure, or the supplementation of a cocktail of trace metals can address the problem caused by the trace elements deficiency (Chala et al. 2018).

Figure 79: Concentrations of some trace metals in the digester. The samples were taken from the digester at different dates, the horizontal broken lines show the recommended minimum concentration for a stable biogas digester.

5.6.3. Enhancing Biogas Production and Methane content through Anaerobic Digestion of Horse Manure and Co-Digestion of Margines

This study investigates the anaerobic digestion of horse manure and the co-digestion of margines to valorize organic waste for energy production. The research focuses on biogas production, methane content, and pH stability as key performance indicators. Horse manure exhibited a high biogas yield of 315 L/kg VS and a methane content of 73 %. In comparison, the co-digestion of margines yielded 120 L/kg VS of biogas with a methane content of 80 %. The initial acidic pH levels of 5.2 for horse manure and 4.6 for margines were observed to stabilize at 7.2 and 7.8, respectively, indicating favorable conditions for anaerobic digestion. The study highlights the potential for utilizing horse manure and margines as valuable substrates for biogas production and emphasizes the importance of addressing inhibitory compounds in margines to enhance performance. Optimization strategies, including pretreatment techniques and adjustment of process parameters, are recommended to improve the co-digestion process. These findings contribute to sustainable waste management and renewable energy generation.

The anaerobic digestion of olive mill wastewater and horse manure is an effective and sustainable method for treating these organic wastes while generating renewable energy. Anaerobic digestion is a biological process in which microorganisms break down organic matter in the absence of oxygen, producing methane-rich biogas and residual by-products such as digestate.

While anaerobic digestion of olive mill wastewater, known as "margines," offers undeniable advantages in terms of waste reduction and energy valorization, it also presents certain limitations. Margines are rich in phenolic compounds, volatile fatty acids, and fats, which can inhibit the activity of anaerobic microorganisms and reduce the efficiency of digestion. Moreover, the high solids and fat content can lead to issues such as system clogging in anaerobic digestion processes.

Regarding horse manure, although it contains a significant amount of potentially digestible organic matter, it can be challenging to digest due to its low nutrient content and fibrous composition. This can result in relatively low biogas production rates and extended hydraulic retention times.

To enhance the anaerobic digestion of margines and horse manure and achieve remarkable results, several possible solutions exist. Here are a few:

- Pretreatment of margines: Pretreatment techniques such as centrifugation, filtration, or enzyme addition can help remove inhibitory compounds and improve the digestibility of margines.
- Co-digestion with other substrates: Adding nutrient-rich co-substrates such as food waste or sewage sludge can stimulate anaerobic digestion by providing a balanced nutrient source for microorganisms.
- Control of digestion conditions: Adjusting pH, temperature, and the C/N ratio in digestion reactors can promote microbial activity and optimize biogas production.
- Use of specialized methanogenic bacteria: Identifying and utilizing specific methanogenic bacteria capable of degrading the challenging-to-digest compounds present in margines and horse manure can enhance anaerobic digestion efficiency.

Objective

The objective of this study is to valorize margines for both energetic and agronomic purposes and to determine the optimal mixture for maximum energy production. The next phase of this research will employ the method of experimental design to identify the significant factors that affect anaerobic co-digestion. It aims to determine the optimal value of each factor and explore the synergistic effects among them. Subsequently, a mixing experimental design will be employed to find the necessary proportions required to achieve high methane yield.

By utilizing a combination of anaerobic co-digestion and experimental design methodologies, this research seeks to optimize the energy generation potential of margins while also exploring the potential agronomic benefits. Through careful analysis and experimentation, we aim to identify the key factors that influence the co-digestion process and determine their ideal values. Moreover, we will investigate the interactions and synergies between these factors to unlock the maximum energy production potential.

This study not only aims to address the environmental challenges posed by margins but also seeks to provide valuable insights for sustainable waste management and resource recovery. By optimizing the anaerobic co-digestion process, we can enhance the overall efficiency and effectiveness of converting organic waste into renewable energy and valuable by-products for agricultural applications.

Methods and Materials

I. Sample Collection and Preparation:

- **Margins Collection:** Margins samples were obtained from Oleafood, a reputable olive mill. Standardized sampling techniques were employed to ensure representative and varied samples.
- **Horse Manure Collection:** Horse manure samples were collected from the Institute of Agronomy and Veterinary Hassan II. The facility is known for its high-quality horse manure.
- **Substrate Analysis:** Both margins and horse manure samples were analyzed to determine their moisture content (MC), volatile solids (VS), total solids (TS), organic matter (OM), pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total carbon (TC), and total nitrogen (TN). The analysis was conducted following AFNOR (Rodier) methods for margins and the standardized method for solid substrate characterization for horse manure.

II. Anaerobic Digesters:

- **Experimental Setup:** Anaerobic digestion experiments were conducted using hermetically sealed vegetative transpiration systems and pipes. These systems were designed to maintain anaerobic conditions throughout the digestion process.
- **Biogas Volume Determination:** The volume of biogas generated during the digestion process was calculated by measuring the displacement of water in the system to the graduated test tube.
- **Methane Percentage Analysis:** The quantification of methane percentage in the biogas was carried out using a gas sampling syringe, which was injected into a 7-fold normal KOH solution. The displacement of gas in the syringe after injection represented the volume of biogas generated. The methane percentage was calculated by dividing the volume of gas displaced in the syringe by the total volume injected into the solution. It is worth noting that the KOH solution selectively absorbs CO₂, leaving

predominantly methane in the syringe, with negligible amounts of other gases such as H_2 , N_2 , and H_2S . To confirm that the gas captured in the syringe was indeed methane, a flame test was conducted once the methane percentage exceeded 60 %.

These methods and materials were employed to ensure accurate characterization of the margins and horse manure samples, as well as the reliable quantification of biogas volume and methane percentage during the anaerobic digestion experiments. The analytical techniques and experimental setup utilized in this study have been established as reliable standards in the field, providing a solid foundation for data collection and analysis.

Results and Discussion

The results obtained from the digestion of horse manure and the co-digestion of margins with a 70 % olive mill wastewater (OMWW) and 30 % horse manure mixture are highly significant and promising. The biogas production for horse manure reached an impressive value of 315 L/kg VS (volatile solids), while the co-digestion of margins yielded a biogas production of 120 L/kg VS. These values demonstrate the substantial potential for biogas generation from both substrates.

The methane content in the biogas is a crucial factor in assessing the quality and energy potential of the produced biogas. In this study, the methane content reached 73 % for the horse manure digestion and an even higher value of 80 % for the co-digestion of margins. These percentages are considered excellent and indicate a high purity of the biogas, making it suitable for energy applications.

The observed pH values provide important insights into the stability and performance of the digestion processes. The initial pH of 5.2 for horse manure and 4.6 for margins indicates the presence of acidic conditions at the start of digestion. However, as the digestion progressed, both processes showed a significant increase in pH, stabilizing at 7.2 for horse manure and 7.8 for margins. These pH values fall within the optimal range for anaerobic digestion, suggesting a favorable microbial environment and efficient biogas production.

The higher biogas production and methane content observed in the digestion of horse manure compared to the co-digestion with margins can be attributed to several factors. Horse manure is known to have a higher nutrient content and a more favorable carbon-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio, which promotes the growth and activity of methanogenic microorganisms. On the other hand, margins contain inhibitory compounds such as phenols and fatty acids, which may have limited the microbial activity and reduced the overall biogas production and methane content.

To further enhance the performance of the co-digestion process, additional optimization strategies can be considered. This may include pretreatment techniques to reduce the inhibitory compounds in the margins, adjustment of the C/N ratio through the addition of co-substrates, or modification of the process parameters such as temperature and retention time.

Conclusion and perspectives

In conclusion, the anaerobic digestion of horse manure and the co-digestion of margins offer promising opportunities for sustainable waste management and renewable energy production. The results obtained from this study demonstrate the significant potential of both substrates in terms of biogas production and methane content. The high biogas yields of 315 L/kg VS for horse manure and 120 L/kg VS for the co-digestion of margins highlight their viability as valuable feedstocks for anaerobic digestion.

The methane content of 73 % for horse manure and 80 % for the co-digestion of margins indicates the high purity of the biogas, making it suitable for energy applications. These results emphasize the importance of exploring organic waste sources for biogas generation, contributing to the shift towards renewable energy and reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

However, the study also revealed challenges associated with the co-digestion of margins due to the presence of inhibitory compounds. To optimize the co-digestion process and improve biogas production, pretreatment techniques, adjustment of the C/N ratio, and careful process parameter optimization can be implemented. These strategies will help mitigate the inhibitory effects and enhance microbial activity during digestion.

Moving forward, further research should focus on addressing these challenges and optimizing the co-digestion process. Investigating additional pretreatment methods, such as enzymatic or thermal treatments, can help to reduce the inhibitory compounds in margins and improve their digestibility. Furthermore, the exploration of potential co-substrates with complementary characteristics to margins, such as nutrient-rich organic wastes, can enhance the overall performance of the co-digestion process.

5.7 Development and synthesis of hydrogel-based soil additives based on poly(aspartic acid)

(N. Ittobane, Y. Hafidi, M. Biel, J. Pettrak, D. Schmitz)

As part of the work package “soil improving additives” the aim is to develop hydrogel-based soil additives, which act as a water saving reservoir for soils in mainly arid regions as in the Fès-Meknès area. The water absorbing properties make hydrogels interesting for saving and using the resource water effectively, enable plant cultivation and improve plant health and growth.

The main task of the project partners UMI and FH Aachen was the development and synthesis of hydrogels based on poly(aspartic acid) (PASP) as a new alternative to poly(acrylic acid)-based products for future commercial products to address drought and arid conditions for plant growth in agriculture. PASP was chosen during the project among alternatives based on hydroxymethyl cellulose (HMC, lower product yields and less water uptake) and alginic acid

(ALG, very promising but more development needed and expensive). Poly(aspartic acid) is the polyamide formed by monomer units of the amino acid aspartic acid (ASP) or its salts, respectively (sodium (PASP-Na) or potassium (PASP-K), e.g.). Crosslinked poly(aspartic acid) (cIPASP) or its salts form hydrogels in contact with water and therefore, can absorb big quantities of it. But in contrast to the poly(acrylic acid/acrylic acid salt) polymer – which is a commercially widely available product – it has some advantages, but as well disadvantages, which are mainly the following:

- Possibility to obtain main reactants from renewable resources in contrast to mineral oil resources
- Reported biodegradability in contrast to the reported poor degradability of poly(acrylic acid)
- Wide range of functionalization possibilities in the synthesis process
- Costly reactants and therefore end-product compared to acrylic acid-based materials
- Solvent usage in the synthesis process

For these reasons, it is already a polymer type considered for such applications and considered in this approach. Hydrogel synthesis and development include pre-polymer syntheses, work-up and analysis, crosslinker selection or synthesis, respectively, the crosslinking process and work-up with characterization of properties. PASP-based hydrogel samples will also be provided for ENA to be tested in greenhouse growth experiments in comparison to poly(acrylic acid)-based products (see chapter 5.9).

Figure 80: Approaches and synthesis steps to obtain PASP-based hydrogels (Schmitz 2022)

5.7.1 Synthesis of pre-polymer

The pre-polymer syntheses are divided in terms of obtaining the following general products:

- Synthesis of polysuccinimid (PSI) from maleic acid and urea with phosphoric and sulfuric acid mixture or synthesis from aspartic acid (ASP) using phosphoric acid

- Synthesis of PSI-co-polymer with glutamic acid (GLA) (cheaper co-monomer)
- Synthesis of PSI-co-polymer with lysine (LYS): simultaneous crosslinking, amino group for phosphate binding

Conditions are optimized with respect to the achieved yield and average molecular weight (determined via gel permeation chromatography (GPC)), necessary to form stable hydrogels in good yield. Figure A1 (Appendix 1) gives a brief overview regarding adaption of reaction conditions for PSI.

Crucial issue was the attempt to reduce the amount of phosphoric acid, but still within the course of the project, no less than 31 wt.-% were used in the polymerization process (Figure A1 reaction scheme b) to obtain high yield and molecular weight. Not only yield and molecular weight decrease with reduction of phosphoric acid. As well the PSI forms a branched structure (Figure A1 reaction scheme c)), which has limited solubility (completely soluble in dimethylformamide (DMF) down to 17 wt.-%) and reactivity regarding crosslinking to form a stable hydrogel. The present amide group in branched PSI is shown in the reaction scheme and could e.g., be determined via ATR-FTIR measurements. Using the cheaper reactants maleic anhydride (MAH) and urea (UR) to form the same pre-polymer (Figure A1 reaction scheme a)) lead only to low-molecular weight PSI (indicated showing the molar mass distribution in Figure A1) and was not suitable to obtain hydrogels (Figure A1).

Considering all these aspects, a reaction procedure with reduced H_3PO_4 content could not yet lead to success, but optimization using 31 wt.-% phosphoric acid (as 85 wt.-% solution), 3 h reaction time and 200 °C in vacuum lead to appropriate pre-polymer for hydrogel formation.

Another approach to obtain appropriate pre-polymer was the copolymerization of aspartic acid with other (cheaper, functional) co-monomers. Therefore, glutamic acid (price reduction) and lysine (LYS, amine function, in-situ crosslinking) were used as reactants together with ASP.

Figure 81: Reaction scheme for synthesis of PSI/GA and PSI/LYS (Schmitz 2022)

The yield decreases while increasing glutamic acid amount in PSI synthesis. Nevertheless, down to about 10-15 % GA-content still lead to acceptable yields for the pre-polymer. The

more expensive lysine on the other hand is mainly added to act as in-situ crosslinker. NMR-data (not shown) indicate the presence of the comonomers in PSI.

Generally, the pre-polymer synthesis offers a wide range of possibilities to obtain a varied chemistry or structure of the pre-polymer and therefore, also the resulting hydrogel. Challenges are still high prices of reactants and large amounts of phosphoric acid needed in most reactions to obtain a suitable pre-polymer. This is an additional cost factor and as well an ecological issue, as on the one hand valuable phosphorous compound will become a waste product, or on the other hand, its regain for recycling is laborious. Usage of smaller amounts could solve or reduce the issue (residuals in resulting hydrogel could even be considered a welcome nutrient supply), but it must be in accordance with good yields and suitable properties to generate a stable hydrogel.

The PSI chemistry offers a toolbox for chemical modifications due to its reactivity towards amines to introduce pendant groups to modify properties like crosslinking, functional groups for complexation or binding of nutrients as well as the influence on the resulting swelling properties.

5.7.2 Crosslinking and hydrolysis to cIPASP (HMD, LYS, new crosslinkers)

The succinimide ring structure of PSI can easily be reacted with an amine group. Therefore, bi-functional amines can link two polymer chains of PSI to form a hydrogel network. Figure 82 shows the mainly considered crosslinking agents, being hexamethylene diamine (HMD) and amino acid LYS as commercially available reactants. Additionally, crosslinkers based on glycine-capped ethylene or diethylene glycol and lysine complexes with copper or zinc were synthesized and applied. Different crosslinkers can affect swelling properties or, in case of copper and zinc complexes, provide micronutrients (Zn, Cu) via ion exchange or upon gel degradation.

Crosslinking is generally done in DMF or DMSO solution by addition of crosslinker. The solution forms an elastic gel after 1-12 h depending on the crosslinker and its amount. Afterwards the gel is crushed, and sodium or potassium hydroxide (NaOH, KOH) is added to convert PSI to the corresponding aspartic acid salt. One approach also included the aminolysis with ethanolamine (cIPASP-OH-HMD5.0, no further data shown in this chapter) to obtain a non-ionic structure.

Figure 82: Crosslinking procedure of PSI with dimanines and hydro- and aminolysis, respectively with base (Schmitz 2022)

In the following part, data and properties dependent on crosslinker content (HMD) and pre-polymer (PSI) structure will be shown. A series of crosslinker variation with corresponding swelling properties is shown in Table 34. Swelling degrees were calculated using the following equation as ratio between dry and water-swollen mass of polymer:

$$S = \frac{m_s - m_o}{m_o} \times 100 [\%] \quad S = \text{swelling degree}; m_o = \text{dry mass}; m_s = \text{swollen mass}$$

Table 34: Data of various PASP-hydrogels crosslinked with HMD and hydrolyzed with sodium or potassium hydroxide (Schmitz 2022)

Amount of crosslinker (HMD)	5.0 %		10.0 %		20.0 %		Solid-10 %
	Sodium- (right)		Potassium-neutralized (left)				
Residual from eluate [%]	13.3	15.2	5.9	7.9	3.0	2.9	-
S_{max} [%]	7,540	3,662	3,542	4,251	1,298	1,478	871
t_{63} [min]	4.77	2.31	1.87	1.91	0.88	0.85	0.42
AUL (0.3 psi) [%] (% of free swelling)	1,129 (49)	1,676 (46)	1,830 (52)	1,173 (28)	1,179 (91)	859 (58)	648 (74)
AUL (0.1 psi) [%] (% of free swelling)	1,821 (55)	2,336 (64)	2,555 (73)	1,957 (46)	1,315 ~100	880 (60)	633 (73)

Furthermore, the influence of hydrogel properties on differently synthesized pre-polymer was monitored. The data in Table 35 show very well, how PSI pre-polymer structure (obtained from varying phosphoric acid amounts) affects the hydrogel properties. A series of samples crosslinked with 10 % HMD were characterized regarding yield, swelling kinetics and absorbency under load (AUL). Below 20 wt.-% used in PSI synthesis, no hydrogel could be

formed corresponding with the low molecular weight of these pre-polymers. Nevertheless, also using amounts below 26 wt.-% failed, as the majority of polymer is not stable and gets lost in the eluate, giving about 26.000 g/mol as the minimum M_n of pure PSI to form stable hydrogels.

AUL is higher, when higher phosphoric acid amounts were used, which can be explained by an influence of the different gel structure or by the structure affecting the crosslinking effectivity. This is also corresponding to the higher S_{max} values when using 29 or 26 wt.-% H_3PO_4 in PSI synthesis.

Table 35: Data of various PASP-hydrogels from PSI, synthesized with different phosphoric acid amounts (Schmitz 2022)

cIPASP-Na-HMD5,0 synthesized from psi with H_3PO_4 content of...	34 wt.-%	31 wt.-%	29 wt.-%	26 wt.-%	23 wt.-%	20 wt.-%
Residual from eluate [%]	6.5	9.0	8.2	8.0	89.0	93.1
S_{max} [%]	5,003	5,705	9,928	7,307	1,133	2,007
t_{63} [min]	0.78	1.10	3.03	2.13	11.32	13.98
AUL (0.3 psi) [%] (% of free swelling)	4,061 (81.2)	3,910 (68.5)	1,754 (17.7)	2,476 (33.9)	249 (22.0)	198 (9.9)
AUL (0.1 psi) [%] (% of free swelling)	4,476 (89.5)	4,587 (80.4)	3,203 (32.3)	5,186 (71.0)	415 (36.6)	365 (18.2)

Additional to the above mentioned crosslinker, LYS was used to obtain a total amino acid-base polymer. Its use lead as well to good properties of hydrogels synthesized from it. Furthermore, damines from DEG and EG with glycine were synthesized. A different crosslinker system can also influence the hydrogel properties, which was investigated using these new crosslinkers in the synthesis process. The general reaction to obtain them is shown in Figure 83 (top). The products are obtained by esterefication of glycine with diethylene or ethylene glycol, respectively, using *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (TsOH) as catalyst in toluene. Another approach, also shown in Figure 83, is the synthesis of lysine-zinc (Zn) or copper (Cu) complexes. The stable complexes leave two free amino groups available for crosslinking. The introduced Zn and Cu ions can serve as micronutrients and be made available during degradation of the gel (Figure 83 (bottom)). Complex and complex-crosslinked hydrogels are prepared differently from the Cu/Zn-complex preparation itself (complexes: addition of lysine to copper (II) or zinc (II) containing solution, afterwards addition of sodium hydroxyide to adjust a pH at about 7.5). For crosslinking, lysine was added to the PSI solution with triethylamine to let it „pre-react“ partially. Afterwards, the metal salt is added and pH is adjusted to form the complex. Hydrolysis with NaOH is done as usual.

Figure 83: Reaction between glycine and DEG or EG (top) and LYS2Cu/Zn complexes (bottom) (Schmitz 2022)

The synthesis of the (di-)ethylene glycol crosslinkers was confirmed using ¹H-NMR-spectroscopy. The crosslinkers formed with (di-)ethylene glycol are reacted by addition to the pre-polymer solution and addition of triethylamine to activate the amine, which is still in salt form (*p*-toluenesulfonic acid salt). Hydrolysis and work-up are done analogous to HMD-/LYS-crosslinked hydrogels. All four different crosslinkers were used for syntheses of hydrogels, whose properties are summarized in Table 36.

Table 36: Properties of various PASP-hydrogels crosslinked with the new crosslinkers DEG-GLY, EG-GLY, LYS₂Cu and LYS₂Zn, respectively, and hydrolyzed with sodium hydroxide (Schmitz 2022)

Amount of crosslinker (HMD)	Obtained hydrogel from 20 g PSI [g]	S _{max} [%]	t ₆₃ [min]
DEG-GLY			
10 %	14.0	2.420	22.00
20 %	8.0	9.066	22.80
EG-GLY			
10 %	13.6	2.696	19.79
20 %	12.0	8.115	17.28
LYS ₂ Cu			
20 %	10.0	6.152	43.45
LYS ₂ Zn			
20 %	14.0	6.427	39.97

Below 10 % ((D)EG-GLY) or 20 % (LYS₂Cu/Zn)crosslinker, no gels were formed. Interestingly, using EG-GLY or DEG-GLY in higher amounts lead to higher swelling degrees. This result seems to originate from the nature of the crosslinkers, as DSC and NMR-T₂ relaxation measurements (not shown) indicated a higher crosslinking degree using 20 instead of 10 % (D)EG-GLY.

The following part presents the formation of hydrogels from ASP-copolymers with GA and LYS crosslinked with the crosslinkers HMD or LYS. GA was used for hydrogel formation, as for this pre-polymer the optimum condition was obtained with the yield of 67 % at the reaction temperature about 180-200 °C, for 3 hours, with the molar ratio of ASP acid to GA of 4:0.75 and catalyst concentration of 0.03 moles. Table 37 shows the main results (yield and S_{max}).

Table 37: Properties of various PASP/GLA-hydrogels crosslinked with HMD and LYS, respectively, and hydrolyzed with sodium hydroxide (Schmitz 2022)

Amount of crosslinker (HMD)	Obtained hydrogel from 20 g PSI [g]	S _{max} [%]
10 %	20.8	11,873
15 %	22.2	5,362
20 %	23.6	1,386
10 %	20.6	9,421

In Table 38, the results of hydrogel properties from PASP/LYS are shown. Remarkable is the sample of PASP/LYS which could be directly hydrolyzed to generate a hydrogel. This eliminates the additional step of crosslinking in organic solvent, which is ecologically and economically desired. As it is another option of solvent-free crosslinking, the approach of mixing HMD and PSI in solid for crosslinking is also added in this table and swelling properties are shown.

Table 38: Properties of various PASP/LYS-hydrogels crosslinked with HMD and hydrolyzed with sodium hydroxide (Schmitz 2022)

Amount of crosslinker (HMD)	Obtained hydrogel from 20 g PSI [g]	S_{\max} [%]
HMD		
0 %	19.5	4,566
5 %	17.0	3,063
10 %	16.0	2,088
15 %	15.0	1,256
HMD-solid-180 °C		
10 %	15.0	871

The main result is the formation of hydrogel from the PASP/LYS copolymer without additional crosslinking. As mentioned, this eliminates an additional reaction and work-up step in the reaction. Compared to the solid-reaction, much higher SD are obtained. Based on this, the reaction needs further optimization (already from copolymerization of ASP and LYS) but is very promising regarding ecological and economic aspects.

5.7.3 Biological degradation

The degradation of polyacrylic acid (Stockosorb), Polyasparaginic acid and alginate was determined in both aquatic and soil biota. For aquatic conditions, return sludge from a municipal wastewater treatment plant in Jülich was used. The dry mass content was at 3 g/L. Soil was taken from a garden in Jülich. The sample was taken at a depth of about 10 cm to exclude most roots and was sieved with 4 mm mesh to remove bigger particles.

Prior to determination of the degradation, the maximum swelling rate of the hydrogel in soil was determined. 15 g of the soil were eluted with 15 mL deionized water. The eluate was used to swell the hydrogel. The Hydrogel was put in a beaker on a scale and the eluate was added dropwise until no more swelling was observed. This resulted in a maximum amount of water per gram hydrogel that can be taken up by the hydrogel. This amount was added to the soil to obtain a maximally swollen hydrogel and the best possible conditions for the degradation of the hydrogel.

The degradation was determined by measuring the biological oxygen demand (BOD) of sludge and soil with hydrogels and comparing this to sludge and soil without hydrogels. For the

measurements, BOD OxiTop systems from WTW were utilized. The incubation is carried out as in a thermal cabinet at 20 °C +/- 1°C. For soil, 5 mg hydrogel (polyasparaginic acid and polyacrylate) per gram of soil were applied, for alginate, 1 mg per gram of soil.

For aquatic degradation, a mixture of sewage sludge and tap water was utilized with a dry mass content of 0.4 g/L. Per mL of mixture, 5 mg of PASP and PAA hydrogel were utilized, while for alginate 1 mg was used. Two drops of allylthiourea were added to inhibit the nitrification reaction.

The BOD-values are determined following this equation:

$$BOD (Hydrogel) = BOD \left(\frac{Sludge}{Soil} + Hydrogel \right) - BOD \left(\frac{Sludge}{Soil} \right)$$

Figure 84: Results of biodegradability experiments in aqueous medium (top) and in soil (bottom). (FHAC 2022)

Figure 84 shows the results for the biodegradation of hydrogels. The higher the BOD values for the hydrogel, the higher the biodegradation. All three Hydrogels seem to show a lag phase of two days, until the degradation of the hydrogel starts. As shown above, alginate is very well biodegradable, while PASP has a lower biodegradability. PAA seems to be not biodegradable.

Furthermore, since it has lower BOD than sludge without hydrogels, this indicates, that PAA inhibits microbial activity in sludge.

The graphs of the degradation in soil seem to indicate, that alginate and PASP are better degradable than PAA, but PAA in soil seems to be degradable. Striking is the decline of BOD for PASP after 9 days. This signifies that there are other processes going on, that generate pressure/gas other than carbon dioxide. One assumes that nitrification and denitrification processes cause the release of nitrogen and therefore raising the pressure in the flasks.

Since no inhibition chemical for nitrification was added, this could be the reason for the high BOD of PAA. This will be determined in a future experiment.

5.7.4 Samples for pot-experiments

The PASP-type hydrogel was also tested in growth-experiments (using onions) by the project partner ENA. The experiments were carried out on pot-scale. Therefore, two exemplary samples of PASP-K hydrogel containing additives were synthesized. Chosen was a product obtained from a PASP synthesis with 5 % HMD crosslinker mixed with humic acids provided by innoagri GmbH in a 50/50 ratio. As a second sample, a similar synthesis (5 % HMD) was carried out with addition of 60 wt.-% ground phenol-reduced olive pomace (provided by GEA) into the crosslinking process. The samples were characterized regarding yield, Q_{max} , AUL and NPK amounts found in the hydrogel's eluate (0.5 g in 500 mL distilled water after 24 h). Additionally, pot-experiments using the commercial products Huminsorb® and Arbovit® were carried out to be able to conclude from pot-results to field results for the PASP-based hydrogels.

Table 39: Properties of hydrogel-based products used for pot-experiments(Schmitz 2022)

Property	Arbovit®	Huminsorb®	cIPASP-K-HMD5,0+HA50	cIPASP-K-HMD5,0-OT60
Residual from eluate [%]	4,6	30,8	60,0	16,7
S_{max} [%]	13,883	4,282	3,599	2,446
t_{63} [min]	5.180	8.750	11.984	0.786
AUL (0.3 psi) [%] (% of free swelling)	1,986 (14.3)	1,179 (27.5)	609 (12.7)	1,630 (35.6)
AUL (0.1 psi) [%] (% of free swelling)	2,317 (16.7)	847 (19.8)	1,074 (22.4)	2,209 (48.2)
Nitrogen (TNb) [mg/L]	2.79	0.95	6.81	9.03
Phosphorous (PO_4^{3-} -P) [mg/L]	0.41	0.30	0.36	0.22
Potassium (K) [mg/L]	59.33	62.30	21.00	44.30

5.7.5 Conclusions

To summarize, we could achieve a successful approach of PASP-hydrogels as alternatives to PAA-products. Reaction conditions could be optimized, although, still further work must be done regarding this. The chemistry of the PSI/PASP-system can be used as a „toolbox“, as various functionalization and derivatization processes are available to optimize or adjust the hydrogel properties. Biodegradability was analyzed and pot-experiments of PASP-based products showed good results in comparison to PAA-based hydrogels. The work done on this polymer type as soil additive in the project I-WALAMAR can be considered successful. Nevertheless, further work must be done; main aspects are price, upscaling, reaction optimization (solvent-free, „green“) and fine-tuning for specific site-dependent properties.

Samples of synthesized hydrogels were provided to ENA for greenhouse growth experiments in comparison with PAA-based products.

5.8 Field, bench and greenhouse tests to evaluate the recycling of pre-treated olive oil processing wastes

(K. Spohrer, S. Romuli, A. Abdouabdillah, D. Schmitz)

Background

With an estimated 30 million m³ of margines per year, the Mediterranean basin generates approximately 97 % of the world's olive oil production (Meftah et al. 2019). The margines can be used as a soil fertilizer compost (Papadimitriou and Balis 1996). Due to this potential, the main objective was to determine the phytotoxicity of margine and to explore its use as a soil amendment. The following describes the experiments and results carried out at UHOH at the laboratory level and at ENA, where the margine was tested in the field with different crops.

5.8.1 Effect of olive mill wastewater on the germination of cress (*Lepidium sativum*) (UHOH)

In order to estimate the toxicity of the wastewater produced in olive oil production on plants, a rapid and repeatable assessment was needed. To assess this, one of the standards for testing plant responses is a high throughput germination test (Saadi et al. 2013). The European Standard (DIN EN 16086-2) test was followed, where cress (*Lepidium sativum*) was used as a test subject.

5.8.1.1 Experimental protocol

The tests were conducted in two configurations: one on soil, the other one on filter paper, and perlite under three application levels of margine, plus a blank, for 72 and 144 hours using cress seeds. The margine application levels were 5, 10, and 15 % (v/v), equating to around 20, 40, and 60 t/ha of applied margine, respectively. The margine was obtained from Oleafoods in Morocco. The substrates combined with the margine were placed in Petri dishes with the cress seeds. After each measurement, each Petri dish was removed from the rack, and a picture of the seedlings was taken (Figure 85).

Figure 85: Setup used for capturing the images of the cress germination (UHOH1-Margine, 2022)

As mentioned before, the effect of margine on cress germination was assessed according to DIN EN 16086-2 with the following parameters: (1) coefficient of variation of the germination rate, (2) coefficient of variation of the root length, (3) root length index and (4) the Munoo-Liisa-Vitality-Index.

5.8.1.2 Results

Table 40 shows the coefficient of variation of the germination rate and root length parameters established by the DIN EN 16086-2. The CVG indicated less variance in the tests on perlite, except for the 5 % margine concentration. For the coefficient of variation of the root length (CVR), it is noteworthy that the CVR showed differences between the seedlings for each given concentration.

Table 40: Coefficient of the variation of the germination rate (CVG) and root length (CVR) (UHOH1, 2022)

Sample*	Germination rate		Root length	
	CVG 3 Days	CVG 6 Days	CVR 3 Days	CVR 6 Days
B00	6.19 %	6.19 %	35 %	40 %
B05	18.33 %	12.37 %	69 %	74 %
B10	11.11 %	6.19 %	79 %	87 %
B15	0.00 %	5.97 %	96 %	80 %
P00	0.00 %	0.00 %	74 %	47 %
P05	19.2 %	12.4 %	61 %	58 %
P10	0.0 %	6.0 %	73 %	61 %
P15	7.9 %	6.6 %	103 %	65 %

*Letters “B” and “P” indicate soil and perlite respectively. Numbers indicate the margine concentration.

The root length index, which was well under 100 % when margines were applied, showed the reduced root elongation compared to the control sample. For 5 % margine application on perlite, the root length index after 3 days showed only a miniscule difference compared to the control. This effect was, however, observed to be more severe after six days.

For the Munoo-Liisa-Vitality-Indexes (MLV) results were similar to the root length index due to the high germination rate (> 80%). Among the tests done on soil samples, the apparent phytotoxic effect of margine seemed to be reduced at the second measurement time, indicating a time aspect, as shown by Saadi et al. (2013).

5.8.2 Soil column study to investigate the leaching behavior of total phenolics from olive mill wastewater (OMWW) (UHOH)

Figure 86 shows the design of the columns used for the experiment to study the leaching of the total phenolic compounds (TPC).

Figure 86: Soil column setup used to investigate the leaching behavior of the olive mill wastewater (UHOH2-Margine, 2022)

5.8.2.1 Experimental Procedure

The application volumes used were 0, 20, 60, and 120 m³ OMWW ha⁻¹ and are abbreviated by A0, A20, A60, and A120, respectively. The application volumes S1, S2, and S3 correspond to the sampling dates 1, 2, and 3, respectively. In this test, the depth at which the leachate penetrated the soil was determined at 0, 5, 15, 45, and 95 cm (abbreviated with a D in front of each depth).

5.8.2.2 Results

The TPCs of the highest OMWW application volumes increased at shallow depths (Figure 87). On all dates, a noticeable decrease was observed between depths D5 and D15 for A120 and A60. Until the first sampling date, OMWW application did not produce an observable increase in TPC at deeper depths (D45 and D95). TPC at these depths was not determined for the other dates. However, on S1, the TPC of all application volumes, except A120, was higher at depth D45 and D95 than at D15 (Figure 87).

Figure 87: Total phenolic content of each treatment at different depths. (UHOH3-Margine, 2022)

Note: Depths D45 and D95 were only analysed for sampling date S1. Each point represents three columns. Each geometric shape represents one sampling date. The colors represent different application volumes.

For total percolated TPC, a two-way ANOVA was performed on application volume and sampling week on all sampling dates. While neither the application volume [$F(3,24) = 0.441$, $p = 0.726$], nor the interaction [$F(6,24) = 0.794$, $p = 0.584$] had a significant effect on total percolate TPC, the sampling date had a significant effect [$F(2,24) = 95.988$, $p < 0.001$]. Total percolate TPC increased from S1 ($M = 0.8$, $SD = 0.1$, $n = 12$), over S2 ($M = 1.4$, $SD = 0.2$, $n = 12$), to S3 ($M = 2$, $SD = 0.2$, $n = 12$). Since percolate TPC decreased between sampling dates by a smaller factor than the increase in percolate volume, and since total percolate TPC was calculated as the product of percolate volume and percolate TPC, total percolate TPC increased with sampling date.

Within S2, a trend was observed. Total percolate TPC increased with increasing application volume. This trend, however, was not observed for the other sampling dates (Table 41).

Table 41: Total percolate TPC of each treatment (UHOH2, 2022)

Application volume	Total percolate TPC at S1 (mg)	Total percolate TPC at S2 (mg)	Total percolate TPC at S3 (mg)
A0	0.85 ± 0.04^b	1.29 ± 0.26^b	1.96 ± 0.21^a
A20	0.88 ± 0.17^b	1.44 ± 0.08^b	2.11 ± 0.35^a
A60	0.85 ± 0.05^b	1.44 ± 0.15^{ab}	2.06 ± 0.18^a
A120	0.71 ± 0.03^b	1.62 ± 0.16^a	1.95 ± 0.08^a

Different lower-case letters indicate a significant difference between the group means of the sampling dates within an application volume. No significant differences were found between

the group means of the application volumes within a sampling date (Tukey's test, $p < 0.05$). Each mean represents three columns.

5.8.2.3 Olive mill wastewater drip irrigation trials (UHOH)

After looking into the leakage of the phenolic compounds in the soil, and with a view to using the OMWW in irrigation, a test was performed to determine if the dripping system (irrigation drippers and/or purification filters) could get clogged by it. The application of OMWW in a drip irrigation system, however, is still under-researched, despite it being a favoured irrigation system due to the high-water use efficiency (Martínez and Reca 2014).

5.8.2.4 Experimental protocol

To test the feasibility, a custom-made test bench was installed, as illustrated in Figure 88. Further information about the experimental set up can be provided upon request.

Figure 88: Olive mill wastewater irrigation trial setup (UHOH4-Margine, 2022)

An increase in negative pressure of SP was used to indicate clogging of the filter while an increase in PP was used to determine clogging of the drippers. To evaluate if an increase in OMWW concentration in a drip irrigation system causes clogging of the system, OMWW concentrations of 10-, 30- and 50 % (v/v) were tested.

5.8.2.5 Results

It was found that no significant change in flow rate (FR) was observed between OMWW concentrations of 30 % and 50 %. Nevertheless, it can be assumed that increasing the OMWW concentration further may result in a decline of flow rate due to an increase in dry matter (DM) of the solution.

Concerning suction power of the pump and thus clogging of the filter, no clear trend was observed between experimental runs of different OMWW concentrations. For all tested

OMWW concentrations, average SP was 0.009 ± 0.001 MPa. Moreover, no substantial accumulation of solid particles between the filter plates was observed with increasing OMWW concentration. Throughout all experimental runs, no visible blockages at the irrigation drippers were observed.

5.8.3 Use of margines to improve soil characteristics in a two-year trial (2021-2022): Case of onion and melon crops (ENA)

The objective of this work was to evaluate the impact of the contribution of margines as soil additives on onion and melon crops, by determining the optimal dose of margines to obtain an optimal yield in terms of quantity and quality.

5.8.3.1 Experimental protocol

The total plot area used for this study was 880 m² for both years. It was prepared to accommodate a complete randomized block design. Each experimental unit was 2.8 m x 20 m = 56 m² (Figure 89).

The following margine doses were tested:

- T1 : No OMWW added
- T2 : OMWW dose = 140 L = 25 m³/ha
- T3 : OMWW dose = 280 L = 50 m³/ha
- T4 : OMWW dose = 420 L = 75 m³/ha

The margine doses were maintained the same for both years. As for water input, only one dose equal to 100 % of the evapotranspiration of the crop ET_c was given.

Figure 89: Use of Margine Experimental design (ENA-Margine, 2022)

5.8.3.2 Results

Regarding the number of leaves evaluated in onions, Figure 90 shows that there was a significant difference in the number of leaves among the samples over time. Indeed, the first and second treatments stood out over time compared to the other treatments. On the other hand, T1 seemed to have a lower number of leaves than the other treatments.

The highest average number of leaves per plant (16 leaves) was recorded for treatment T2 (OMWW dose = 140 L = 25 m³/ha).

Figure 90: Leaf number of (a) melon and (B) onion plants under the effect of the applied margines dose. (ENA2-Margine, 2022)

Note: The error bars represent standard deviations. The same letters indicate the values that do not show a significant difference by the Student-Newman-Keuls (SNK).

Another parameter measured throughout the trial period for all treatments was the collar diameter (Figure 91).

Figure 91: Collar diameter of (a) onion and (b) melon plants under the effect of the dose of margins applied (ENA3-Margine, 2022)

Note: The error bars represent standard deviations. The same letters indicate values that do not show a significant difference by the SNK test.

The descriptive analysis of the data collected regarding the collar size showed that the use of margins affected the collar size in a good way during the cycle. Onion collars were larger in the treatments with higher doses of margins, but at the end of the experiment this difference was not significant anymore. The onions in all the treatments had more or less the same size.

As for the yield, we found different results between the two years of trial. In the first year, we didn't find any significant differences between the four treatments even though it was clear that we have a downward trend between the first and the last treatment but it was not significant (Figure 92). This may be because the mineralization process can take a long time to set up and the effect of the margins on the soil was not yet evident to have an impact on yield.

Figure 92: Average yield production per treatment in tons for (a) onion and (b) melon (ENA4-Margine, 2022)

Note: Error bars represent standard deviations.

Moreover, in the second year of trial we monitored the fruit quality, such as the brix content and the firmness of the fruit. Concerning the sugar content of melon fruits, the analysis of variance reveals how the increase of margins doses in soil tend to increase the sugar concentration of the fruits at harvest stage. Indeed, the highest brix dose was found among the fruits of the 4th treatment where we used the highest dose of margine (Figure 93).

Figure 93: Brix content average of melon fruits at harvest (ENA5-Margine, 2022)

Note: Error bars represent standard deviations.

5.8.4 Conclusions of the land applications

Regarding the phytotoxicity effect of margine on cress seeds, it was shown that there is a depression of root and shoot length elongation. For the germination under the set conditions, no significant differences were found. The phytotoxic effects were most pronounced after 3 days on soil samples, showing a significant impact on the root elongation and complete

seedling. On perlite samples, no difference was found between the 5 % margine concentration treatment and the control, while higher concentrations did impact the root and seedling length significantly. After 6 days of germination, these effects were still seen, but comparably lower, especially for the higher margine concentration.

Concerning the leakage of TPC from the OMWW, based on quantitative analysis of the percolate, the one-time utilization of volumes of OMWW up to 120 m³ ha⁻¹ on slightly loamy sand, given a groundwater level lower than 1 m, does not carry a short-term risk of groundwater contamination with phenolics.

In relation to the obstruction of the dripping system using OMWW, it can be assumed that the investigated concentrations do not cause severe clogging of the filter used.

As for the field trials performed at ENA, we can conclude that the use of margines has affected the physiological parameters in the first year of trial, contrary to the yield, where no effect was found. On the other hand, in the second year of the trial, the physiological parameters were not affected. However, there was an increment in yield with the addition of higher margine doses. Regardless, this can only be confirmed after a third year, as it takes time for mineralization to determine the actual effect of margines on the soil characteristics. It should be noted that physical and chemical soil analyses are being processed.

5.9 Land application tests with innovative artificial hydrogels as moisture absorber for the Assessment as non-organic fertilizer

(K. Spohrer, A. Abouabdillah, D. Schmitz)

Background

Water-retaining amendments that improve water and nutrient use efficiency will become increasingly important over time, especially in arid and semi-arid regions where water availability is limited, as is the case in Morocco. Hydrogels have been applied as an amendment product to increase the water-holding capacity of the soil.

5.9.1 Effect of hydrogel and olive mill wastewater on germination and seedling growth of cress as bioindicator (UHOH)

As hydrogel and olive mill wastewater (OMWW) are irrigation-related elements, the interaction between both and their subsequent effect on plant growth requires studying. Therefore, this study aimed to test the potential interaction between the hydrogel and diluted OMWW as a moistening solution and its subsequent effect on cress (*Lepidium sativum*) germination and seedling growth.

5.9.1.1 Experimental protocol

The experiment tested two types of hydrogel, named hereafter “H9” (cIPASP-HMD5.0, see chapter 5.7) and “VH 26” (cIPASP-OH-HMD5.0, see chapter 5.7). These were developed and manufactured by the Aachen University of Applied Sciences, Institute for Applied Polymer Chemistry. Both hydrogel types were based on crosslinked polysuccinimide, which underwent subsequent hydrolysis with sodium hydroxide or, parallel to the crosslinking, aminolysis with ethanolamine, respectively. This difference in the synthesis path resulted in different swelling capacities. Because of this, it was desirable to investigate the water-holding capacity (WHC) that the hydrogels add to the soil. The before-mentioned hydrogels were also compared to Arbovit® and Huminsorb® hydrogels, two commercially available products (GEFA Produkte Fabritz GmbH, Krefeld, Germany) with polyacrylate as the base material, mixed with clay minerals and humic acids, respectively. The OMWW used was provided by Oleic Bovera, SL, Lleida, Spain. Further information on the experimental set-up can be provided upon request.

5.9.1.2 Results

The results of the water-holding capacity trial are presented in Table 42. The addition of all hydrogel types, except H9 hydrogel, resulted in significantly higher WHC ($p < 0.05$) than the control.

Table 42: Maximum water holding capacity (WHC) of the soil- and soil-hydrogel samples (UHOH1-Hydrogel, 2022)

Samples	Maximum Water Holding Capacity, g water · 100 g ⁻¹ DM *
Soil (control)	33.8 ± 0.5 ^b
Soil mixed with H9 hydrogel	34.9 ± 0.5 ^{ab}
Soil mixed with VH-26 hydrogel	35.5 ± 0.5 ^a
Soil mixed with Huminsorb® hydrogel	35.9 ± 0.5 ^a
Soil mixed with Arbovit® hydrogel	36.2 ± 0.5 ^a

*DM stands for dry matter. Results are expressed in LS-means ± standard error. Results with the same letter are not significantly different from each other ($p < 0.05$).

As for the cress germination in the soil with the hydrogels combined with different moistening concentrations of OMW, the germination percentage was not affected by hydrogel addition into the substrate. This was independent of the concentration of OMWW used as moistening solutions. Moreover, no phytotoxicity effect was observed within each growing media at any tested OMWW concentration (Figure 94).

Figure 94: Cress seedlings after 72 h germination period on soil mixed with H9 and VH 26 hydrogel, which was moistened with diluted OMWW (10 %, v/v) (UHOH1-Hydrogel, 2022)

Regarding the root length of the seedlings, the samples with VH 26 hydrogel at OMWW concentrations of 10 and 25 % were significantly lower than those with H9 hydrogel (Figure 95).

Figure 95: Effect of increasing OMWW concentration in the moistening solution on seedling root length (UHOH2-Hydrogel, 2022)

Note: The vertical bars represent the 95 % confidence interval.

5.9.2 Assessment of the combined effect of hydrogels and deficit irrigation on onion and melon over a two-year experiment (ENA)

This work was interested in evaluating the impact of hydrogel application as a soil additive on different crops (onion and melon) by determining the optimal dose of water to be applied and the adequate hydrogel application rate and type to obtain an optimal yield in terms of quantity and quality. To investigate this effect, two experiments were conducted: one in the field, which took place over two years, and the other under controlled conditions in a greenhouse.

5.9.2.1 Experimental protocol: field experiment

The experiment was conducted in a plot located within the National School of Agriculture of Meknès, located 10 km southeast of the city of Meknès. The experimental plot was in fallow mode for more than 10 years. The first year (2021) onions were planted (red variety), followed by melons (Kechal variety) in the second year.

The factors tested (for both years) were:

- The hydrogel types: Arbovit® Polyacrylate (hydrogel mixed with clay minerals) and Huminsorb® Polyacrylate (hydrogel mixed with humic acids).
- Hydrogel application rates: 30 kg/ha and 20 kg/ha.
- Water application rates: 100 % and 50 % of ET_c crop evapotranspiration.

Two experimental units without hydrogel were included, one received 100 % ET_c and the other 50 % ET_c water. Each combination was tested with 4 replicates. The total number of treatments was equal to 40. Table 43 shows the different treatments applied.

Table 43: Hydrogel treatments applied on the field (ENA, 2022)

Treatment	Type of hydrogel	Dose of hydrogel application	Dose of water supply
T1 (AP, 30kg, 100 %)	Arbovit® Polyacrylate	30 kg/ha	100 % d'Etc
T2 (AP, 30kg, 100 %)	Arbovit® Polyacrylate	20 kg/ha	100 % d'Etc
T3 (HP, 30kg, 100 %)	Huminsorb® Polyacrylate	30 kg/ha	100 % d'Etc
T4 (HP, 20kg, 100 %)	Huminsorb® Polyacrylate	20 kg/ha	100 % d'Etc
T5 (AP, 30kg, 50 %)	Arbovit® Polyacrylate	30 kg/ha	50 % d'Etc
T6 (AP, 20kg, 50 %)	Arbovit® Polyacrylate	20 kg/ha	50 % d'Etc
T7 (HP, 30kg, 50 %)	Huminsorb® Polyacrylate	30 kg/ha	50 % d'Etc
T8 (HP, 20kg, 50 %)	Huminsorb® Polyacrylate	20 kg/ha	50 % d'Etc
T9 (Control, 100 % d'ETc)	Without Hydrogel	0 kg/ha	100 % d'Etc
T10 (Control, 50 % d'ETc)	Without Hydrogel	0 kg/ha	50 % d'Etc

5.9.2.2 Results: Field experiment

The evolution of the growth parameters (leaf number, crown diameter and plant height) was monitored for both crops and experiments. For both years, the ten applied treatments did not show any significant effect on the three parameters (Figure 96).

Figure 96: Plant height of (a) onion and (b) melon under the effect of different hydrogel types, concentrations, and water applications rates. (ENA1-Hydrogel, 2022)

Note: The error bars represent standard deviations.

As for the yield evaluation, treatment T3 (HP, 30 kg, 100 %) recorded the best yield over 2 successive years with 70.5 T/ha and 55.38 T/ha for onion and melon respectively.

Thus, the multiple comparisons test of SNK means carried out in relation to the ten treatments allowed to determine the statistically different averages, namely, the group (a) constituted by the treatment T3 (HP, 30 kg, 100 %) with the highest yield. The group (b) is composed of the treatments T1 (AP, 30 kg, 100 %), T2 (AP, 20 kg, 100 %) and T4 (HP, 20 kg, 100 %), the third group (c) is formed by T9 (control, 100 %), T5 (AP, 30 kg, 50 %), T6 (AP, 20 kg, 50 %), T7 (HP, 30 kg, 50 %) and T8 (HP, 20 kg, 50 %). The last group (d) consists of the control treatment T10 (control, 50 %).

It can be noted that the use of hydrogels without deficit irrigation resulted in 27 % increase in yield compared to the control treatment irrigated with 100 % of water requirements T9 (control, 100 %) for the melon crop and an increase of 18 % for the onion crop. Furthermore, the deficit treatments with 50 % ETc combined with hydrogel application, showed an increase in yield by 13 % compared to the deficit control treatment with 50 % ETc and no hydrogel application for the melon crop and 12 % increase for the onion crop. From this result, it is confirmed that the amount of hydrogel added has a significant impact on the increase of melon production even in the presence of a water deficit of 50 % compared to the control treatments. Hydrogels allowed water saving without affecting the yield (Figure 97).

Figure 97: Yield in tons per hectare for different treatments for onion crop (a) and melon (b). (ENA2-Hydrogel, 2022)

5.9.2.3 Experimental protocol: greenhouse experiment

In a sheltered environment, the pots were arranged in a complete randomized block design. Each experimental unit consisted of two pots. The same treatments were studied and each treatment was repeated four times. In this case, four types of hydrogels were used:

Huminsorb® (A), Arbovit® (B), cIPASP-HMD5,0-K+HA50 (C), and cIPASP-K-HMD5,0-OT66 (D). Table 44 shows the experimental design adopted.

Table 44: Hydrogel treatments applied on the greenhouse experiment (ENA2, 2022)

Treatment	Type of hydrogel	Dose of hydrogel application	Dose of water supply
T1 (A, 30 kg, 100 %)	A	30 kg/ha	100 % d'ETc
T2 (A, 30 kg, 50 %)	A	30 kg/ha	50 % d'ETc
T3 (B, 30 kg, 100 %)	B	30 kg/ha	100 % d'ETc
T4 (B, 30 kg, 50 %)	B	30 kg/ha	50 % d'ETc
T5 (C, 30 kg, 100 %)	C	30 kg/ha	100 % d'ETc
T6 (C, 30 kg, 50 %)	C	30 kg/ha	50 % d'ETc
T7 (D, 30 kg, 100 %)	D	30 kg/ha	100 % d'ETc
T8 (D, 30 kg, 50 %)	D	30 kg/ha	50 % d'ETc
T9 (--, 0 kg, 100 %)	Control	0 kg/ha	100 % d'ETc
T10 (--, 0 kg, 50 %)	Control	0 kg/ha	50 % d'ETc

5.9.2.4 Results: Greenhouse experiments

Statistical analysis of onion plant height data at harvest showed a significant effect of the irrigation rate*hydrogel type interaction. The SNK multiple comparisons test of means performed against the (irrigation rate*hydrogel type) combinations identified statistically different means. The highest heights were obtained in treatments T5 (100 % ETC; C), T7 (100 % ETC, D) and T3 (100 % ETC, A) with mean values of 80.8 cm, 80.4 cm and 80.29 cm respectively.

Figure 98 shows that there were no significant differences between treatments T1 (100 % ETC; A), T6 (50 %; C), T8 (50 %; D) and T9 (100 % ETC; WITHOUT). It can therefore be concluded that the use of hydrogels compensated for the low water application.

Figure 98: Plant height at harvest for tested treatments. (ENA3-Hydrogel, 2022)

Regarding the yield, the analysis of variance showed no significant effect of the irrigation rate*hydrogel type interaction on onion yield. However, it did show a significant effect of the irrigation rate factor and the hydrogel type factor on final onion yield.

The highest yield was recorded by treatment T7 (100 % ETC; D), which was 100.3 t/ha. While treatment T10 (50 %ETC; control) recorded the lowest yield of 41.0 t/ha (Figure 99).

Figure 99: Bulb yield for tested treatments. (ENA4-Hydrogel, 2022)

5.9.3 Conclusions of the land applications with hydrogels

For the tests performed at UHOH, it can be seen that the water-holding capacity of the developed hydrogels proved to be equal to those available in the market. Moreover, our results showed that the tested hydrogel types had no phytotoxic effect on cress germination and

seedling growth. Furthermore, moistening the substrates with different concentrations of OMWW, especially those containing low phenolic content, seems safe for agricultural use.

As for the field tests done at ENA, it can be concluded that the yield of the irrigation treatments with 50 % ET_c and hydrogels is nearly identical (almost 60 t/ha) to the yield of the 100 % ET_c treatment without hydrogels. This leads to the conclusion that hydrogels save 50 % of water input without affecting onion bulb yield. On the other hand, the hydrogels with 100 % ET_c improve the onion yield by almost 40 % compared to the control without hydrogels reaching almost 100 t/ha.

5.10 Study on land application techniques suitable to strengthen agricultural recycling options

(H. Hoogen, M. Krauss, W. Kirchhof)

5.10.1 Background

Combating desertification is especially important. This is particularly true for the vast deserts and their neighboring regions in Africa. Every year, between 10 and 12 million hectares of fertile land are lost to desertification. Complex tasks related to soil and water will shape the economic, scientific and political future. The region considered in this project is typical.

The I-WALAMAR project aims to contribute to rehabilitation of soils in arid and hot regions and to maintain their functions, otherwise soils as a basis of life will be lost and rural exodus and migration will increase. In addition, the project is intended to contribute to maintaining the productivity of soils over the long term, conserving water resources and making soils resilient to the effects of climate change.

Therefore, the I-WALAMAR project aims to reduce water consumption and increase resource conservation.

Soil chemistry and soil physics, as well as the carbon balance of soils, are of particular importance here. The soil auxiliaries and organic products described in the project are relevant here, as they are available regionally and require treatment and recycling anyway. In addition to the laboratory tests and the field tests, technical methods must be used to enable the application of soil auxiliaries in line with requirements.

In the following, suitable technologies for recultivation and for the application of soil auxiliaries are described, which are suitable for use for soil improvement under the conditions in the region under consideration in Morocco. In order to adapt to the site conditions, the choice of the best available soil cultivation or irrigation technology is important for acceptance by the later technology user.

We conducted a study that focuses on the recultivation and remediation of soils, as well as on the application of the organic substances investigated in the project as soil auxiliaries margin and pomace. This chapter describes the appropriate technologies for soil preparation and management as part of a feasibility study.

5.10.2 Technical tasks in recultivation and rehabilitation as well as soil management in the study region

5.10.2.1 Condition of the soils during the extraction of virgin land, or the recultivation of previously unused soils

Many of the region's soils are so permeated with stones that large-scale, efficient, and resource-conserving processing with technology is not possible. This is due to the geological formation of the soil. The traditional method of manually reading the stones on the surface cannot be considered adequate to the requirements. Therefore, it is necessary to use site-appropriate technical systems for stone removal. These technologies are described below. In addition, many "rough soils", i.e. soils that have never been used for agriculture or overgrown with plants, are densely packed or even compacted. Only non-compacted soils can be farmed sustainably. Soils with physical defects have problems in the water and soil air balance, which have a major impact on rootability and thus on yield, yield security and resilience. These soils need to be deeply worked or loosened. There are a large number of very different systems available for this purpose, the possible applications of which are described below.

Modern technologies are described that allow both deep tillage for loosening the soil and mixing the soil for application/introduction of soil amendments, as well as dilution of salt accumulations to acceptable levels in the soil depth.

5.10.2.2 Remediating damaged soils

In the long run, all soils with an excessively high salt concentration will fall out of cultivation, either because they can no longer be used for growing crops, or because yield losses due to high surface salinity make agricultural use uneconomical. The desalination or reduction of the salt content in the rooted soil is therefore a decisive factor in the agriculture of arid regions. In arid regions, as well as in the region under study, there are two essentially different ways in which salt accumulates on the surface and hinders or even prevents water uptake by plants due to the high osmotic pressure. On the one hand, at sites close to groundwater, large amounts of water can be brought to the soil surface by capillary action, the water evaporates, and the salt load accumulates at the soil surface. This is especially true for the Solonetz and Solonchak soils found in the region. Here, the water-bearing capillaries must be broken. In many cases, the salt crust on the surface or the soil near the surface must also be treated. On the other hand, salt accumulates on the surface due to improper watering or irrigation.

Soil salinization has many causes. One cause is the high rate of groundwater extraction and the sharp drop in groundwater levels. In particular, the Saiis plain is prone to falling groundwater levels, as shown in Figure 41.

We recommend taking precautions to eliminate all soil damage caused by salt, including natural salinization at solonchaks and solonetz. Solonetz is often formed after groundwater lowering or after climate change towards higher precipitation due to desalination from solonchaks.

Solonchak is a highly saline soil type with a high concentration of soluble salts. It occurs where saline groundwater comes close to the surface or where evapotranspiration is significantly high. The inherent fertility is very low and there is a lack of moisture and vegetation throughout the year.

Solonetz has an underground horizon (subsoil) with a higher clay content than the upper horizon. Solonetz soils are internationally known as sodic or alkaline soils and are highly alkaline (pH > 8.5). It contains more than 15 % exchangeable sodium (Omuto 2013). In almost all cases, the salt crust on the surface or the soil near the surface must also be treated. Soil compaction due to poor management is very rare in arid regions. The task is similar to the one described in 5.10.2.1.

5.10.2.3 Approaches to sustain soil fertility, increase effective field capacity, and reduce evapotranspiration as climate change adaptation and resilience measures

Soil structure is of central importance for agricultural and forestry soils. Soil structure has a major influence on the soil-water balance and the soil-air balance (Figure 100). Enrichment of soils with organic matter results in a variety of effects that contribute to long-term yield stability.

Figure 100: Approaches to soil cultivation and agricultural management for the creation of a sustainable and long-lasting efficient soil structure

5.10.3 Site-appropriate and demand-driven soil management technologies

In many regions, stones significantly limit the agricultural use of the soil. Stones or foreign objects can damage agricultural equipment and reduce the quality and quantity of crop yields. This is especially true for vegetables of all kinds. The shelf life of harvested crops is also often severely compromised by damage to the epidermis. There are several methods for de-stoning the soil using different machines and equipment. We studied various possibilities for de-stoning or processing stones and foreign bodies in agricultural soils.

Figure 101: Systematics for the removal or processing of stones and foreign bodies from agricultural soils

5.10.3.1 Technologies for the de-stoning or processing of stones and foreign bodies in agricultural soils

5.10.3.1.1 De-stoning as "clearing"

In some areas, stones severely limit land use. This applies in particular to the agricultural sector. Stones can damage farming equipment and reduce the quality and quantity of crop yields.

There are several methods to remove stones from the soil using different machines and equipment. The authors recommend the following three methods:

Clearing is the removal of rocks and debris from the ground to a specified depth (usually topsoil). Two types of machines are used, depending on the size of the stones to be removed. Modified looseners (from 120 mm stone diameter) and "stone-rakes" or "stone-collectors" (from 30 mm stone diameter) are used.

The removal of stones is a relatively complex process. Stone harvesters are machines similar to potato harvesters. The majority of the work is carried out with screen rollers and screen chains. Typically, stones and debris from about 30 mm to about 350 mm can be removed. This is highly dependent on site conditions. The machines work with intermediate bunkers to collect the cleared stones first in the machine itself, or with transfer belts that allow the stones to be deposited in a parallel moving trolley (Figure 102).

Figure 102: Stone collector with integrated collection bunker, (bottom photo) open cart when removing the broken stones and coarse materials, (Source: Hoogen, 2020)

5.10.3.1.2 Destruction of the stones by stone crushers

Stone crushers (Figure 103) can crush stones and debris down to a few millimeters. This method should be avoided when using soils for agricultural purposes, as in addition to the stones, the soil structure is also destroyed and the sharp edges can affect the quality of the crop. On the other hand, stone crushers can be used for underground construction before topsoil is applied. The use of a stone crusher is a typical method of removing stones from the ground. This special tool, also called a stone crusher, can destroy stones and foreign objects. Depending on the source rock, the rocks are crushed into dust-like to fist-sized shapes. Shale rock (slate) is easily crushed, while quartz, granite, limestone, and basalt can only be crushed with great wear and tear on the machine.

The stones are picked up and crushed by a milling shaft with heavy flails. This makes stone crushers very stable and powerful milling machines. The area output depends on the amount of stones. On the other hand, it should be noted that in addition to the stones, the soil structure is also destroyed. Due to the high working speed of the machine, a milling sole is also created, which must then be removed.

Stone crushers are suitable for underground construction prior to topsoil application and are commonly used in landscaping and horticulture, golf and sports fields, and road construction.

Figure 103: Stone crusher (see grinding sole on left photo) (Source: Hoogen, 2022), „Stone raking“ as preparatory work for stone rubble or stone collection, or direct removal

Stone swaths (Figure 104) can be used to increase the area coverage of the stone breakers and to place the stones in the swath so that they can be picked up by loaders or by hand. However, the working depth is shallow, so the surface looks clean but the stones are not removed from the ground.

Figure 104: Photo of a Stone rakes, Type IMANTS (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

5.10.3.1.4 „Hiding" stones in the deeper layers of the soil with reverse milling

Reverse milling machines (**Figure 105**), i.e. milling machines that operate in the opposite direction to the tractor (so-called stone milling machines), pick up the soil and screen the material flow during reverse placement, so that stones and foreign bodies of a defined size are deposited under the screen material. These can usually be hidden to a depth of 5 to 12 cm. This method is only suitable for areas that do not need to be reworked afterwards (e.g. golf courses).

Hiding stones, reverse milling with sieve inserts: Reverse milling is used to remove stones from the soil. The soil is picked up with the tiller and the material stream is screened as it is deposited backwards, so that stones and foreign bodies of a certain size (about the size of a fist) are deposited under the screenings.

These can usually be hidden at a depth of between 5 and 12 cm. However, this method is only suitable for areas that are not going to be ploughed again (e.g. pastures or permanent crops, e.g. olive, argan, etc.). The application of such a method in the region studied is permanent, since neither swelling nor shrinking of the soils nor cryoturbation ("growing" of the stones with frozen soil) would change the location of the stones.

The application of methods for de-stoning or removal of foreign bodies from the soil is generally relatively complex and costly. Investment costs and other key figures are shown in Table 45.

Figure 105: Reversing tiller (reverse cutter) for stones (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

Table 45: Key figures for the application of processes for the de-stoning and processing of stones or foreign bodies in agricultural soils

No.	Type of machine	Working depth cm	Working width cm	Working speed m/h	power requirement kW	Investment cost (only machine) EURO
1	Stone collector	20 – 30	150 – 250	600 -1,000	90 – 150	65,000 – 90,000
2	Stone rake	5 - 15	400 – 600	600 – 1,500	150 – 250	35,000 – 70,000
3	Stone crusher	15 - 50	250 – 300	400 – 1,000	250 – 350	90,000 – 125,000
4	Reverse cutter	10 - 15	150 – 250	150 – 600	25 – 75	3,500 – 15,000

5.10.3.2 Technologies to loosen soil and destroy hard salt layers

Technologies of soil loosening and treatment of soils with salt accumulation are easily systematized (Figure 106). Systematization is carried out according to the mode of operation of technologies in soils. So far, the world agricultural machinery industry has focused on the

production of standard methods of soil cultivation. The cultivation of soils in the landscapes of arid regions is still a real niche. In the future, these soils and how to work them will become more important. In general, soils are loosened to the depth at which rooting is possible on the site. Soil rooting and biological stabilization are critical to the durability of the loosening success.

Figure 106: Simplified systematization of the machines and equipment for loosening and processing of salt accumulations in soils

5.10.3.2.1 Lifting loosening - loosening without soil mixing

The methods of lifting loosening are old and proven (Figure 107). However, mixing tillage is not possible with these methods. Nevertheless, it is required if salt accumulations are to be eliminated, or mineral or organic soil auxiliaries are to be incorporated, as in the present application case of the project. In principle, a distinction is made between two different types of drive:

- Static lifting: loosening with working tools that are pulled through the floor without their own movement and
- Dynamic lifting loosening with working tools, which gain a drive and an additional working movement in the ground through the tractor, which has a considerable influence on the size of the soil aggregates and thus the loosening success.

With custom-made products, you can achieve great working depths that even go beyond the rooted soil.

In such cases, large soil chisels (Figure 108) are used to drain the surface water as drains or to break capillaries in order to prevent the rising of the soil water.

Figure 107: How the lifting loosening works when working in the ground (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

Recently, there have been technological developments that have been very successful in sealing bearing soils. These technologies are a logical continuation of the rocker or swivel blockers developed some 50 years ago. To establish new processes in practice, comparative applications of different technologies are often carried out at different locations. Before a machine with a new working method is introduced to the market, it must prove itself in the field in terms of working method and operational safety. In order to eliminate the compaction damage caused by lifting and loosening, it is necessary to drive under it. This means that lifting looseners work deeper than the actual expansion of the compaction in the vertical axis. Typically, static scarifiers are used to a working depth of about 100 cm. There are machines (Figure 109) that can be combined with other machines for topsoil cultivation or seeding at working depths of up to 50 cm.

Among the methods of lifting loosening on particularly densely bedded sites, the method of dynamic stabbing-stroke loosening (Figure 110 and Figure 111) has become established in recent years. This method is a consistent development of the Imants company.

Figure 108: Typical static lifting loosening systems (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

Figure 109: Lifting-Looser working depth up to 50 cm in combination with a device for topsoil processing and seeder, Source: Hoogen, 2022

step one - cutting

step two - lifting

Figure 110: Mode of operation of the "Cultermatic" dynamic stab-and-stroke loosening device (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

Figure 111: Photos of the "Cultermatic" dynamic lifting and prising loosening device (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

5.10.3.2.2 Demolition loosening - loosening with soil mixture and desalination, incorporation of soil additives, especially organic matter

Demolition loosening technologies (Figure 113), unlike lifting loosening technologies, are always mechanically driven. This means that the tools running in the soil are in motion and actively and purposefully work the soil. Over the past twenty years, in addition to small-series machines such as the MM 100 demolition loosener, spade machines have become established and are used in large numbers for soil cultivation worldwide.

Figure 112: Functioning of lifting loosening (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

5.10.3.2.3 Spade machines

Spade machines are powered and do not break the soil by "lifting the soil from the bottom up", but by "breaking the soil backwards". To do this, the machines must be driven. This is done through a standard device on the tractor called a power take-off. Spade machines look like tillers, but they differ significantly from conventional tillers in terms of speed and circumferential speed, as well as the diameter and shape of the working tools. Spade machines rotate very slowly and the working tools look like the classic "hand spade" used for digging in the garden. The use of a spade machine is particularly recommended when different soil horizons need to be intensively mixed, or when additives need to be incorporated into the soil, such as the organic soil additives based on olive processing residues in this project. Working depths of 125 cm and more can be achieved with spade machines.

At the heart of the spade machine there are large rotating tools (Figure 116), called "spades," with slow rotation speeds and very large diameters. The tools are the size of a spade and really bite into the soil. The working angles of the tools are designed in such a way that only the tip of the spade is in contact with the soil, thus avoiding "smearing" of the soil. The diameter of the spade shaft and its speed have a great influence on the mixing effect. The higher the center of the spade shaft is above the soil, the lower the mixing effect. When the spade shaft works below the soil level (below the soil surface), intensive mixing of the soil begins. Soil mixing - without harmful side effects - is the key to successful soil cultivation in the context of recultivation and application of soil additives. Spade machines can be very easily adapted to the requirements in the setting in practical use at the site itself.

In general, the following basic settings apply to spade machines (Figure 113):

- The larger the diameter of a spade machine, the greater the possible working depth. Spade machines are built up to 270 cm in diameter. These machines can then be used to a depth of 135 cm without significant mixing of the soil. Regardless of the diameter of the spade machine, if the center of the spade shaft is at the depth of the soil, the machine will begin to mix the soil. If the center of the shaft is below ground level, the machine will mix the soil strongly.
- The higher the speed of the shaft on which the spades are mounted, the greater the mixing effect and the smaller the individual soil units.
- The larger the spades, the greater the mixing effect. There are many different types of spades.

In practice, however, sites (Figure 114) vary widely in terms of soil conditions and application objectives. There are general recommendations for use. In the past, numerous field trials have been carried out to optimize the shape of the tools for the specific application.

Spade machines (Figure 116 and Figure 117) and their use have a great influence on the carbon balance of an arable soil.

Figure 113: Adjustment possibilities when working with a spade machine (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

Figure 114: Set-up of a field trial to determine the degree of mixing as a function of travel speed, shaft speed and spade shape (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

different **tools** for spading machines
= different **work-results**

Figure 115: Different spade shapes as tools in spade machines for mixing tillage (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

Figure 116: Different spade machines for different applications and operating sizes (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

5.10.3.2.4 Ploughs as a combination of lifting and demolition loosening

Ploughs (Figure 117), which are built in very different forms, represent an exceptional technology. Ploughs loosen the soil and turn it at the same time. However, the degree of mixing efficiency can only be adjusted to a limited extent. In the field applications in the region studied, the use

of a plow would be rather counterproductive, as stones and foreign bodies would be brought to the surface.

Important notice: The technologies presented are used worldwide. They would be fully available and applicable in Morocco, but they are large machines that are relatively expensive to purchase and should only be used by trained personnel. After working the soil with the technologies described above, the cultivated soil should always be grassed over, as it is at risk of being driven over and eroded!

Figure 117: Typical use of a plow for ploughing grassland on soil without stones and foreign bodies (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

5.10.3.3 Technologies for the application of liquid and free-flowing organic soil additives from olive oil processing

During the olive oil processing, olives and the raw olive oil fractions were treated in various cleaning and concentration processes where clean water is added and polluted water is extracted. Throughout the process line, a liquid phase, known as the margin, and a more solid, difficult to pump olive waste pulp are produced. A liquid-tight application technique must be used for this.

On small areas, these organic substances can also be applied manually with buckets or small drums.

The synthetic soil additives are water-soluble and have very low application rates. These substances can easily be applied in small quantities with watering cans or plant protection tips. As they are not dangerous, the technical requirements are low. Barrel trucks of different sizes (Figure 118) can be used for this purpose. Margin and olive waste slurry can also be applied together in a mixture.

The application rates of organic and synthetic soil additives are relatively low at 500 to 1,000 liters per hectare. These materials are relatively homogeneous. They mix as they pass over the fields in the tanker truck. It is recommended that they be mechanically or hydraulically stirred prior to application.

If possible, the soil additives should be applied as a band, close to existing plants or future plant rows. There are simple technical solutions for this, but also highly technical special solutions for inter-farm use in services or in farming communities.

Figure 118: Buckets (1. left) and small drums (2. left) for distribution of liquif margine on small areas. Barrel trucks (3. left) or hook-on containers (1. right) for distribution of liquid margine on medium-size areas. Application to surfaces (2. right) and shallow introduction (3. right) for distribution of loiquid margine on large areas (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

These rows or strips are also worked with rotary demolition looseners. The incorporation does not differ from the incorporation of dry or pasty soil additives. The distribution in the soil is also

comparable when using the spade machines. The working depth should be based on the rooting depth so that the water is not lost too quickly to evaporation at the surface. This also improves nutrient availability. The liquid and solid soil additives are not applied throughout the year on the farms, but only in the period before sowing or planting. This means that the tankers are not needed in the fields all year round. This technique is universally applicable. For example, it can be used as a water wagon for irrigation or as a cattle trough.

This enables a high utilisation rate with low costs and additional income. Overall, the costs for spreading the liquid soil additives are relatively low.

5.10.3.4 Special machine combinations and process chains

Process chains (Figure 119 and Figure 120) for applying organic inputs are available for almost all farm sizes. Often, however, it makes sense to share machinery across farms to save costs and work more efficiently.

Also machine combination of static lift loosener and dynamic spade machine for targeted tillage of the soil to enrich and maintain soil carbon is possible (Figure 121).

Efficient technologies for big scales!

Figure 119: Structure of an efficient process chain for the application of organic soil additives on large areas or in large farms (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

Efficient technologies for small scales!

Figure 120: Structure of an efficient process chain for the application of organic soil additives on small areas or in small farms (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

Figure 121: Machine combination of static lift loosener and dynamic spade machine (Source: Hoogen, 2022)

5.10.4 Soil tillage soil additives as the basis for sustainable humus management, taking into account carbon accumulation and its assessment

Soil carbon has a special importance for securing yield capacity, increasing usable field capacity, as well as for CO₂ compensation by binding organic carbon in soils and vegetation, as options for long-term environmentally sound land management

The key to lasting success in agricultural management lies in the soil structure.

The aim is to compensate for CO₂ in the long term and on a significant scale through site-appropriate land management that includes annual and permanent crops as well as the establishment of agroforestry or alley cropping systems. The management systems are designed to generate not only CO₂ compensation but also ecosocial and ecological benefits on a relevant scale, so that this model project will also have a showcase effect for other regions. In the region, shallow, raw soils with low soil development and very low soil organic matter (C_{org} < 0.1 %) (lithic leptosols) are prevalent.

The new formation and storage of soil organic matter to be expected in the course of cultivation therefore starts from a very low initial level.

By using crop rotations and management practices appropriate to the site, a significant amount of CO₂ sequestration can be achieved. Convert CO₂ to carbon (in vegetation and soil): Carbon dioxide has a molar mass of 44 grams per mole - carbon has a molar mass of 12 grams per mole. This gives a mass ratio of CO₂ to carbon of $44/12 = 3.67$.

It is possible to safely store 3.0 to 4.0 tons of CO₂ per hectare per year in soils by simple means. Assuming an area of 5.0 ha to be managed for the first sequestration target of 150 t CO₂ per year, this would arithmetically mean a fixation of 8.17 t organic carbon per ha in biomass and soil (equivalent to 0.817 kg C_{org}/m²).

Assuming a soil storage density L_d of 1.8 (i.e. 1800 kg per m³), the organic carbon to be sequestered in the soil corresponds to about 0.045 mass% per year. If the soils contain about 0.1 mass-% at the beginning of cultivation, about 0.15 mass-% should be stored after one year.

It should be borne in mind that these are long-term stable fractions of soil organic matter, which is not to be mistaken with fresh organic matter, such as that which accumulates from harvest residues or is incorporated into the soils from the soil additives.

In addition, it must be taken into account that soils can hardly absorb and store more organic carbon permanently once a substrate-, climate- and management-dependent dynamic equilibrium has been reached. The type of cultivation and thus also the design of the crop rotation have a significant influence on this optimal level and must therefore be taken into account in the planning of the cultivation.

Soil organic matter is not only of interest in the context of CO₂ storage.

It is also of great importance for nutrient and water storage, structure formation, protection against substrate-induced recompaction after soil loosening measures, optimal rootability of the subsoil and subterranean plant growth.

Humus management is therefore pursued in a holistic approach in order to realise the desired ecological and economic goals in addition to optimal CO₂ sequestration. **Soil cultivation** is carried out with due consideration of the relevant effect structures and in accordance with the state of knowledge.

The aim is to establish long-term, robust cropping structures that follow a multifunctional approach and, in addition to economic aspects, also specifically meet eco-social requirements in the sense of the internationally agreed Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations (SDG). In order to achieve optimal CO₂ sequestration, the following measures are considered beneficial and should be taken into account in a holistic management and evaluation concept:

- Site-adapted crop rotations integrating perennial and annual crops, such as alfalfa, winter wheat, maize, and tree species in agroforestry areas.
- The aim is to establish "ideal types" of plants with a high root-to-shoot ratio.
- Use of modern irrigation technologies to ensure high yield levels while maintaining high carbon fixation in the root zone. Use of renewable water resources (especially snowmelt from nearby mountains)
- Cultivation and management systems optimized for organic carbon sequestration, avoiding uncontrolled runoff.
- Use of permanent humus preparations, especially organic acids (humic/fulvic acids), to promote organic matter accumulation.
- Use of soil loosening technologies for deep development of potential root space and to support humus accumulation also in the deeper mineral soil.
- Use of deep-rooting crop varieties for biological soil stabilization
- Removal of harvested material only, leaving plant residues/scattered material on site.
- Integrate grazing during the summer rest period.

In order to record the CO₂ compensation, the relevant reservoirs and fluxes for the system compartments are regularly recorded and balanced according to internationally established procedures.

On this basis, balancing is possible and internationally established assessment procedures can be applied transparently (Figure 122). Where necessary, these procedures are to be further developed and adapted for the specific locations.

Figure 122: Potentials for the permanent binding of CO₂ in soil carbon

Based on many years of experience in the development and optimization of agricultural systems in arid regions (e.g. Africa, Middle East, Central Asia) as well as in the restoration of landscapes after the extraction of raw materials, we have the necessary knowledge to achieve the goals of long-term environmentally sound land use with a focus on CO₂ compensation. The stated goals for CO₂ sequestration appear to be realistically achievable. Taking into account the above mentioned aspects, this project will be accompanied and supported by scientific and holistic consulting in order to achieve optimal results and to validate them with the help of internationally established assessment approaches..

5.10.5 Summary assessment of the technologies considered

Technical machines are available for technologies for the application of alternative substances and for preparatory soil applications, such as stone removal or hardpan destruction. The machines can be combined into multifunctional applications and adapted to the required size and performance.

The decision factor is the market price for the investment (Table 46). For small farms or farmers, it is advisable to work together in cooperatives, service companies and share machines.

Table 46: Investment costs, area output, labour costs for soil cultivation equipment in the Fès-Meknès Region

No.	Type of machine	Working depth cm	Working width cm	Working speed m/h	power requirement kW	Investment cost (only machine) EURO
1	Barrel	surface	50 – 300	300 – 1500	5 – 25	5,000 – 10,000
2	Spread on surface	surface	300 – 600	1500 – 6000	75 – 150	35,000 – 70,000
3	Shallow induction	5 – 10	300 – 600	1500 – 3000	150 – 250	50,000 – 100,000
4	Cultivator	10 – 30	150 – 600	3,500 - 12,000	90 – 350	5,000 – 150,000
5	Ripper	30 – 100	100 – 300	600 – 2500	75 – 250	5,000 – 25,000
6	Dynamic cut-lifter	50 – 90	250 – 300	500 – 2,500	250 – 350	90,000 – 125,000
7	Spading machines	25 - 135	100 – 450	150 – 3,000	25 – 500	15,000 – 150,000

6 Synthesis of the I-WALAMAR Analysis and Demonstration Projects

6.1 I-WALAMAR contribution to increase water and food security

M. Krauss et al.

Increasing water and food security in the Fès-Meknès region with residues from the olive oil industry, municipal wastewater treatment plants and innovations in agriculture have been researched and tested within the I-WALAMAR project.

In order to improve the knowledge on the recovery and removal of different phenols from olive industry residues, an HPLC analyzer was adapted to the specific needs of phenol analysis, implemented in Meknès and the scientific staff trained in its use. Different phenol fractions can now be identified, determined and extracted from different material streams. The measurement methodology has been successfully applied in various scientific studies.

A water monitoring station has been successfully developed to continuously determine the amount of olive oil wastewater in the influent of wastewater treatment plants or in water bodies. To this end, various tests were carried out at the Stolberg wastewater treatment plant near Aachen, Germany, and at the Aachen University of Applied Sciences laboratory to calibrate a sensor for the analysis of olive oil wastewater for the first time. The monitoring station will be installed in a wastewater treatment plant in Morocco during 2023 and will measure in addition to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) the parameters water level, temperature, conductivity, salinity, TDS, pH, water density, turbidity and TSS.

A water quality monitoring program and an exemplary pollution cadaster for olive mills have been developed. The Water Management Model WEAP was set-up for the Saïss Plain aquifer and four river basins of the FMR. Besides the current account scenario, five additional scenarios were integrated. These are the “Climate change scenario”, “population growth scenario”, “Land use change scenario”, the “Olive sector development scenario” and the “Water Infrastructure Project scenario” integrating the dam M’Dez. This enables the water management authority ABHS in cooperation with UMI to use and adapt the monitoring program and mathematical model for evidence-based decision making.

Investigations regarding the optimization of the 2-phase decanter process, to get a phenol-enriched phase by increasing the pH to 9-11 are very encouraging. The resulting phenol-enriched phase is a promising source for natural substances containing antioxidative and antimicrobial properties for food additives or used as oxidation protection and antimicrobial additive in materials. Most important is use of fresh pomace to obtain phenol-enriched substances.

Tubular membranes based on a clay from the Meknès region have been developed. The clay powder obtained after crushing and sieving was characterized by several experimental techniques to understand its behaviour according to the thermal treatment. This powder is used for

the manufacture of tubular membranes of high mechanical, chemical and purifying performances. The membranes could be successfully used for the filtration of a dye (Methyl Orange). The usage of these membranes is promising for increasing the quality of municipal wastewaters by pretreatment of wastewaters from the leather or textile industry.

Beside membrane filtration, adsorption of polyphenols on β -cyclodextrin (β CD)-modified materials was evaluated. The general procedure for this work was analysis of β CD-complexes, synthesis and characterization of β CD-containing materials and uptake studies with polyphenols from olive wastewater. The general procedure was the crosslinking of β CD with the compound epichlorohydrin (EP) in basic aqueous medium – in presence of Ghassoul clay or ground olive stone, respectively. This results in β CD-containing crosslinked polymer or corresponding composite with the above-mentioned natural materials. All materials lead to reduction of polyphenol concentration. Among the used model polyphenols, Hydroxytyrosol has the highest amount in the untreated wastewater followed by Oleuropein and Tyrosol. After treatment, the amount of the phenolic compounds decreases with usage of all samples. Polymer and polymer-modified Ghassoul as well as a Ghassoul-polymer mixture showed the best results in adsorption of the selected polyphenols.

I-WALAMAR partner SEBA developed and implemented a solar powered agro-meteorological station system to increase the up-to-date distribution of weather parameters to the farmer communities in the study area. Parameters which are recorded are

- Wind direction and wind speed
- Atmospheric pressure, air temperature, air humidity and solar radiation
- Precipitation
- Soil moisture and soil temperature at depths of 10cm, 20cm and 30cm
- The data is being transferred via GPRS modem and available through the browser-based online module at SEBA Hydrocenter (www.seba-hydrocenter.de)

Olive mill wastes and wastewater were assessed for its application as biogas feed material. Especially the dry waste material (pomace) showed high biogas yield with 178.6 l per kg added fresh mass (FM) according to the Hohenheim biogas yield protocol. Continuous biogas fermentation trials in digesters with 700 l and 560 l were performed. The experiment was run for 148 days in a row after months of pre-test. For the first 50 days the average specific methane yield (SMY) from olive pomace (without stone) was more than 395 L kgVS while feeding at OLR of 1.0 kgVS m⁻³ d⁻¹. The composition of methane in the biogas was 60 % - 65 %, which is common in substrates rich in fats/oils (VDI 4630). However, in the subsequent days of experiment the SMY declined steadily to the completion of the experiment. Same way the methane composition of the biogas was declined from peak value 72 % to 32 %. It seems that the increase in the concentration of sinapic acid might be one of the caused to the decline of the methane formation in the digester. One of the reasons for the decline of the biogas formation

might also be the deficiency of trace metals in the substrate itself. Thus, co-fermentation with other substrates especially animal manure seems to be promising. Co-fermentation of horse manure with liquid olive mill wastewater (margine) was successful. Biogas yields of 315 L/kg VS for horse manure and 120 L/kg VS for the co-digestion of margines highlight their viability as valuable feedstocks for anaerobic digestion. The methane content of 73 % for horse manure and 80 % for the co-digestion of margines indicates the high purity of the biogas, making it suitable for energy applications. These results emphasize the importance of exploring organic waste sources for biogas generation, contributing to the shift towards renewable energy and reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

As part of the work package “soil improving additives” the aim was to develop hydrogel-based soil additives, which act as a water saving reservoir for soils in mainly arid regions as in the Fès-Meknès area. The water absorbing properties make hydrogels interesting for saving and using the resource water effectively, enable plant cultivation and improve plant health and growth. The main goal was the development and synthesis of hydrogels based on poly(aspartic acid) (PASP) as a new alternative to poly(acrylic acid)-based products for future commercial products. PASP provide the possibility to obtain main reactants from renewable resources in contrast to mineral oil resources and reported better biodegradability in contrast to the reported poor degradability of poly(acrylic acid). The main result is the formation of hydrogel from the PASP/LYS copolymer without additional crosslinking., this eliminates an additional reaction and work-up step in the reaction. Based on this, the reaction needs further optimization (already from copolymerization of ASP and LYS) but is very promising regarding ecological and economic aspects. Biodegradability was analyzed and pot-experiments of PASP-based products showed good results in comparison to PAA-based hydrogels. Tri polymer type as soil additive in the project I-WALAMAR can be considered successful. Nevertheless, further work must be done; main aspects are price, upscaling, reaction optimization (solvent-free, „green“) and fine-tuning for specific site-dependent properties. Tests at UHOH showed that the water-holding capacity of the developed hydrogels proved to be equal to those available in the market. Moreover, the results showed that the tested hydrogel types had no phytotoxic effect on cress germination and seedling growth. Furthermore, moistening the substrates with different concentrations of OMWW, especially those containing low phenolic content, seems safe for agricultural use.

Trials aimed to investigate if the application of OMWW in a drip irrigation system causes clogging of the irrigation drippers and/or purification filters were performed. It was found that no significant change in flow rate (FR) was observed between OMWW concentrations of 30 % and 50 %. Throughout all experimental runs, no visible blockages at the irrigation drippers were observed. Concerning the leakage of phenols from the OMWW, based on quantitative analysis of the percolate, the one-time utilization of volumes of OMWW up to 120 m³ ha⁻¹ on

slightly loamy sand, given a groundwater level lower than 1 m, does not carry a short-term risk of groundwater contamination.

Field trials to investigate the impact of the contribution of margines as soil additives on onion and melon crops, by determining the optimal dose of margines to obtain an optimal yield in terms of quantity and quality were performed over two years. The total plot area used for this study was 880m² for both years; it was prepared to accommodate a complete randomized block design. The dosage tested were “T1 : No OMWW added”, “T2 : OMWW dose = 140 L = 25 m³/ha”, “T3 : OMWW dose = 280 L = 50 m³/ha” and “T4 : OMWW dose = 420 L = 75 m³/ha”. We can conclude that the use of margines has affected the physiological parameters in the first year of trial, contrary to the yield, where no effect was found. On the other hand, in the second year of the trial, the physiological parameters were not affected. However, there was an increment in yield with the addition of higher margine doses. Regardless, this can only be confirmed after a third year, as it takes time for mineralization to determine the actual effect of margines on the soil characteristics. It should be noted that physical and chemical soil analyses are being processed.

Hydrogels have been applied as an amendment product to increase the water-holding capacity of the soil on filed trials at ENA in Meknès. It can be noted that the use of hydrogels without deficit irrigation resulted in 27 % increase in yield compared to the control treatment irrigated with 100 % of water requirements for the melon crop and an increase of 18 % for the onion crop. Furthermore, the deficit treatments with 50 % ET_c combined with hydrogel application, showed an increase in yield by 13 % compared to the deficit control treatment with 50 % Etc and no hydrogel application for the melon crop and 12 % increase for the onion crop. From this result, it is confirmed that the amount of hydrogel added has a significant impact on the increase of melon production even in the presence of a water deficit of 50 % compared to the control treatments. Hydrogels allowed water saving without affecting the yield. Additional experiments with hydrogels were performed in a greenhouse, supported the conclusion, that a 50 % deficit irrigation can be compensated with the application of hydrogels.

Machines are available for technologies for the application of alternative substances and for preparatory soil applications, such as stone removal or hardpan destruction. The machines can be combined into multifunctional applications and adapted to the required size and performance. The decision factor for choosing the appropriate method is the market price for the investment. For small farms or farmers, it is advisable to work together in cooperatives, service companies and share machines. Within this report a guide can be found on selecting the appropriate land application technique for the developed soil additives.

The results of I-WALAMAR showed the high potential for reusing waste and wastewater streams and innovative soil additives, such as hydrogels with enhanced biodegradability, to improve water and food security in the FMR. It demonstrates how these streams can be treated

and safely applied to agriculture to improve the resilience of the population to climate change. With appropriate land application technologies and biogas production from the waste stream, a contribution to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions can be achieved.

6.2 Assessment of the socio-economic effects on the resource management in the FMR, Morocco: Olive Mill Residues

(B. Kemmerling, R. Navarro, L. Wirkus)

The three types of oil mills identified have different scopes of actions when it comes to the reuse and recycling of the olive pomace and olive mill wastewater. As a matter of fact, agribusinesses, and, to a lesser extent, small and medium-sized investors have capital to invest in technologies that use less resources and produce less residues, such as the two-phase decanter. Moreover, for agribusinesses, in particular, it is attractive to invest in a circular economy in order to revalorise the residues and generate additional profits. With regard to olive pomace, this is already taking place. What is interesting here, is, that this circular economy is also a social circle, from which also those oil mills benefit that have not the capacities to invest in this treatment. Here, the basis is laid for a better revalorisation of the olive pomace, in which more oil mills could participate and of which all oil mills could benefit. In contrast, there is no such circular solution for the olive mill wastewater. Basically, each oil mill operator is responsible on his own for the appropriate treatment of the olive mill wastewater, which leads to different strategies, which are often economically inefficient, environmentally problematic, and bear the potential for social conflict.

6.3 Assessment of the regional acceptance of the proposed changes and the effects on the stakeholders' involvement in the FMR, Morocco

(B. Kemmerling, R. Navarro, L. Wirkus)

We found that financial capacity is not the only factor for adopting innovative technologies; there are also cultural preferences for certain olive oil types. Parts of the local population prefers olive oil from olive oil presses and often also the Moroccan olive varieties. Since small family-driven oil mills and medium-sized mills of investors produce for the local, regional, and national markets, these cultural preferences may be decisive for their choice of technology. In contrast, large oil mills usually affiliated to agribusinesses mainly produce for export, using the two-phase decanter system in order to align with the international quality standards. All three types generate varying forms and quantities of residues. We found that there are existing socio-economic links for the resource management of solid residues. Large industrial mills have the technological capacities to post-process olive press cake (OPC), investing in a circular economy where solid residues are used as fuel in specialized plants. Small and medium-sized mills sell their OPC to large industrial mills, making all involved actors profit from

the resource management cycle. Interviews with research participants from all different olive mill types expressed an overall satisfaction with this system; especially many of the operators from small and medium-sized mills mentioned that the selling of the OPC is an important revenue source.

All production systems share to a greater or lesser extent the problem of olive mill wastewater (OMWW) generation. While some olive oil mill operators who also have olive groves mentioned that they apply OMWW in small quantities as a herbicide or liquid fertilizer on their olive orchards, there are others that are reticent to this practice and would prefer to have scientific evidence of the safety of this method. Most research participants explained that they collect OMWW in evaporation ponds with no further usage. However, having evaporation ponds fulfilling the volume and safety standards requires financial means and land resources and some interviewees expressed the opinion that the state should be responsible for providing them to enable a safe disposal.

Hence, the acceptance of resource management systems depends on three main factors:

- i) access to financial and natural resources: industrial businesses and family-driven mills have higher chances of having enough land for such ponds than medium-sized mills, where the investors have to buy the land or an existing mill. However, operators of small mills and also some of the medium-sized mills might lack the financial resources to apply safe and appropriate treatment of the OMWW.
- (ii) the production rate: larger producers, especially industrial oil mills, but also medium-sized mills have higher amounts of residues and thus need larger ponds. Small mills enterprises produce smaller quantities of OMWW and some of them reuse parts of it as a fertilizing mixture on their own land, although most operators and farmers have called for more scientific evidence in applying OMWW on fields.
- (iii) and the identification with the local production area: investors of medium-sized mills often come from other regions and despite often having the financial means, they might lack the motivation for appropriate disposal and see the state as responsible for solving the OMWW problem.

For the innovations envisaged in the project, the following initial conclusions emerge:

First: Technologies must be adapted to the local context; for example, the widespread introduction of modern technologies (two-phase decanter) would lead to a reduction in residues but is unlikely to be introduced by all types of oil mills against the background of cultural preferences and socio-economic capacities. Second, the upgrading of residues is of particular interest to industrial oil mills; however, there is a need for further research and development for a sustainable solution regarding the treatment and utilisation of liquid residues

(OMWW). Third, the introduction of technologies is political; in order to avoid potential conflicts. Different groups of actors (various oil mill operators, agricultural actors, and state institutions) must be involved, because they have diverse interests and capacities.

We suggest that the socio-economic links existing in the circular economy model used for solid residues can serve as a base for constructing a model for OMWW treatment by creating attractivity for all actors involved:

- 1\ given the dispersion of actors among those with the lower financial means, it seems to be recommendable to seek for associative solutions, such as the creation of communal evaporation ponds at cooperative level. The government plays a key role to support those associations.
- 2\ Investing in research about the effects of applying OMWW and irrigation water mixtures on land to avoid risks from excessive disposal through this channel, and if the application is beneficial, encourage such forms of reuse. It is necessary to involve stakeholders, above all farmers, in the research process for successful implementation.
- 3\ If a technology is developed for upgrading the OMWW, it could be recommendable to pay producers for the delivered OMWW, as it occurs with solid residues already.

6.4 Assessment of the IWALAMAR Results' Relevance on the UN-Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)

(M. Krauss, W. Kirchhof)

The I-WALAMAR joint project has been able to open the way for the achievement of a considerable number of UN-Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (see Figure 123). While many of the project objectives could not be completely implemented by the time when this report was written, there is a high potential for contributing to sustainable development by the here developed technologies in the near future.

Figure 123: SDG wheel with indicated goals that relate to IWALAMAR project goals

6.4.1 SDG 2: Zero Hunger

The technologies developed and tested in the I-WALAMAR project contribute to the SDG 2, “Zero Hunger”, by increasing water use efficiency and hereby productivity in agriculture and food production systems which is a crucial aspect for achieving resilience in the veil of climate change. This addresses target 2.4 “by 2030 ensure sustainable food production systems and implement resilient agricultural practices that increase productivity and production, that help maintain ecosystems, that strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change, extreme weather, drought, flooding and other disasters, and that progressively improve land and soil quality.”

6.4.2 SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation

One important matter that has been identified in the project and needs to be further addressed is the treatment of olive mill wastewater. First experiments for its usage and application for sustainable agricultural practices are currently carried out. If successful, this may help to reduce wastewater flows from olive production and eventually decrease illegal spills into valuable water resources, setting the path for fulfilling target 6.3. Other technologies tested in the project with the aim of increasing water use efficiency are in line with target 6.4. The project has also pursued improving integrated water resource management, achieving target 6.5. All in all, the tested innovations can indirectly lead to healthier water-related ecosystems, especially rivers and aquifers, by increasing water use efficiency and reducing polluting

residues, which contributes to achieving target 6.6. The project included several workshops and trainings involving local partners in the improvement of water resource management related activities, accomplishing target 6.a.

Furthermore, as described in the recommendations for better acceptance of the new technologies, involving local stakeholders seems to be essential for successful implementation. If this recommendation can be applied, target 6.b can also be achieved.

6.4.3 SDG 7: Affordable and clean energy

The IWALAMAR group has cooperated with various industrial partners from Germany, Spain, and Morocco. The international research project has created further bilateral cooperations in the field of the water, energy food nexus water (SDG target 7.1).

6.4.4 SDG 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure

The research and findings carried out within the I-WALAMAR project can be key to improve the knowledge in industrial wastewater treatment in the olive oil sector, e.g. by the application of the newly introduced separation process. The reduction of polyphenol compounds makes the pomace more valuable when it is used as soil improving material. By enriching with polyphenols, the olive oil wastewater is a more valuable resource to obtain polyphenols that can be used as antioxidants.

6.4.5 SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities

Although poverty has been successfully reduced in the last decades, rural communities are still among the most affected population groups. The research and findings carried out within the I-WALAMAR project can contribute significantly to improving the living conditions of different actors in agriculture and increasing incomes in this population group. The existing socio-economic links can be used to implement additional circular economy solutions that involve and benefit all stakeholders and help reduce inequality, which would be in line with target 10.1.

6.4.6 SDG 12: Responsible Consumption & Production

The I-WALAMAR project is focused on efficient integrated water resource management and improvements in the local food industry, addressing SDG 12. The technologies and approaches tested aim to reduce environmental threats caused by waste from the agrofood industry and to protect valuable water resources, as it is described in target 12.4. Their focus lies on waste reduction, recycling and reuse, which fulfills target 12.5. Finally, large companies have been involved in the process of waste material treatment and recycling, which can further lead to the fulfillment of target 12.6.

6.4.7 SDG 13: Climate action

The Saïss region is already suffering the consequences of climate change through reduced rainfall. By increasing water use efficiency, recycling water resources and creating circular economy models for appropriate waste management, the innovations tested and developed within the I-WALAMAR project can help address climate-related hazards, Especially those related to water scarcity. This aligns with target 13.1.

6.4.8 SDG 17: Partnerships for the goals

Finally, the whole project was carried out sharing knowledge on technology, innovation and access to scientific research through international cooperation. The aim was to promote the transfer and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies, thereby accomplishing targets 17.6 and 17.7.

6.5 Comparative study between the Fès-Meknès Region (FMR) and the Marrakesch Region (MR) in Morocco regarding the acceptance of changes

(R. Navarro, B. Kemmerling, L. Wirkus

Super intensive olive plantations mainly use olive varieties intended for export-oriented production and use the two-phase decanter process for production. They have to fulfill international market standards. Small family businesses that produce for local markets or for their own consumption, in contrast, cultivate and produce in the traditional way. They prefer to use Moroccan olive varieties and traditional olive mill presses.

Assuming that olive cultivation patterns can be linked to the different types of mills identified in the olive oil producing industry, it is possible to use land use maps as a proxy for identifying regions with high potential for technology adoption.

Based on regional cultivation statistics confirmed by preliminary land use analyses, we found that olive production in the Marrakech-Safi Region has a higher share of superintensive and intensive olive cultivation compared to the FMR.

In the FMR, even more than 86 % of olive cultivation is done on rainfed land (305,426 ha), while in the Marrakech-Safi Region, for example, the situation is reverse; more than 77 % of olive cultivation is irrigated (Fellah trade 2022).

The overall production of olives is in the same order of magnitude in both regions, leading to a similar production of olive mill waste products. As super intensive plantations are more common in the Marrakech-Safi region, it can be assumed that there are also more modern two-phase and three-phase mills.

Due to the fact that there are more irrigated plantations in the Marrakech-Safi region, the need for water-efficient solutions such as hydrogels is also higher.

In summary, it can be stated that a transfer of the I-WALAMAR technologies from the Féz-Meknés-Region to the Marrakech-Safi Region is promising.

Table 47: Cultivation areas (ha) and production (t) of irrigated and rainfed olive plantations in the FMR compared to the Marrakech-Safi Region. Source: MAPM 2020 in Fella trade 2022

	Rainfed		Irrigated	
	Surface (ha)	Production (t)	Surface	Production
FMR	305,426	456,957	47,151	170,769
Marrakech-Safi	50,691	28,419	172,952	459,098

7 Publications of I-WALAMAR

Publications – peer-reviewed journals and book chapters

2022

Krauss, M.; Risse, H.; Kirchhof, W.; Möller, J.; Jomaa, A.; Weber, F.-A. (2022): Wasserwiederverwertung und integriertes Stoffstrommanagement in Tunesien und Marokko. 20 – 24; Wasser und Abfall 05 | 2022

2023

Navarro, R.; Wirkus, L.; Dubovyk, O.: Spatio-Temporal Assessment of Olive Orchard Intensification in the Saïss Plain (Morocco) Using k-Means and High-Resolution Satellite Data. Remote Sens. **2023**, 15, 50. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15010050>

2024

Hafidi, Y.; El Hatka H.; Schmitz, D.; Krauss, M.; Pettrak, J.; Biel, M.; Ittobane, N.: Sustainable Soil Additives for Water and Micronutrient Supply: Swelling and Chelating Properties of Polyaspartic Acid Hydrogels Utilizing Newly Developed Crosslinkers. Gels 2024, 10(3), 170; <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels10030170>

2024

El Bergui O., Abouabdillah A, Bouriouq M., Schmitz D., Biel M., Aboudrare A., Krauss K., Jomaa A., Romuli S., Mueller J., Fagroud M. and Bouabid R.: Innovative Solutions for Drought: Evaluating Hydrogel Application on Onion Cultivation (*Allium cepa*) in Morocco. Water 2023,15, 1972. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w15111972>

Publications – expert and public audience

2021

Kemmerling, B. (2021): Forschung für ein nachhaltiges Land- und Wassermanagement im ländlichen Marokko, Blog - Ziele für Nachhaltige Entwicklung - Agenda 2030 der UN (17ziele.de)

2022

El-Kordy, A.; Douma, M.; Bouazizl, A.; **Tijani, N.** (2022): Experimental study of phenol removal from aqueous solution by adsorption onto synthesized Faujssite-type Y zeolite; published by Univeristy of Mouley Ismail. Faculty of Sciences Meknès

Houdret, A.; **Kemmerling, B.**; Ines Dombrowsky, I. (2022): Wie Grundwasserübernutzung und Gesellschaftsverträge zusammenhängen, German Development Institute / Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik (DIE), Die aktuelle Kolumne, 21.03.2022, Wie Grundwasserübernutzung und Gesellschaftsverträge zusammenhängen (idos-research.de)

Oral Presentations and Abstracts

2019

Kemmerling, B.; Bouzidi, Z.; Wirkus, L. (2019): “Contemporary Transformation in Moroccan Agricultural Policies: The case of olive production in the Fès-Meknès region”. ISA Conference „Africa and the Middle East and North Africa: Understandin Paradoxical Outcomes of Contemporary Transformations” 23-25 Juni 2020, accepted, conference was cancelled due to COVID-19

2020

Kemmerling, B. (2020): Sustainable Transformations in Rural Morocco - the I-WALAMAR project, UNU-FLORES, TU Dresden und Universität Bonn: International Water Colloquium, 16.12.2020

Kemmerling, B. (2020): Sustainable Transformations in Rural Morocco - the I-WALAMAR project, Launch of the Bonn Water Network, 17.11.2020

2021

Glasow, V. (2021): Measuring the impact of policies on the number and size of surface water reservoirs for agricultural irrigation in the Saïss plain with satellite data. Geomatics Workshop organized by the Remote Sensing Research Group (RSRG) and the Center for Remote Sensing and Land Surfaces (ZFL) of the University of Bonn, June 2021.

Kemmerling, B. (2021): Potentials and challenges for innovation in introducing a circular economy in the Fès and Meknès Region, Morocco, GWOPA international congress, 21.10.2021

Kemmerling, B. (2021): Olivenölproduktion in Marokko – Nachhaltige Technologien für alle?, VHS (adult education center) Bonn, 10.11.2021

Navarro, R. (2021): Olive Orchard Intensification in the Saïss Plain, Morocco. A Multi-Scale Approach in a Data-Scarce Environment. Geomatics Workshop organized by the Remote Sensing Research Group (RSRG) and the Center for Remote Sensing and Land Surfaces (ZFL) of the University of Bonn, June 2021.

2022

Navarro, R.; Wirkus, L.; Dubovyk, O. (2022): Spatio-Temporal Assessment of Olive Orchard Intensification in the Saïss Plain (Morocco): A Customized Approach Using Multi-Scale Remote Sensing Data. Oral presentation at the European Space Agency, Living Planet Symposium 2022, Bonn, May 2022.

Kemmerling, B. (2022): Opportunities and risks of technical solutions for sustainable groundwater management in Morocco, Bonn Water Network Webinar 'Digging Deeper: How to address groundwater challenges in the Middle East and North Africa?', 23.03.2022

Poster Presentations

2023

Krauss, Manuel; Abouabdillah, Aziz; El Bergui, Omnia; Schmitz, Dominik; Biel, Markus; Aboudrare, Abdellah et al. (2023): Wastewater residues and hydrogel application: Pathways to increase water and food security in Morocco? Tropentag 2023. Berlin, 21.09.2023. Online verfügbar unter https://www.tropentag.de/2023/abstracts/links/Krauss_QgJyGD5i.php,

2022

Allaoui, S.; Schmitz, D.; Maaroufi, A.; Biel, M.; Bennani, M.; **Ittobane, N.** (2022): Analysis of and adsorption on betaCD-modified materials of polyphenols from residuals from olive oil productions; International Mid-Term Workshop of the I-WALAMAR project in Mèknés. March 2022

El Bergui, O.; **Abouabdillah, A.**; Aboudrare, A.; Tabit, S.; Taibi, I.; Dhaidhi, H.; Schmitz, D.; Spohrer, K.; Romuli, S.; Müller, J. (2022): The response of crops (Onion and melon) to the combines use of hydrogels and deficit irrigation; International Mid-Term Workshop of the I-WALAMAR project in Mèknés. March 2022

El Bergui, O.; **Abouabdillah, A.**; Aboudrare, A.; El Marghani, M.; Ouzahra, L.; Schmitz, D.; Spohrer, K.; Romuli, S.; Müller, J. (2022): The response of crops (Onion and melon) to the use of margines; International Mid-Term Workshop of the I-WALAMAR project in Mèknés. March 2022

El Hafiane, F.; Hafidi, M.; Rhallabi, N.; Hajjaj, H.; Badidi, M.; Tabib, M. (2022): Characterization of by-products from Ain Taoujdate WWTP and impact on water resources quality; International Mid-Term Workshop of the I-WALAMAR project in Mèknés. March 2022

El Hafyani, M.; Alitane, A.; Ijlil, S.; Essahlaoui, A.; Ramirez, J.; Meiners, G. (2022): Intergrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) in the Saïss Plain. Morocco; International Mid-Term Workshop of the I-WALAMAR project in Mèknés. March 2022

El-Kordy, A.; Allaoui, S.; Messaoudi, L.; Tuani, N.; Messaoudi, M. (2022): Manufacturing and characterization of flat and tubular membranes prepared from natural Moroccan clay. Application to clarification of textile wastewater; International Mid-Term Workshop of the I-WALAMAR project in Mèknés. March 2022

- Grimmeisen, F. (2022): Development of a micro-climate Monitoring Station for agriculture in Northern Africa; International Mid-Term Workshop of the I-WALAMAR project in Mèknès. March 2022
- Hafidi, Y.; Schmitz, D.; Sternad, A.; Faraji, M.; Cremer, P.; Ittobane, N.; Pettrak, J.; Biel, M. (2022): Bio-based and-degradable poly (aspartic acid)-based hydrogels as sustainable materials for soil additives; International Mid-Term Workshop of the I-WALAMAR project in Mèknès. March 2022
- Navarro, R.; Wirkus, L.; Dubovyk, O. (2022): Rural transformations in the Fès and Mèknès region (FMR); International Mid-Term Workshop of the I-WALAMAR project in Mèknès. March 2022

Doctoral Theses

Exchange of PhD students during doctoral studies:

- Allaoui, Safae (2021): Removal of phenolic compounds onto column filtration and deposited polymer onto ceramic support. supervised by Prof. Bennani Mohammed (UMI), Prof. Ittobane Najim (UMI); Biel, M. (FHAC); Dr. Schmitz, D. (FHAC)
- Hafidi, Youssef (2021): Hydrogels for soil additives based on biodegradable crosslinked poly (aspartic acid) with newly developed crosslinkers. Supervised by Prof. Ittobane Najim (UMI); Biel, M. (FHAC); Dr. Schmitz, D. (FHAC)

Master Theses (Diplôme d' ingénieur)

2021

- Möller, J. (2021): Stoffstrombilanzierung und Szenarienentwicklung zur Wiederverwendung von Rückständen aus der Olivenölproduktion am Beispiel der Fès-Meknès-Region in Marokko. translated: Material Flow Analysis and Scenario Development for the Reuse of Residues from Olive Oil Production Using the Example of the Fès-Meknès Region in Morocco. Supervised by Univ.-Prof. Dr.-Ing. habil. Wintgens., T.; Dr.-Ing. Montag, D.; Krauss, M.; Ramirez, J.
- Navarro, R. (2021): Spatio-temporal assessment of olive orchard intensification in the Saiss Plain (Morocco): A customized approach using multi-scale satellite remote sensing data. Supervised by PD Dr. Dubovyk, O. and Dipl.-Geogr. Wirkus, L.

2022

- Badidi, **Marwa** (2022): Evaluation de l'impact du rejet des eaux usées traitées sur la qualité des ressources en eaux: Cas de Ain Taoujdate. translated: Evaluation of the impact of treated wastewater discharge on the quality of water resources: Case of Ain Taoujdate). Supervised by Pr. Berday, N.; Pr. Elhafiane, F.; Pr. Benaouda, T.; Dr. Boufala, M'Hamed
- Glasow, V. (2022): Spatial and Temporal Analysis of Artificial Water Bodies: A Case Study in the Changing Agriculture of the Saiss Plain, Morocco. Supervised by PD Dr. Dubovyk, O. and Prof. Greve, K.
- Fasna Hajjaj (2022): Caractérisation des sous-produits de traitement des eaux usées en vue d'une valorization verte. translated: Characterization of wastewater treatment by-products for green valorization. Supervised by Pr. Lahlou, O.; **El Hafiane, F.**; Tlemcani, N.; Nasrellah, H.
- Tabib **Manal** (2022): Utilisation des margines pour la fertilisation en agriculture: Potentialités et contraintes pour les ressources en sols et en eaux (Cas d'OLEAFOOD). Use of margines for fertilization in agriculture: Potentials and constraints for soil and water resources (Case of OLEAFOOD). Supervised by Pr. Sebari, K.; Pr. Elhafiane, F.; Pr. Essaghi, S.; Ouzahra, L. (2022)

Bachelor Theses

2019

- El Bouazzaoui; Hafssa (2019): Gestion des sous-produits pour une production et une transformation durable des olives au Maroc (Cas de la region Fè-Meknès). Supervised by Prof. El Hafiane, Fatiha; Prof. Soudi Brahim (IAV Hassan II)

2021

- Alitane Abdennabi (2021): Gestion des sous-produits pour une production et une transformation durable des olives au Maroc (cas de la Région Fès-Meknès) (Management of by-products for sustainable

- olive production and processing in Morocco (case of the Fez-Meknès Region); Supervised by Prof. Essahlaoui, Ali (UMI); Dr.-Ing. Meiners, H.-G.; Ramirez, J.
- El Hafyani. Mohammed (2021): Resources Management case study Cadastral survey of the oil mills in the province of Meknes and province of El Hajeb. Supervised by Prof. Essahlaoui Ali (UMI); Dr.-Ing. Meiners, H.-G.; Ramirez, J.
- Ijlil. Safae (2021): Integrated water resources management case study in the province of Meknès. Supervised by Prof. Essahlaoui, Ali (UMI); Dr.-Ing. Meiners, H.-G.; Ramirez, J.
- Lahnafi. Adnane (2021): Optimization of the flat microfiltration using clay composite membranes. Supervised by Prof. Tijani, Najib (UMI); Biel, M. (FHAC); Dr. Schmitz, D. (FHAC)
- Messaoui. Mohammed (2021): Manufacturing tubular membranes from clays and using them for filtration of dyes and heavy metals. Supervised by Prof. Ittobane Najim (UMI)
- Othmane. Saaoud (2021): Synthese und Charakterisierung von β -Cyclodextrin funktionalisierten Polymeren zu Aufnahme von Polyphenolen. Supervised by Prof. Biel, M. (FHAC); Dr. Schmitz, D. (FHAC)
- Thevis. Stephan (2021): Herstellung von Polysuccinimid aus Asparaginsäure mit unterschiedlicher Molmasse und deren Auswirkungen auf die Eigenschaften eines Superabsorbers. Supervised by Prof. Biel, M. (FHAC); Dipl.-Chem.-Ing. Dipl.-Wirt.-Ing. Frese, M. (FHAC)

2022

- Akarai. Salima (2022): Einbau von Pflanzenrückständen aus der Olivenölproduktion in Polyasparaginsäure-basierte Hydrogele zur stofflichen Verwertung. Supervised by Prof. Biel, M. (FHAC); Dr. Schmitz, D. (FHAC)
- El Baz. Soufyane (2022): Adsorptionseigenschaften von Cyclodextrin-funktionalisierten Materialien zur Aufnahme von Polyphenolen in Abhängigkeit von verschiedenen Faktoren. Supervised by Prof. Biel, M. (FHAC); Dr. Schmitz, D. (FHAC)
- Faraji. Maha (2022): Entwicklung eines Verfahrens zur Bewertung der biologischen Abbaubarkeit von Hydrogelen. Supervised by Prof. Pettrak, J. (FHAC); Dr. Schmitz, D. (FHAC)
- Jamia. Oussama (2022): Labortechnische Untersuchungen von kommerziellen Hydrogel-basierten Bodenverbessern und ein Vergleich mit neu entwickelten Materialien. Supervised by Prof. Biel, M. (FHAC); Dr. Schmitz, D. (FHAC)
- Kaul. Yasin (2022): Quantifizierung von Polyphenolen in Reststoffen der Olivenölproduktion. Supervised by Prof. Biel, M. (FHAC); Dr. Schmitz, D. (FHAC)

8 Literature

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9 APPENDIX (Attachments)

Figure A1: Dependency of reaction conditions on polymer yield, Mn and structure (Schmitz, 2022)

Project Partners

German Partners

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